

The Role of Deepfake Technology in Voice Phishing Attacks: Emerging threats and Cyber Security Countermeasures

This project investigates the role of deepfake voice technology in the evolution of vishing attacks, focusing on the interaction between AI capabilities and human behavioural vulnerabilities. A mixed-methods approach was used, combining fraud datasets, questionnaire findings, and real-world case study analysis. The results identify a clear gap between user awareness and secure behaviour, while demonstrating that AI enhances traditional social engineering techniques. Based on these findings, a dual framework of mitigation strategies for both individuals and organisations are proposed. The study concludes that AI-enabled vishing represents a growing cybersecurity threat requiring combined technological and behavioural countermeasures.

Charlie Russell
(Student)
5238095@student.gloscol.ac.uk
Computing Department
Gloucestershire
College

Dr Michael Okeke
(Supervisor)
okekem@gloscol.ac.uk
Computing Department
Gloucestershire
College

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

Advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have significantly reshaped the cybersecurity landscape, enabling both innovative opportunities and increasingly complex cyber threats (WEF, 2024). Among these developments, deepfake technology, capable of producing highly realistic synthetic audio, video and images, has emerged as a particularly disruptive force with researchers warning that its misuse is escalating rapidly across multiple domains (Chesney & Citron, 2019). As this technology becomes more accurate and widely accessible, cybercriminals are adapting it to enhance traditional forms of social engineering, creating new and more convincing attack vectors that exploit trust, authority and human vulnerability (Mirsky & Lee, 2021)

This research project examines one of the most concerning developments within this field that being the use of deepfake voice technology in voice phishing or vishing attacks. These attacks combine AI-driven impersonation with psychological manipulation to deceive victims into revealing sensitive information, performing unauthorised actions or compromising organisational security (Pindrop, 2020), recent incidents show that deepfake enabled voice impersonation has already resulted in major financial losses and operational disruptions, highlighting the increasing severity of this emerging threat (Europol, 2023). Despite these issues, studies indicate that awareness of synthetic voice threats remains limited among both general users and some cybersecurity professionals. (WEF, 2024)

This project adopts a hybrid methodology for its approach, integrating a quantitative questionnaire, qualitative open-ended questions, Dataset and real-world case study analysis to build a comprehensive understanding of deepfake enabled vishing. This approach aligns with recommendations from cybersecurity researchers who emphasise the need to analyse both the technical mechanisms of deepfakes and the human factors that influence susceptibility to social engineering attacks (Abroshan et al, 2021; Jagatic et al, 2007). Through assessing awareness levels, evaluating countermeasures and exploring the psychological strategies used by attackers, the research aims to produce practical, evidence-based guidance for reducing risk.

Overall, this study contributes to a growing body of work examining AI-driven impersonation threats and supports the researcher's development of advanced skills in cyber threat analysis, research methodology and security evaluation. The following sections provide the background to the topic, outline the study's objectives, present the rationale for the research and describe the structure of the project.

1.1 BACKGROUND

1.1.1 PHISHING IN THE MODERN CYBER LANDSCAPE

Phishing is one of the most persistent and effective cybercrime techniques, continuing to pose a significant threat to individuals and organisations despite decades of security awareness efforts. At its core, phishing involves deceptive communication designed to impersonate a legitimate entity to manipulate victims into revealing sensitive information, transferring funds, or granting unauthorised access to systems (Jagatic et al, 2007). Unlike purely technical attacks, phishing exploits human psychology, making it particularly difficult to eliminate through technological controls alone.

Modern phishing attacks leverage well established social engineering principles, including authority, urgency, fear and trust. Attackers frequently impersonate trusted figures such as employees, financial institutions or government agencies to create a sense of legitimacy and pressure victims into rapid compliance (Abroshan et al, 2021). Research shows that even technically knowledgeable users can be vulnerable when cognitive biases are triggered, particularly under time pressure or emotional stress (Jagatic et al, 2007) this human centric nature of phishing explains its continued success despite improvements in spam filtering and detection technologies.

The contemporary cyber landscape has further amplified the effectiveness of phishing due to digital transformation and changing communication habits. The widespread adoption of remote work, cloud services and online collaboration tools has increased reliance on digital and voice-based communication, expanding the attack surface available to cybercriminals (WEF, 2024). Employees are now accustomed to receiving instructions, payment requests and security

alerts through email, messaging platforms and phone calls, making malicious communications harder to distinguish from legitimate ones.

As well as this, phishing has evolved from isolated attacks into coordinated, multi-channel campaigns. Attackers increasingly combine email phishing with SMS messages, social media interactions and voice calls to reinforce credibility and bypass suspicion (Abroshan et al, 2021). This convergence of attack vectors allows adversaries to build trust over time and exploit multiple points of failure within organisational communication workflows. As a result, phishing is no longer a low effort attack method but a sophisticated threat that adapts rapidly to defensive measures.

As artificial intelligence becomes more integrated into cybercrime, phishing continues to evolve in complexity and realism. AI generated text, automated targeting and voice synthesis technologies are transforming traditional phishing into highly personalised and convincing attacks (WEF, 2024). These developments lay the foundation for advanced threats such as deepfake enabled vishing, where attackers move beyond written deception to exploit the inherent trust placed in human voice communication.

1.1.1.1 EVOLUTION OF SOCIAL ENGINEERING AND EMERGING VOICE THREATS

Phishing has evolved from simple, generic mass emails to highly targeted and multilayered attacks. Early phishing campaigns in the 1990s and early 2000s relied heavily on low quality messages and basic deception techniques (Jagatic et al, 2007) As cybercriminals adapted to improved user awareness, phishing shifted towards spear-phishing, where attackers use personal or organisational information to appear more credible (Abroshan et al, 2021). The increasing use of automation, Ai generates content and multi-channel delivery, including social media, SMS and voice calls, has expanded phishing into a comprehensive ecosystem of threat vectors (WEF, 2024). The shift from text-based deception to voice-based manipulation marks a major evolution in attacker strategies, allowing deepfake audio to exploit inherent trust in vocal communication.

1.1.2 DEEPFAKE TECHNOLOGY: CAPABILITIES AND RISKS

Deepfake technology leverages advanced machine learning techniques, particularly Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and transformer-based models to create synthetic media that convincingly mimics real individuals (Chesney & Citron, 2019). Audio deepfakes are now capable of replicating speech patterns, tone, accent and even emotional cues using only minimal recorded input (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018). While deepfakes have potential applications in entertainment, accessibility and digital communication, their misuse poses significant risk and threats in identity fraud, misinformation, impersonation as well as cyber enabled crim (Mirsky & Lee, 2021)

1.1.2.1 EVOLUTION OF DEEPFAKE TECHNOLOGY

The evolution of deepfake technology reflects significant advances in machine learning:

- **Early manipulation (Pre-2015)** – Initial digital forgeries relied on manual editing and basic ML models, producing limited realism (Chesney & Citron, 2019).
- **GAN revolution (2014-2017)** – Generative Adversarial Networks improved image and audio synthesis through adversarial training (Mirsky & Lee, 2021).
- **Mainstream proliferation (2018-2020)** – tools like DeepFaceLab, FakeApp and Lyrebird made deepfakes accessible to the public (Europol, 2023).
- **Real time deepfakes (2021 – Present)** – neural voice synthesis and advanced reenactment models enable live impersonation, increasingly used in fraud (Pindrop, 2020).

1.1.2.2 TYPES OF DEEPFAKES

<i>Deepfake Type</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Primary Cybersecurity Risk</i>	<i>Common Use Cases</i>	<i>Key sources</i>
<i>Audio Deepfakes</i>	AI-generated speech that replicates a target’s voice using	Vishing, executive impersonation,	Financial fraud, social engineering,	Korshunov & Marcel (2018) Pindrop (2020)

	neural voice synthesis	bypassing voice authentication	identity impersonation	
<i>Video Deepfakes</i>	Synthetic or manipulated video content such as face swaps or reenactment	Disinformation, reputational harm, identity fraud	Fake news, blackmail, impersonation	Chesney & Citron (2019) Mirsky & Lee (2021)
<i>Face Morphing</i>	Blending multiple identities into a single biometric representation	Circumventing facial recognition and identity verification systems	Border control evasion, account takeover	NIST (2023), Europol (2023)
<i>Text-Based deepfakes</i>	AI-generated written content that mimics an individual's writing style	Phishing, misinformation, impersonation	Email fraud, fake statements, social engineering	Zellers et al (2019), WEF (2024)
<i>Real time deepfakes</i>	Live manipulation of audio or video during communication	High-impact impersonation, rapid fraud execution	Live Vishing, fake video meetings	Europol (2023), WEF (2024)

Table 1 – Types of Deepfakes

While all categories of deepfakes present cybersecurity risks, audio and real time deepfakes pose the most immediate and severe threat to organisations. These forms directly exploit trust-based communication channels and require minimal data to generate convincing impersonation, making them particularly effective in Vishing attacks (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018). Real time deepfakes further intensify this risk by enabling live interaction, reducing opportunities for verification and increasing the likelihood of impulsive decision making under pressure (Europol, 2023). Compared to video or text based deepfakes, audio driven impersonation targets human trust rather than technical vulnerabilities, highlighting the growing importance of human centric cybersecurity strategies and awareness training (Abroshan et al, 2021, WEF, 2024).

1.1.3 VISHING AND ITS AMPLIFICATION THROUGH DEEPFAKES

Vishing traditionally involves attackers contacting victims via voice communication while impersonating an authority figure, such as a bank representative, employer or a service provider (Pindrop, 2020). Prior to deepfake technology, vishing relies primarily on persuasion, scripted dialogue or generic impersonation. However, the introduction of deepfake audio now allows attackers to replicate specific individuals voice with a level of realism that makes fraudulent calls significantly more convincing (Europol, 2023). Real cases of deepfake enabled vishing to have already resulted in substantial financial losses and security breaches, showing the severity and growing prevalence of this threat.

1.1.3.1 TYPES OF VISHING ATTACKS

Vishing attacks take multiple forms depending on the goals of the attacker:

- **Authority impersonation vishing** – attackers will impersonate banks, government agencies or IT departments (Pindrop, 2020).
- **Business Email Compromise (BEC) voice fraud** – attackers pose as executives using voice manipulation to authorise fraudulent payments (Europol, 2023).
- **Tech support scams** – convincing victims to fix non-existent technical issues, often leading to remote access compromise (Jagatic et al, 2007).
- **Robocall vishing** – automated mass fraudulent calls with spoofed caller IDs (WEF, 2024)
- **Hybrid phishing/vishing attacks** – coordinated emails and calls to reinforce legitimacy (Abroshan et al, 2021).
- **Deepfake enhanced vishing** – synthetic voice models impersonating real individuals with near perfect realism (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018)

1.1.4 IMPLICATIONS FOR TODAY'S CYBERSECURITY ENVIRONMENT

Several modern factors increase the impact of deepfake enabled vishing:

- Remote working environments, where voice communication frequently replaces face to face verification
- Increasing reliance on voice-based authentication systems, many of which are vulnerable to synthetic audio attacks (NIST, 2023).
- Widespread availability of AI voice synthesis tools, reducing the skill threshold required for attackers (Villalba et al, 2020)
- Human trust in familiar voices, providing attackers with powerful psychological leverage (WEF, 2024).

These conditions create an environment in which deepfake enabled vishing poses a significant and evolving cybersecurity challenge, demanding improved awareness, technical countermeasures and organisational readiness.

1.1.4.1 WHAT IS CYBERSECURITY

Cybersecurity refers to the combination of technologies, processes and practices designed to protect computer systems, networks, data and communication from unauthorised access, disruption or damage (NIST, 2023). It incorporates technical controls such as encryption and authentication, human factors including awareness training and social engineering prevention (Abroshan et al, 2021) and procedural controls like incident response planning and risk management frameworks (WEF, 2024).

1.1.4.2 WHY DEEPFAKE VISHING CHALLENGES CYBERSECURITY

Deepfake enabled vishing disrupts cybersecurity on multiple levels. Technically, synthetic voices can bypass voice recognition and authentication systems (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018). Human factors are also exploited, as high realism of deepfakes amplifies trust and emotional manipulation (Mirsky & Lee, 2021). Procedurally, traditional verification protocols often fail to detect sophisticated synthetic audio, especially during urgent or high-pressure scenarios (Europol, 2023).

1.1.4.3 OVERALL IMPACT ON THE CYBER LANDSCAPE

The risk of deepfake vishing increases financial, operational and reputational risks. Identity verification becomes more difficult; fraud can be scaled rapidly and trust in communication channels is eroded. Factors such as remote working environment, reliance on voice-based authentication, the wide availability of AI voice synthesis tools and inherent human trust in familiar voices all contribute to the growing effectiveness of those attacks (Villalba et al, 2020, WEF,2024).

1.2 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.2.1 AIM OF THE STUDY

The primary aim of this study is to conduct an in-depth investigation into how deepfake voice technology is transforming the landscape of voice phishing attacks. This includes examining the scale and complexity of the threat, analysing real world incidents, assessing defensive strategies and developing a framework to guide organisational preparedness, by combing both technical and behavioural perspectives, the study aims to provide a holistic understanding of an emerging cyber threat that has not yet been widely researched.

1.2.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To investigate awareness levels of voice based deepfake threats among cybersecurity professionals and end users.
- To examine real world incidents of deepfake enabled vishing attacks and their impacts on organisations.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of current countermeasures against voice deepfakes in phishing scenarios.
- To assess the psychological and social engineering techniques that make deepfake vishing attacks successful
- To propose a framework of best practices and technical strategies to mitigate risks from deepfake vishing attacks.

1.2.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Building on the objectives, the research explores the following questions:

- What current knowledge do professionals and end users have regarding synthetic voice threats and how does this influence vulnerability?
- What patterns, indicators and organisational consequences are evident in documented cases of deepfake enabled vishing?
- Which defensive tools, training methods and security policies have proven effective and where do they fall short?
- How do attackers exploit trust, authority, urgency and cognitive bias when using deepfake audio in vishing attempts?
- What combination of technical, procedural and human focused strategies can meaningfully reduce the risks associated with these attacks?

These questions guide the direction of data collection and help ensure the projects findings address practical challenges faced by the organisations.

1.3 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

1.3.1 JUSTIFICATION FOR TOPIC CHOICE

The rapid evolution of AI-generated synthetic media has created a security gap in which organisations and individuals are increasingly exposed to highly sophisticated impersonation attacks. Deepfake audio poses a particularly substantial threat due to its ease of production and its impact on trust-based communication channels. Despite its significance, research specifically addressing deepfake enabled vishing is still limited, making this a timely and necessary area of investigation.

1.3.3 INDUSTRY RELEVANCE

Cybercriminals are leveraging deepfake technology to bypass verification procedures, exploit remote communication workflows and impersonate high profile figures with unprecedented accuracy. Incidents of AI driven fraud have risen sharply, with organisations reporting financial losses, compromised operational processes and reputational damage. Understanding the mechanisms and impacts of these attacks is essential for developing modern security strategies.

1.3.3 ACADEMIC SIGNIFICANCE

This study contributes to the growing body of academic research on artificial intelligence driven cyber threats by addressing a clear gap in the existing literature. Previous research has extensively examined phishing and social engineering techniques, focusing on psychological manipulation and user susceptibility (Jagatic et al, 2007, Abroshan et al, 2021). In parallel, other studies have explored technical development, capabilities and detection of deepfake media, particularly in relation to video and image manipulation (Chesney & Citron, 2019, Mirsky & Lees, 2021). However, relatively limited research has specifically examined the convergence of deepfake voice technology and vishing attacks.

In particular, the human centred implications of synthetic voice impersonation remain underexplored within cybersecurity scholarship. While technical studies highlight the increasing realism of AI generated audio and its potential to bypass traditional security mechanisms (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018) fewer works investigate how these capabilities interact with social engineering strategies and cognitive biases during voice based attacks (Abroshan et al, 2021) this lack of integration between technical and behavioural perspectives limits current understanding of why deepfake enabled vishing is especially effective.

By combining insights from artificial intelligence research, social engineering theory and human factors in cybersecurity, this study advances a more holistic understanding of emerging voice-based threats. Rather than focusing solely on detection technologies, the research examines awareness levels, attacker strategies and organisational vulnerabilities, contributing evidence to support socio technical approaches to cybersecurity (WEF, 2024, as deepfake technologies continue to evolve and become more accessible, this study provides a foundation for future academic research into adaptive security frameworks that address both technological innovation and persistent human vulnerabilities.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE LITERATURE REVIEW

The Rapid advancement of artificial intelligence has significantly altered the cybersecurity threat landscape, introducing new forms of deception that challenge both technical controls and human judgment. One of the most impactful developments is deepfake technology, which enables the generation of highly realistic synthetic audio, video and text. While existing research has examined deepfakes from legal, ethical and technical perspectives (Chesney & Citron, 2019; Mirsky & Lee, 2021), their role in amplifying social engineering attacks particularly voice phishing remains underexplored.

This literature review examines academic, industry and law enforcement research relating to deepfake technology, audio impersonation, social engineering and vishing. Foundational studies on phishing psychology provide insight into why deception-based attacks remain effective despite increased awareness (Jagatic et al, 2007; Abroshan et al, 2021) technical analyses of voice synthesis and biometric spoofing further demonstrate how AI has increased the realism and scalability of impersonation attacks (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018; Villalba et al, 2020).

To provide real world context, this review also incorporates industry reports and law enforcement assessment documenting the practical use of deepfake audio in fraud and impersonation attacks (Pindrop, 2020; Europol, 2023). Strategic outlooks are included to situate deepfake enabled vishing within broader cybersecurity trends (World Economic Forum, 2024) as well as this literature exploring the dual use and beneficial applications of deepfake technology is considered to provide a balanced and critical perspective (Kietzmann et al, 2020)

Table 2 summarises key literature reviewed in this chapter, outlining publication details, focus areas, relevance to this study and access links for transparency and ease of reference.

Author	Year	Title	Primary Focus	Relevance to this study	Perspective	Link
Chesney, R. & Citron, D	2019	Deep Fakes: A looming Challenge for Privacy, Democracy, and National Security	Societal and security risks of Deepfakes	Establishes deepfakes as a serious emerging threat	Legal/ Security threat focused	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3213954
Mirsky, Y. & Lee, W.	2021	The Creation and Detection of Deepfakes: A Survey	Deepfake Generation and detection Techniques	Shows technical advancement and detection limitations	Technical/ Defensive	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3425780
Korshunov, P. & Marcel, S.	2018	Speaker Inconsistency Detection in Tampered Voice Recordings	Audio Deepfakes and voice spoofing	Demonstrates vulnerability of voice authentication	Technical/Voice-specific	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8461439
Jagatic, T. et al.	2007	Social Phishing	Psychological manipulation in phishing	Explains human susceptibility exploited by vishing	Behavioural/ Social engineering	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1290958.1290968
Abroshan, H. et al	2021	Phishing attacks, prevention techniques and user awareness	Phishing Methods and defences	Highlights limitations of awareness-based defences	Behaviour/prevention	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167404820303852

<i>Europol</i>	2023	Facing Reality? Law Enforcement and the Challenge of Deepfakes	Criminal use of Deepfakes	Confirms real world deepfake enabled fraud	Law enforcement/applied	https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/publications/facing-reality
<i>Pindrop</i>	2020	The Rise of Deepfake Audio Fraud	Voice Fraud and impersonation	Directly links deepfake audio to vishing	Industry/applied	https://www.pindrop.com/resources/reports/the-rise-of-deepfake-audio-fraud
<i>Villalba, J. et al.</i>	2020	Spoofing and Anti-Spoofing in Automatic Speaker Verification	Voice Biometrics and Spoofing	Shows weaknesses in speaker verification systems	Technical/biometric	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167639320300463
<i>World Economic Forum</i>	2024	Global Cybersecurity Outlook	Emerging Cyber threat trends	Positions deepfake vishing within AI threat evolution	Strategic/future oriented	https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-cybersecurity-outlook-2024
<i>Kietzmann, J.H. et al</i>	2020	Deepfakes: Trick or Treat?	Ethical and beneficial uses of deepfakes	Provides balanced, dual use perspective	Ethical/ Dual use	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0007681319301444

Table 2 - Sources Used in Literature Review

2.2 DEEPFAKE TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

Deepfake technology has developed rapidly alongside advances in artificial intelligence and machine learning, fundamentally altering the nature of digital deception. While early academic disclosure framed deepfakes primarily as a visual or media integrity concern, more recent literature increasingly recognises their implications for cybersecurity and social engineering (Chesney & Citron, 2019; Mirsky & Lee, 2021). This section critically examines advances in deepfake generation, the emergence of audio focused manipulation, the limitations of detection approaches and the broader implications for cyber-enabled deception.

2.2.1 ADVANCES IN DEEPFAKE GENERATION TECHNOLOGIES

Initial deepfake systems were largely dependent on Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) which introduced adversarial learning as a mechanism for generating increasingly realistic synthetic media (Chesney & Citron, 2019) while effective, early GAN based models were constrained by limited training data and computational power, often producing artefacts that could be identified through manual or automated analysis. As a result, early detection research focused on identifying visual inconsistencies such as unnatural facial movements or lighting anomalies.

Subsequent research highlights a shift toward more sophisticated architectures, including transformer-based models and end to end neural pipelines, which significantly reduce these artefacts (Mirsky & Lee, 2021). These models benefit from larger datasets, improved optimisation techniques and transfer learning, enabling higher fidelity synthesis with reduced training requirements. Europol (2023) notes that this technical maturation has coincided with the public release of deepfake tools, lowering the skill threshold required to generate convincing synthetic content.

From a cybersecurity perspective, this progression has important implications. As deepfake generation becomes faster, cheaper and more accessible, attackers are no longer limited by technical expertise. The literature consistently suggests

that this demonstration of deepfake technology increases the likelihood of misuse, particularly in social engineering contexts where realism directly correlates with attacker success (WEF, 2024).

2.2.2 AUDIO DEEPAKES AND THE SHIFT TOWARD VOICE-BASED IMPERSONATION

Although much early deepfake research focused on video manipulation, several authors argue that audio deepfakes now pose a more immediate and scalable threat. Korshunov and Marcel (2018) demonstrate that neural voice synthesis models can replicate speaker identity, tone and prosody (patterns of rhythm) with limited training data, making voice cloning significantly easier than visual impersonation. This capability is further reinforced by the widespread availability of public audio samples through social media, video platforms and corporate communications.

Industry research supports this assessment, indicating that convincing voice clones can be generated from recordings lasting only a few seconds (Pindrop, 2020). Unlike video deepfakes, audio manipulation does not require visual scrutiny and can be deployed in real time, increasing its effectiveness in urgent or high-pressure scenarios. Villalba et al. (2020) argue that this makes audio deepfakes particularly well suited to impersonation attacks, as they exploit deeply ingrained human trust in familiar voices.

The literature also highlights a shift in attacker strategy from mass deception to targeted impersonation. By combining voice synthesis with contextual information, attackers can convincingly impersonate executives, colleagues or family members. This shift aligns closely with the operational characteristics of vishing attacks, where trust, authority and immediacy play a central role. Collectively, these findings suggest that audio deepfakes represent a convergence point between advanced AI capabilities and traditional social engineering techniques.

2.2.3 DETECTION CHALLENGES AND DEFENSIVE LIMITATIONS

Despite increased research into Deepfake detection, the literature consistently identifies significant limitations in current defensive approaches. Mirsky and Less (2021) describes an ongoing “arms race” in which improvements in generation techniques rapidly invalidate detection models that rely on static artefacts. This problem is particularly pronounced in audio deepfake detection, where distinguishing between genuine and synthetic speech is inherently challenging due to natural variability in human voice.

Korshunov and Marcel (2018) note that many speaker verification systems were designed to authenticate human speech rather than detect synthetic manipulation, leaving them vulnerable to spoofing attacks. Villalba et al. (2020) further argue that spoofing measures often perform poorly under real world conditions such as background noise, compressed audio or live communication environments. These constraints significantly reduce the effectiveness of technical defences in practical vishing scenarios.

Law enforcement perspectives reinforce these concerns. Europol (2023) warns that reliance on automated detection alone is insufficient, particularly when attacks exploit organisational procedures rather than technical vulnerabilities. The literature therefore suggests that while detection technologies are necessary, they are not sufficient on their own and must be complemented by procedural and human centred controls.

2.2.4 IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIAL ENGINEERING AND CYBERCRIME

The convergence of advanced deepfake technology and established social engineering principles represents a significant escalation in cybercrime capability. Chesney and Citron (2019) argue that deepfakes undermine traditional trust mechanisms by enabling attackers to convincingly impersonate known individuals, eroding confidence in digital communication. This concern is echoed by Abroshan et al. (2021), who highlight that even informed users remain vulnerable to authority and urgency cues.

Audio deepfakes amplify these vulnerabilities by reducing opportunities for verification and increasing the perceived authenticity of fraudulent communications. The literature suggests that this communication shifts the balance of power toward attackers, particularly in voice-based fraud where decisions are often made quickly and without secondary

confirmation (Pindrop, 2020). Strategic assessments further indicate that these threats are likely to intensify as AI tools become more accessible and integrated into criminal workflows (WEF, 2024).

Despite growing recognition of these risks, there remains a lack of research specifically examining deepfake enabled vishing from a human centred perspective. Existing studies tend to focus either on technical detection or general phishing behaviour, leaving a gap in understanding how victims interpret and respond to synthetic voice impersonation in practice. This gap directly motivates the present study and underscores the need for interdisciplinary research that integrates technical, psychological and organisational dimensions of cybersecurity.

2.3 AUDIO DEEPPAKES AND VOICE IMPERSONATION

Audio deepfakes represent a distinct and increasingly dangerous subset of deepfake technology due to their ability to exploit trust in a voice-based communication. Unlike visual deepfakes, which often require careful inspection, synthetic audio can be deployed rapidly and with minimal opportunity for verification. The literature increasingly identifies audio deepfakes as a critical enabler of impersonation-based cybercrime, particularly in the context of social engineering and vishing attacks (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018; Pindrop, 2020)

2.3.1 NEURAL VOICE SYNTHESIS AND VOICE CLONING TECHNIQUES

Neural voice synthesis refers to the use of deep learning models to generate artificial speech that closely resembles a targets speakers voice. Early text to speech systems produced robotic and easily identifiable outputs, however, modern neural approaches, such as WaveNet and Tacotron-based architectures, have dramatically improved naturalness and intelligibility (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018). These systems can model not only linguistic content but also paralinguistic features, including intonational, rhythm and emotional expression.

Recent studies highlight that voice cloning can now be achieved using limited training data, sometimes requiring only a few seconds of recorded speech (Villalba et al, 2020). This development has significant security implications, as attackers can easily obtain audio samples from publicly available sources such as social media videos, conference presentations or even voicemail recordings. Pindrop (2020) notes that the reduction in data requirements has transformed voice cloning from a specialised research capability into a practical tool for fraud.

The literature also distinguishes between text dependent and text independent synthesis. Text-independent models are particularly concerning for cybersecurity, as they allow attackers to generate speech content while maintaining vocal authenticity. This flexibility enables dynamic and interactive impersonation, aligning closely with the operational needs of vishing attacks.

2.3.2 AUDIO DEEPPAKES AND SPEAKER VERIFICATION SYSTEMS

Speaker verification systems are widely used in banking, customer service and access control environments to authenticate users based on vocal characteristics. However, several studies argue that these systems were designed under the assumption that inputs originate from human speakers, leaving them vulnerable to synthetic audio manipulation (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018). As a result, many verification mechanisms struggle to distinguish between genuine and AI generated speech.

Villalba et al, (2020) demonstrate that state-of-the-art voice cloning techniques can successfully bypass common speaker verification systems, particularly when combined with replay or synthesis based spoofing attacks. These findings raise concerns about the continued reliance on voice-based authentication in security critical contexts. Europol (2023) similarly warns that organisations often overestimate the robustness of voice authentication systems, underestimating their susceptibility to AI driven impersonation.

The literature further suggests that improvements in synthesis quality reduce the effectiveness of traditional anti spoofing measures, which often rely on detecting artefacts introduced during generation. As these artefacts diminish, detection accuracy decreases, [particularly in real world conditions. This vulnerability is especially problematic in vishing scenarios, where attackers exploit not only technical weaknesses but also procedural trust.

2.3.3 REAL-TIME AUDIO DEEPFAKES AND INTERACTIVE IMPERSONATION

One of the most concerning developments identified in the literature is the emergence of real time audio deepfakes. Unlike pre-generated recordings, real time synthesis allows attackers to engage in interactive conversations, adapting responses dynamically to victim behaviour. Mirsky and Lee (2021) argue that this capability represents a significant escalation in impersonation threats, as it removes many of the constraints associated with scripted fraud.

Industry reports indicate that real time voice manipulation has already been used in targeted fraud cases, particularly against organisations with hierarchical decision-making structures (Europol, 2023) in such cases, attackers impersonate senior executives to authorise financial transactions or extract sensitive information. The ability to respond naturally to questions and objections significantly increase the credibility and reduces suspicion.

From a psychological perspective, real time interaction amplifies social engineering effectiveness. Abroshan et al. (2021) note that conversational engagement increases cognitive load, making individuals more susceptible to manipulation under pressure. When combined with a familiar or authoritative voice, this effect becomes even more pronounced, therefore reinforcing the threat posed by real time audio deepfakes in vishing attacks.

2.3.4 IMPLICATIONS FOR VISHING AND ORGANISATIONAL SECURITY

The literature consistently links audio deepfakes to an increased risk of vishing attacks, particularly those targeting high value individuals or sensitive organisational processes. Pindrop (2020) reports that voice-based fraud is more likely to succeed when attackers impersonate known individuals, as victims are less inclined to question familiar voices. This observation aligns with broader social engineering research emphasising the role of trust and authority in deception (Abroshan et al, 2021).

Audio deepfakes also challenge traditional security awareness training, which often focuses on identifying suspicious language or unusual requests. When fraudulent messages are delivered in a trusted voice, these cues may be overlooked. Europol (2023) argues that this undermines existing procedural safeguards and highlights the need for multi factor verification processes that do not rely solely on voice authentication.

Despite these concerns, the literature reveals a lack of research examining how individuals perceive and respond to synthetic voice impersonation in real world contexts. Most studies focus on technical feasibility rather than user behaviour or organisational, response. This gap reinforces the need for research that integrates technical analysis with human centred investigation, directly supporting the focus of the present study on deepfake enabled vishing.

2.4 SOCIAL ENGINEERING AND PHISHING THEORY

Social engineering remains one of the most effective techniques in cybercrime due to its reliance on exploiting predictable human behaviours rather than technical vulnerabilities. The literature consistently demonstrates that even well informed users can be manipulated under conditions of authority, urgency and perceived legitimacy (Abroshan et al, 2021; Jagatic et al, 2007) this section critically examines social engineering theory, psychological mechanisms underlying phishing susceptibility and the specific dynamics of voice-based manipulation that make vishing and particularly deepfake enabled vishing highly effective.

2.4.1 PRINCIPLES OF SOCIAL ENGINEERING

Social engineering is grounded in the manipulation of human trust and cognitive shortcuts rather than direct exploitation of software or hardware flaws. Early foundational studies identify key principles such as authority, reciprocity, social proof and urgency as central to successful deception (Jagatic et al, 2007). These principles allow attackers to influence decision making by triggering automatic, heuristic based responses rather than reflective reasoning.

Later research builds on this foundation by emphasising the role of contextual credibility. Abroshan et al. (2021) argue that modern social engineering attacks are increasingly tailored, leveraging personal or organisational information to enhance realism. This shift from generic to targeted manipulation reduces suspicion and increases compliance.

Importantly, the literature suggests that increased technical awareness does not necessarily reduce susceptibility, as social engineering exploits fundamental cognitive biases rather than knowledge gaps.

From this perspective, social engineering is best understood as a socio-technical phenomenon in which psychological manipulation operates alongside technological enablers. This framing particularly relevant when examining deepfake enabled attacks, where advanced AI tools serve to reinforce long standing psychological principles rather than replace them.

2.4.2 PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS IN PHISHING SUSCEPTIBILITY

A substantial body of literature explores why individuals fall victim to phishing despite widespread awareness of cyber threats. Jagatic et al. (2007) demonstrate that familiarity and perceived trustworthiness significantly influence user behaviour, often overriding rational risk assessment. This finding is echoed by Abroshan et al. (2021), who identify cognitive overload, stress and time pressure as key factors increasing susceptibility.

Dual-process theories of cognition provide a useful framework for understanding this behaviour. Under conditions of urgency or emotional arousal, individuals are more likely to rely on fast, intuitive decision making rather than deliberate analysis. Attackers deliberately engineer these conditions through urgency language, authoritative tone and plausible scenarios. When combined with realistic impersonate, such as a familiar voice, these factors substantially reduce the likelihood of sceptical evaluation.

The literature also highlights overconfidence as a vulnerability. Users who believe they are unlikely to be deceived may pay less attention to warning signs, increasing risk. This insight challenges assumptions that training alone is sufficient to prevent social engineering attacks and suggests the need for systematic safeguards that do not rely solely on user judgement.

2.4.3 TRUST, AUTHORITY AND URGENCY IN VOICE-BASED ATTACKS

Voice based communication introduces unique psychological dynamics that differentiate vishing from email or text-based phishing. Research indicates that vocal cues such as tone, cadence and emotional expression enhance perceived authenticity and trust (Pindrop, 2020). Unlike written communication, voice interactions are inherently transient, reducing opportunities for verification or reflection.

Authority plays a particularly strong role in vishing attacks. Abroshan et al. (2021) note that individuals are more likely to comply with requests delivered verbally by perceived authority figures, especially in organisational hierarchies. This effect is amplified when the voice matches that of a known superior or trusted contact. Deepfake audio enables attackers to exploit this dynamic with unprecedented precision, transforming authority from a social construct into a programmable asset.

Urgency further compounds the effects. Real time voice interactions create pressure to respond immediately, limiting the victim's ability to seek confirmation or consult security policies. Jagatic et al. (2007) argue that this temporal constraint is a critical success factor in phishing, and its impact is magnified in voice-based scenarios. Deepfake enabled vishing therefore represents an evolution of social engineering that combines psychological pressure with advanced technological deception.

2.4.4 IMPLICATIONS FOR DEEPPFAKE-ENABLED VISHING

The literature suggests that deepfake audio significantly enhances the effectiveness of social engineering by strengthening psychological triggers that attackers have long exploited. Chesney and Citron (2019) argue that deepfakes erode traditional trust signals, making it increasingly difficult to distinguish between legitimate and fraudulent communications. When applied to voice-based attacks, this erosion undermines one of the most intuitive human verification mechanisms e.g recognising familiar voices.

Despite Growing recognition of this threat, existing research often treats social engineering and deepfake technology as separate domains. Few studies examine how synthetic voice impersonation alters user perception, trust calibration or

decision making under pressure. The gap is particularly evident in the context of vishing, where the interaction between psychological manipulation and AI generated realism remains underexplored,

Consequently, the literature supports the need for interdisciplinary research that integrates cognitive psychology, cybersecurity and AI ethics. Understanding how individuals interpret and respond to deepfake enabled voice manipulation is essential for developing effective countermeasures that address both technical and human vulnerabilities. This recognition directly informs the focus and methodology of the present study.

2.5 VISHING AND DEEPFAKE-ENABLED VOICE ATTACKS: REAL WORLD EVIDENCE

The emergence of deepfake enabled vishing is no longer a speculative concern but a documented and growing form of cyber enabled fraud. While earlier research treated audio deepfakes as an experimental threat, recent industry reports and law enforcement assessments confirm their use in real world criminal activity, particularly in financially motivated and organisationally targeted attacks (Pindrop, 2020; Europol 2023). This section reviews documented cases of vishing and deepfake voice impersonation, analysing how these attacks operate in practice and what they reveal about attacker capabilities.

2.5.1 EXECUTIVE IMPERSONATION AND FINANCIAL FRAUD CASES

One of the most widely cited real world examples of deepfake-enabled vishing involves executive impersonation within corporate environments. Europol (2023) documents multiple incidents in which attackers used AI-generated voice technology to impersonate senior executives and instruct employees to transfer funds or disclose sensitive information. In these cases, the synthetic voice closely matched that of the executive, including accent and speech patterns, leading victims to comply without invoking secondary verification procedures.

A frequently referenced case involved attackers impersonating a company's chief executive during a phone call to a finance employee, resulting in fraudulent transfer of several hundred thousand euros (Europol, 2023). The success of the attack was attributed not only to the realism of the voice but also to the authority associated with the impersonated role and the urgency conveyed during the call. This aligns with findings from Pindrop (2020) which note that voice-based fraud is particularly effective when it targets hierarchical decision-making structures,

These cases demonstrate that deepfake audio is already being utilised in targeted fraud rather than mass scams. The literature suggests that attacks are likely to increase as organisations continue to rely on voice communication for sensitive transactions, particularly in remote or hybrid working environments.

2.5.2 VISHING ATTACKS EXPLOITING FAMILIAR VOICES

Beyond executive impersonation, real world reports indicate that attackers increasingly exploit familiarity to enhance credibility. Pindrop (2020) documents incidents where synthetic voices were used to impersonate colleagues, business partners or trusted service providers. In these cases, attackers leveraged contextual information obtained through prior reconnaissance allowing them to reference ongoing projects or internal terminology during the call.

Europol (2023) highlights that these attacks are difficult to detect because they do not rely on generic scripts. Instead, they blend deepfake audio with personalised social engineering, creating interactions that appear legitimate even to security aware individuals. Victims often report that the familiarity of the voice was a decisive factor in their compliance, overriding doubts raised by unusual requests.

These examples reinforce the argument that audio deepfakes fundamentally alter the threat model for vishing. Traditional advice to "verify the caller" becomes less effective when the caller sounds exactly like a known and trusted individual.

2.5.3 DEEPFAKE AUDIO IN BUSINESS EMAIL COMPROMISE (BEC) SCHEMES

Several documented cases illustrate how deepfake voice technology is being integrated into broader Business Email Compromise (BEC) schemes. Europol (2023) reports that attackers increasingly combine phishing emails with follow up

voice calls using synthetic audio to reinforce legitimacy. This hybrid approach exploits multiple communication channels, reducing suspicion and increasing the likelihood of success.

In these incidents, victims typically receive an email requesting an urgent action, followed by a phone call from a voice impersonating an executive or financial controller. The voice call serves to validate the email request, neutralising scepticism and accelerating compliance. Industry analysts describe this technique as partially effective because it exploits confirmation bias with the voice interaction acting as perceived proof of authenticity (Pindrop, 2020)

These real-world cases demonstrate that deepfake enabled vishing is not isolated phenomenon but part of a broader evolution in organised cybercrime tactics. Attackers strategically deploy synthetic voices to complement existing fraud techniques rather than replace them.

2.5.4 LAW ENFORCEMENT AND INDUSTRY ASSESSMENTS OF EMERGING TRENDS

Law enforcement agencies and cybersecurity firms consistently warn that documented cases likely represent only a fraction of actual incidents, Europol (2023) emphasises that many organisations do not publicly disclose deepfake related fraud due to reputational concerns, leading to underreporting. This assessment suggests that the true scale of deepfake enabled vishing may be significantly larger than current figures indicate.

Industry data supports this view. Pindrop (2020) reports a measurable increase in voice-based fraud attempts coinciding with improvements in AI voice synthesis tools. The report highlights that attackers are rapidly adopting these technologies due to their low cost, scalability and effectiveness. Importantly, both sources stress that existing security controls, particularly voice authentication and informal verification procedures are insufficient to counter these threats.

Together, these real-world assessments indicate that deepfake enabled vishing is transitioning from an emerging threat to an established attack vector. The literature consistently points to a need for improved detection mechanisms, stronger procedural safeguards and greater awareness of voice-based impersonation risks.

2.5.5 IMPLICATIONS DRAWN FROM REAL-WORLD CASES

Analysis of documented incidents reveals several consistent patterns. First, attackers preferentially target high trust relationships and time sensitive processes. Second, victims rarely suspect deception during the call itself, instead identifying fraud only after financial or operational damage has occurred (Europol, 2023). Third, reliance on voice familiarity or perceived authority is a critical failure point exploited by attackers (Pindrop, 2020)

Despite these insights, the literature remains largely descriptive, focusing on what has happened rather than systematically analysing victim perception or organisational response. There is limited research examining how individuals interpret synthetic voice cues or how security policies perform under deepfake enabled pressure scenario this gap highlights the importance of further research into deepfake enabled vishing that integrates real world evidence with behavioural and organisational analysis, directly supporting the objectives of the present study

2.6 DEFENSIVE MEASURES AND COUNTERMEASURES IN THE LITERATURE

The literature addressing deepfake enabled vishing consistently emphasises that effective defence cannot rely on a single control. Instead, authors argue for a combination of technical, procedural and human centred measures, while also acknowledging significant limitations in current approaches (Mirsky & Lee, 202; Europol, 2023), this section critically reviews defensive measures that are explicitly discussed within existing literature, focusing on their effectiveness and shortcomings in real world contexts.

2.6.1 TECHNICAL DETECTION AND ANTI-SPOOFING MEASURES

A significant portion of the literature examines technical approaches to detecting synthetic audio, particularly within speaker verification and authentication systems. Korshunov and Marcel (2018) evaluate anti-spoofing techniques designed to identify artefacts introduced during voice synthesis, such as spectral inconsistencies or unnatural temporal

patterns. While these methods demonstrate effectiveness in controlled environments, their performance degrades under real world conditions, including background noise and audio compression.

Mirsky and Lee (2021) argue that detection-based defences are inherently reactive, as they depend on identifying characteristics of existing generation techniques. As synthesis models improve, these detectable artefacts diminish, reducing the long-term reliability of detection systems. This dynamic creates an arms race in which defenders must continually update models to keep pace with evolving deepfake generation methods.

Law enforcement assessments echo these concerns. Europol (2023) cautions that many organisations place undue confidence in voice authentication systems, despite evidence that synthetic audio can bypass these controls. As a result, the literature suggests that while technical detection remains a necessary component of defence, it cannot serve as a standalone solution against deepfake enabled vishing.

2.6.2 MULTI-FACTOR AND OUT-OF-BAND VERIFICATION

Several sources emphasise the importance of procedural safeguards that reduce reliance on voice-based trust. Pindrop (2020) advocates for multi factor authentication mechanisms that require confirmation through independent channels, such as secure messaging platforms or internal approval workflows. These measures are designed to interrupt social engineering attempts by introducing friction into high-risk process.

Europol (2023) similarly recommends out of band verification for sensitive requests, particularly those involving financial transactions or changes to access permissions. Documented cases show that attacks frequently succeed when victims feel pressured to act quickly without seeking confirmation. Procedural requirements that mandate secondary verification can therefore mitigate risk by countering urgency-based manipulation

However, the literature also notes practical challenges. Abroshan et al. (2021) argue that procedural controls are only effective if consistently enforced and that organisational culture often undermines formal policies during perceived emergencies. This limitation highlights the need for alignment between technical controls and human behaviour.

2.6.3 HUMAN-CENTRED DEFENCES AND AWARENESS TRAINING

Human centred defences feature prominently in the literature, particularly in discussions of social engineering prevention. Abroshan et al. (2021) emphasise that awareness training remains essential, as many attacks exploit predictable cognitive biases rather than technical flaws. Training programmes that educate users about authority manipulation, urgency cues and impersonation tactics are shown to improve scepticism and reporting behaviour.

Nevertheless, multiple studies caution against overreliance on training alone. Jagatic et al. (2007) demonstrate that even trained individuals remain susceptible under realistic conditions, particularly when attacks involve familiar or trusted identities. Europol (2023) reinforces this view, noting that victims of deepfake enabled vishing often include experienced professionals who did not perceive the attack as suspicious at the time.

The literature therefore positions awareness training as a complementary measure rather than a primary defence. Its effectiveness depends on reinforcement through procedural and technical controls that reduce the burden on individual judgment.

2.6.4 ORGANISATIONAL POLICIES AND INCIDENT RESPONSE FRAMEWORKS

Several authors highlight the role of organisational policies in mitigating deepfake enabled threats. Europol (2023) recommends the integration of voice impersonation scenarios into incident response planning, arguing that many organisations are unprepared for Ai-driven fraud. Clear escalation procedures and reporting mechanisms can reduce damage by enabling rapid response when suspicious calls occur.

The literature also emphasises the importance of rehearsed response protocols. Pindrop (2020) suggests that organisations should treat voice-based fraud as a distinct threat category rather than an extension of email phishing. This distinction allows for tailored controls and clearer guidance for employees.

However, Mirsky and Lee (2021) note that policy effectiveness is limited when not supported by technical visibility or organisational buy in. policies that are not embedded into daily workflows may be bypassed during high pressure situations, reinforcing the need for layered defence strategies.

2.6.5 LIMITATIONS OF CURRENT DEFENSIVE APPROACHES

Across the literature, there is broad agreement that existing defensive measures are insufficient to fully address deepfake-enabled vishing. Technical detection struggles to keep pace with advancing synthesis techniques, while procedural and human centred controls are vulnerable to manipulation and non-compliance (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018; Abroshan et al, 2021).

Europol (2023) concludes that the most significant weakness lies in the continued reliance on video as a trusted authentication factor. If voice communication is treated as inherently reliable, attackers can exploit this assumption using synthetic audio. The literature therefore supports a shift toward scepticism-based security models that assume voice can be compromised.

Despite growing awareness of these limitations, there is limited research evaluating how defensive measures perform specifically against deepfake-enabled vishing in operational environments. This lack of evidence underscores the need for further investigation into effective, context-aware mitigation strategies, an objective directly addressed by the present study.

2.7 ETHICAL, LEGAL AND DUAL-USE CONSIDERATIONS

The rapid advancement of deepfake technology raises significant ethical and legal concerns, particularly when applied to voice based social engineering attacks. The literature consistently frames deepfake systems as dual use technologies, tools capable of generating both socially beneficial applications and serious harm (Chesney & Citron, 2019; Mirsky & Lee, 2021). This duality complicates regulatory responses and creates tensions between innovation, free expression and security.

2.7.1 THE DUAL-USE NATURE OF DEEPPFAKE TECHNOLOGY

Deep learning models used for synthetic voice generation are not inherently malicious. As highlighted by Chesney and Citron (2019), deepfake technologies have legitimate applications in accessibility, entertainment, language translation, assistive communication and digital content production. Voice cloning can enable media production workflows.

However, the same underlying generative models can be repurposed for impersonation and fraud. Mirsky and Lee (2021) argue that this dual use characteristic makes deepfakes particularly difficult to regulate, as restrictions targeting malicious use risk limiting beneficial innovation. The ethical dilemma therefore lies not in the existence of the technology but in how access, distribution and accountability are managed.

Within the context of vishing, the misuse of synthetic voice technology amplifies existing social engineering techniques by artificially preproducing identity cues that human is evolutionarily predisposed to trust. This creates an ethical concern centred on deception at scale, where attackers can convincingly simulate authority, familiarity or emotional urgency without physical presence.

2.7.2 HARM, TRUST EROSION AND SOCIETAL IMPACT

The literature identifies broader societal consequences beyond individual financial loss. Chesney and Citron (2019) introduce the concept of a “liar’s dividend,” whereby the existence of deepfake technology allows individuals to plausibly deny authentic recordings by claiming they are fabricated. Although primarily discussed in relation to video media, this concept extends to synthetic audio and has implications for legal evidence, corporate accountability and institutional trust.

Mirsky and Lee (2021) further argue that widespread awareness of deepfake capabilities may contribute to generalised scepticism toward digital media. In organisational settings, this erosion of trust may disrupt legitimate communication

channels, complicating crisis response and internal operations. The threat therefore extends beyond fraud to the destabilisation of confidence in digital verification mechanism.

Europol (2023) reinforces this concern in the context of financial crime, noting that synthetic voice attacks undermine assumptions about voice as a reliable biometric or authentication factor. As these attacks increase in sophistication, the boundary between authentic and artificial speech becomes less perceptible to human listeners, challenging traditional notions of identity verification.

2.7.3 LEGAL CHALLENGES AND REGULATORY LIMITATIONS

The legal landscape surrounding deepfakes remains fragmented and reactive. Chesney and Citron (2019) observe that existing legal framework often struggle to address synthetic media harms effectively, particularly when content does not fall neatly within established categories such as defamation, fraud or identity theft. The authors argue that the law tends to respond to harms after they occur rather than proactively regulating enabling technologies.

Mirsky and Lee (2021) similarly note that enforcement is complicated by the accessibility and global distribution of generative AI tools. Deepfake creation software is often open source or distributed across jurisdictions, limiting the practical effectiveness of national regulation. This creates enforcement asymmetric, where attackers can exploit regulatory gaps between countries.

Europol (2023) highlights that voice based deepfake fraud typically intersects with existing financial crime statutes rather than AI-specific legislation. While traditional fraud laws can address the act of deception, they do not necessarily account for the unique technological dimension of synthetic identity replication. Consequently, legal response focuses on criminal prosecution rather than preventative governance of AI systems.

The World Economic Forum (2024) further emphasises the regulatory lag between technological advancement and policy adaptation, identifying generative AI misuse as a growing global risk. This lag contributes to uncertainty regarding liability, accountability and compliance standards for organisations deploying or interacting with AI-generated content.

2.7.4 ETHICAL RESPONSIBILITY OF DEVELOPERS AND ORGANISATIONS

Beyond legal compliance, the literature raises questions regarding ethical responsibility among AI developers and deploying organisations. Mirsky and Lee (2021) argue that creators of generative models bear partial responsibility for anticipating misuse and incorporating safeguards into system design. However, they acknowledge the practical difficulty of preventing, malicious repurposing once models are released publicly.

From an organisational perspective, Europol (2023) suggests that companies must adapt governance frameworks to account for AI-driven impersonation risk. Ethical responsibility extends to implementing verification procedures, educating employees and reducing reliance on vulnerable authentication methods. Failure to adapt may constitute negligence in environments where the risk of synthetic impersonation is widely documented.

Chesney and Citron (2019) advocate for a balanced approach that preserves beneficial innovation while mitigating foreseeable harms. This includes transparency measures, improved detection research and clearer attribution mechanisms. However, the authors caution that overregulation could prevent technological progress and beneficial applications.

2.7.5 IMPLICATIONS FOR DEEPFAKE-ENABLED VISHING

When applied specifically to deepfake enabled vishing, ethical and legal considerations converge around identity manipulation, informed consent and deception. Synthetic voice attacks involve the unauthorised replication of an individual's vocal identity, raising concerns regarding personal autonomy and reputational harm (Chesney & Citron, 2019).

As well as this, the literature suggests that reliance on voice as an indicator of authenticity creates structural vulnerability within communication systems (Europol, 2023). If voice carries implicit trust, attackers can exploit this assumption.

Ethical governance must therefore consider not only misuse of AI tools but also the cultural and institutional norms that enable such misuse to succeed.

Overall, the literature indicates that current ethical and legal frameworks remain insufficiently aligned with the capabilities of generative AI systems. The Dual use nature of deepfake technology complicates regulatory intervention, while societal trust in digital media continues to erode. These unresolved tensions showcase the necessity for further interdisciplinary research into governance, accountability and secure authentication models in the age of synthetic media.

2.8 IDENTIFICATION OF RESEARCH GAPS

Despite the rapid expansion of research into deepfake technologies and the long-standing study of social engineering, the literature reveals a significant disconnect between these two domains. While technical research has focused heavily on the detection and generation of synthetic media (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018; Mirsky & Lee, 2021) and social engineering research has explored psychological manipulation in phishing contexts (Jagatic et al, 2007; Abroshan et al, 2021), there remains limited integrated analysis of how AI generated voice specifically transforms vishing attacks.

2.8.1 LIMITED EMPIRICAL RESEARCH ON DEEFAKE-ENABLED VISHING

A major gap identified within the literature is the absence of large-scale empirical studies examining real world deepfake enabled voice phishing incidents. Europol (2023) documents cases of AI-assisted voice fraud, yet these reports primarily provide descriptive threat intelligence rather than systematic behavioural or technical analysis. Similarly, industry research such as Pindrop (2020) highlights the emergence of synthetic voice threats but does not offer peer reviewed empirical evaluation of attack success rates or psychological impact.

Academic literature has extensively examined video based deepfakes (Chesney & Citron, 2019; Mirsky & Lee, 2021), but comparatively little attention has been given to audio only impersonation in social engineering contexts. This imbalance suggests that voice based deepfake threats remain under theorised within academic discourse, despite increasing documentation in law enforcement reports (Europol, 2023).

Consequently, there is clear need for research that moves beyond general deepfake risk discussions and directly analyses deepfake enabled vishing as a distinct threat category.

2.8.2 INSUFFICIENT INTEGRATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND TECHNICAL PERSPECTIVES

The literature on social engineering emphasises cognitive bias such as authority, urgency and trust in familiar identities (Jagatic et al, 2007; Abroshan et al, 2021). Meanwhile, technical deepfake research focuses on generation quality and detection mechanisms (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018; Mirsky & Lee, 2021). However, few studies explicitly examine how improvements in voice synthesis interact with these psychological vulnerabilities.

For example, while Mirsky and Lee (2021) discuss the growing realism of synthetic media, they do not empirically analyse how such realism alters victim decision making processes. Similarly, Abroshan et al. (2021) analyse susceptibility to social engineering but do not account for AI generated identity replication as a variable within attack scenarios.

This disciplinary separation causes a gap in context, the psychological literature assumes human impersonation, while the technical literature assumes detection challenges, but neither fully models the behavioural implications of synthetic voice impersonation. Research that bridges these domains would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how deepfakes realism modifies established social engineering dynamics.

2.8.3 LIMITED EVALUATION OF DEFENSIVE EFFECTIVENESS AGAINST SYNTHETIC VIDEO

Although defensive measures such as multi factor authentication, anti-spoofing systems and awareness training are discussed in the literature (Korshunov & Marcel, 2018; Pindrop, 2020; Europol, 2023) there is limited empirical evaluation of how these measures perform specifically against AI-generated voice attacks.

Korshunov and Marcel (2018) demonstrate that anti-spoofing techniques can detect synthetic audio under experimental conditions, yet the literature acknowledges that real world performance varies significantly. Similarly, awareness training is widely recommended (Abroshan et al, 2021), but studies such as Jagatic et al. (2007) suggest that individuals remain vulnerable even when informed about phishing risks.

There is therefore insufficient evidence regarding whether existing social engineering countermeasures remain effective when the impersonation involves highly realistic synthetic voice rather than traditional human deception. Research that experimentally evaluates defensive resilience against deepfake enabled vishing would address this gap.

2.8.4 REGULATORY AND GOVERNANCE UNCERTAINTY

The legal scholarship surrounding deepfakes highlights regulatory fragmentation and reactive policymaking (Chesney & Citron, 2019). Europol (2023) and the World Economic Forum (2024) both identify generative AI misuse as an emerging risk, yet there remains limited clarity on governance models specific to synthetic audio fraud.

While fraud statutes may apply to individual cases, there is little discussion within the literature regarding preventative governance mechanisms for AI voice cloning tools. As well as this, cross-jurisdictional enforcement challenges complicate regulatory responses (Mirsky & Lee, 2021).

This suggests a governance gap: the technological capability has advanced more rapidly than coordinated regulatory adaptation. Further interdisciplinary research is required to explore accountability frameworks, developer responsibility and organisational compliance strategies specific not AI-enabled voice impersonation.

2.8.5 CONCEPTUAL GAP: TRUST IN VOICE AS AN AUTHENTICATION MECHANISM

Perhaps the most significant gap emerging from the literature is the persistent assumption that voice retains inherent authenticity. Europol (2023) explicitly warns against continued reliance on voice as a trusted biometric, yet many organisational practices still treat voice recognition or familiar speech patterns as credible indicators of identity.

Existing research has not fully examined how the erosion of voice authenticity reshapes trust models within cybersecurity frameworks. As Chesney and Citron (2019) note in relation to synthetic media more broadly, the destabilisation of evidentiary trust has profound societal implications. However, specific analysis of how this applies to corporate voice verification systems remains limited.

This conceptual gap highlights the need for research that re-evaluates trust assumptions within communication security in the age of synthetic media.

2.8.6 SUMMARY OF RESEARCH GAPS

The literature demonstrates substantial progress in understanding deepfake generation and traditional social engineering tactics. However, critical gaps remain:

- Limited empirical research on deepfake enabled vishing specifically
- Insufficient integration of psychological and technical perspectives
- Lack of experimental evaluation of defensive measures against synthetic voice
- Regulatory uncertainty surrounding AI voice impersonation
- Under examined erosion of voice as a trusted authentication factor

Addressing these gaps is essential for developing evidence based defensive strategies and for understanding how AI-driven impersonation reshapes the threat landscape of social engineering attacks.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY AND APPROACH

The examination of deepfake voice technology and its influence on social engineering requires a methodological framework capable of addressing both measurable technological phenomenon and socially constructed behavioural responses. As established in Chapter 2, existing literature has largely treated these domains separately, technical research has focused on synthetic media generation and detection accuracy (Korshunov and Marcel, 2018; Mirsky and Lee, 2021), while behavioural research has examined cognitive susceptibility to phishing and manipulation (Jagatic et al, 2007; Abroshan et al, 2021). The methodological challenge of this study is therefore to integrate these perspectives within a coherent research design.

Research philosophy provides the foundation upon which methodological decisions are built. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) emphasise that clarity regarding philosophical positioning is essential to ensure alignment between research questions, methods and epistemology assumptions. Similarly, Creswell and Creswell (2018) argue that research paradigms guide not only data collection techniques but also the interpretation of findings. In response to the interdisciplinary nature of the research problem, this study adopts a pragmatic stance supported by a primarily deductive research approach.

3.1.1 RESEARCH PARADIGM

This study is placed within a pragmatic research paradigm. Pragmatism, as outlined by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019), prioritises the research problem and practical consequences of inquiry over strict adherence to a single ontological or epistemological doctrine. Creswell and Creswell (2018) similarly describe pragmatism as particularly suited to applied research where multiple methods may be required to address complex real-world issues.

Deepfake enabled vishing represents precisely such a problem. From a positivist standpoint, aspects of synthetic voice technology can be objectively measured. For example, technical studies have evaluated spoofing detection systems through empirical performance metrics such as error rates and classification accuracy (Korshunov and Marcel, 2018). Advances in generative adversarial networks and neural voice synthesis demonstrates quantifiable improvements in realism (Mirsky and Lee, 2021). These developments indicate that certain dimensions of the phenomenon exist independently of human perception and may be empirically assessed.

However, social engineering success depends not solely on technological realism but on human interpretation. Bryman (2016) notes that interpretivist approaches recognise social reality as constructed through meaning and interaction. In phishing contexts, Jagatic et al. (2007) demonstrate that contextual trust and perceived familiarity significantly influence compliance. Abroshan et al. (2021) further highlight how cognitive biases shape responses to manipulative communication. In the case of AI-generated voice, perceived authenticity is not just a technical attribute but a psychological judgment.

Chesney and Citron (2019) argue that synthetic media destabilises traditional assumptions of evidentiary authenticity. This erosion of trust underlines the need to analyse both the objective properties of synthetic voice and the subjective interpretations of the recipients. A strictly positivist framework would neglect the social impacts regarding trust, while a purely interpretivist framework would fail to account for measurable technological advancements.

By adopting pragmatism, this study acknowledges that:

- Deepfake voice realism can be empirically evaluated.
- Trusted in voice communication is socially mediated and context dependent.
- The interaction between technological capability and psychological perception defines the core research problem.

This philosophical flexibility enables integration of quantitative and qualitative elements where necessary, consistent with guidance from Creswell and Creswell (2018)

3.1.2 ONTOLOGICAL AND EPISTEMOLOGICAL POSITIONING

Ontologically, the study aligns with critical realism. Bryman (2016) explains that critical realism recognises the existence of a reality independent of human perception while acknowledging that knowledge of that reality is socially mediated. Deepfake voice systems are materially real technological artefacts, exhibiting measurable properties such as waveform structure, latency and spectral accuracy (Mirsky and Lee, 2021) these characteristics exist regardless of individual interpretation.

However, the impact of such systems in vishing scenarios is dependent upon human cognition. An AI generated voice may be technically synthetic yet perceived as authentic by the recipient. The behavioural outcome such as compliance with fraudulent instruction results from this interpretative process. This dual recognition of objective technological existence and subjective experimental interpretation reflects a critical realist stance.

Epistemologically, knowledge in this study is generated through a combination of empirical observation and interpretative analysis. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) describe this approach as compatible with pragmatic research, where multiple forms of evidence are integrated to answer applied research questions. Empirical measurement may reveal differences in behavioural responses between traditional and AI-enhanced impersonation scenarios. However, explaining these differences requires engagement with established psychological constructs such as authority bias and trust formation (Jagatic et al, 2007; Abroshan et al, 2021)

This epistemological positioning directly responds to the gap identified in chapter 2: the lack of integrated socio-technical analysis within existing deepfake and social engineering literature.

3.1.3 RESEARCH APPROACH

This study adopts a primarily deductive research approach. Deduction involves developing hypotheses or propositions taken from existing theory and testing them within a specific empirical context (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The literature reviewed in chapter 2 provides several theoretical foundations:

- Authority bias and contextual trust in phishing (Jagatic et al, 2007)
- Cognitive susceptibility to manipulation (Abroshan et al, 2021)
- Increasing realism of synthetic media (Mirsky and Lee, 2021)
- Vulnerabilities in voice spoofing detection systems (Korshunov and Marcel, 2018)
- Societal implications of synthetic authenticity erosion (Chesney and Citron, 2019)

Drawing on these foundations, the deductive premise of this study is that enhancing impersonation realism through AI generated voice may intensify established psychological mechanisms underlining social engineering attacks. In other words, if authority bias and trust in familiar voices increase compliance in traditional vishing contexts, then synthetic voice realism may amplify these vulnerabilities.

However, the research design remains open to limited abductive refinement. Creswell and Creswell (2018) note that contemporary applied research often combines deductive structure with flexibility for theoretical adjustment where unexpected findings emerge. Should results indicate heightened scepticism toward synthetic voice, this may suggest evolving digital awareness or trust recalibration, thereby contributing to theoretical development rather than simple confirmation.

This structured yet adaptable approach ensures that the research remains grounded in established theory while capable of contributing novel insight into AI-enabled vishing dynamics.

3.1.4 RESEARCH STRATEGY

The research strategy is designed to operationalise the interdisciplinary integration identified as lacking in the literature. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) emphasise that research strategy should logically follow from philosophical positioning and research questions. Given the pragmatic paradigm adopted here, the strategy prioritises applied empirical investigation supported by critical engagement with secondary literature.

Unlike conceptual analyses that discuss deepfake risks at a theoretical level (Chesney and Citron, 2019), this study seeks measurable behavioural evidence. Similarly, it extends beyond technical benchmarking studies (Korshunov and Marcel, 2018) by incorporating psychological variables. The strategy therefore seeks to bridge technical realism assessment and behavioural response analysis.

Specifically, the research strategy aims to:

- Examine behavioural responses to simulated vishing scenarios.
- Compare perceived authenticity between human impersonation and AI generated voice
- Assess whether synthetic voice alters established psychological manipulation

This strategy aligns with Cresswell and Cresswell's (2018) guidance that applied research addressing complex societal issues often requires integration of methodological perspectives. By grounding methodological decisions in established research philosophy literature while situating the inquiry within specific scholarship, the study establishes a coherent and academically robust foundation for the research design outlined in 3.2

3.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

Building upon the pragmatic philosophical foundation established in section 3.1, this study adopts a multi-method research design combining quantitative dataset analysis with qualitative case study examination. This design reflects the socio-technical nature of deepfake enabled vishing and directly addresses the inter disciplinary gaps identified in Chapter 2

Cresswell and Cresswell (2018) argue that mixed or multi method approaches are particularly suitable where research problems involve both measurable phenomena and contextual interpretation. Similarly, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) emphasise that research design should align with the research question rather than conform to a single methodological tradition. Given that this study seeks to understand both measurable patterns in AI-assisted fraud and the contextual dynamics of real-world incidents, a multi method design.

3.2.1 QUANTITATIVE DATASET ANALYSIS

The quantitative component of this study involves secondary analysis of relevant cybersecurity and fraud datasets. Dataset analysis allows identification of measurable trends in:

- Frequency of AI-assisted fraud incidents
- Growth patterns in vishing attacks
- Financial impact of voice based social engineering
- Detection success and failure rates

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) note that secondary quantitative analysis is appropriate where reliable datasets already exist and where the research aims to identify patterns or correlations. In the context of deepfake enabled fraud, datasets may include law enforcement statistics, cybersecurity industry reports or publicly available fraud trend data.

This component addresses a key gap identified in section 2.8, mainly the limited empirical measurement of deepfake enabled vishing prevalence. While Europol (2023) and industry sources highlight emerging threats, systematic academic quantification remains limited. By analysing datasets, this research provides measurable evidence regarding the scale and trajectory of AI enhanced social engineering.

From a positivist perspective within pragmatic framework, this stage treats fraud incidents and detection metrics as observable phenomena capable of statistical examination.

3.2.2 QUALITATIVE CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

To complement quantitative findings, this study incorporates qualitative case study analysis of documented deepfake enabled fraud incidents. Yin (2018) defines case study research as an empirical method that investigates contemporary

phenomena within real world contexts, particularly where boundaries between phenomenon and context are unclear. This is highly applicable to deepfake vishing, where technological capability, organisational response and human behaviour are deeply connected.

Case studies enable exploration of:

- How synthetic voice was deployed operationally
- Organisational vulnerabilities exploited
- Psychological manipulation techniques observed
- Defensive failures or mitigation strategies

While datasets provide scale and frequency, case studies provide contextual richness. Bryman (2016) emphasises that qualitative approaches allow researchers to examine processes, meanings and mechanisms that quantitative data alone cannot reveal. For example, a dataset may show an increase in AI-assisted fraud, but only case level analysis reveals how attackers constructed authority, urgency or familiarity within specific incidents.

This component also directly addresses the conceptual gap identified in chapter 2 regarding the erosion of voice as an authentication mechanism (Chesney and Citron, 2019). Case analysis examination of how organisations responded when traditional trust assumptions failed.

3.2.3 RATIONALE FOR MULTI-METHOD INTEGRATION

The integration of dataset analysis and case study examination reflects the pragmatic paradigm adopted in section 3.1. Cresswell and Cresswell (2018) note that multi-method designs allow researchers to triangulate findings, thereby strengthening validity. In this study:

- Quantitative analysis established empirical patterns and trends
- Qualitative case analysis explains how and why those patterns manifest in practice.

This design enables methodological triangulation, increasing robustness and credibility (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). It also ensures that neither the technological nor the behavioural dimensions of deepfake enabled vishing are examined in isolation.

Rather than treating AI voice fraud solely as a technical detection problem (Korshunov and Marcel, 2018) or solely as a behavioural susceptibility issue (Jagatic et al, 2007; Abroshan et al, 2021), the multi method design synthesis both perspectives. This directly responds to the interdisciplinary disconnect identified in section 2.8.

3.2.4 SCOPE AND DELIMITATIONS

The research design focuses specifically on:

- AI-generated voice in social engineering contexts
- Voice-based impersonation within financial or organisational fraud
- Documented real world incidents and measurable fraud datasets

The study does not examine:

- Political deepfake manipulation
- Purely synthetic media detection algorithm development
- Experimental participant simulations

These delimitations are necessary to maintain analytical depth and ensure feasibility within the projects scope (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). By narrowing the focus to voice-based impersonation within fraud contexts, the study maintains conceptual clarity and direct alignment with its research objectives.

3.3 DATA COLLECTION METHODS

In alignment with the pragmatic and multi-method design established in section 3.2, this study utilises secondary data drawn from publicly available datasets and authoritative industry reports. Secondary data analysis is appropriate where existing data sources provide reliable, large-scale evidence relevant to the research problem (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Cresswell and Cresswell (2018) further note that secondary quantitative data allows researchers to identify macro-level patterns without the ethical and logistical constraints associated with primary data collection.

Given the emerging nature of deepfake enabled vishing, public datasets and institutional threat intelligence reports provide the most reliable and ethically appropriate sources of empirical evidence.

3.3.1 QUANTITATIVE DATASET COLLECTION

The quantitative component of this research draws from publicly accessible cybersecurity and fraud datasets. These datasets were selected based on:

- Relevance to voice-based fraud or impersonation
- Inclusion of fraud typologies related to social engineering
- Institutional credibility
- Public accessibility and transparency

Bryman (2016) emphasises that’s secondary quantitative data must be critically evaluated for reliability, completeness and methodological transparency. Therefore, only datasets produced by established law enforcement agencies, national centres or recognise cybersecurity bodies were included.

The datasets support statistical analysis of:

- Reported vishing incidents
- Financial losses associated with impersonation fraud
- Growth trends in AI-assisted fraud
- Organisational reporting patterns

Dataset/Report	Publisher	Years(s) Used	Relevance to Study	Type of Data	Access Link
<i>Internet Crime Complaint Centre (IC3) Annual Reports</i>	Federal Bureau of Investigation	2020-2024	Includes business email compromise, impersonation fraud and emerging AI-assisted scam reporting	Incident Frequency and financial losses	https://www.ic3.gov/Media/AnnualReports
<i>Fraud the facts</i>	UK Finance	2022-2024	UK fraud statistics including authorised push payment fraud and impersonation scams	Financial loss data	https://www.ukfinance.org.uk/policy-and-guidance/reports-publications/fraud-facts
<i>Annual Fraud Indicator</i>	Crowe UK	2023	National fraud loss estimates including cyber enabled fraud	Economic impact estimates	https://www.crowe.co.uk/insights/annual-fraud-indicator
<i>Crime Survey for England and Wales (Fraud and Computer Misuse)</i>	Office for National Statistics	2022-2024	National victimisation statistics for fraud and computer misuse	Survey-based victimisation data	https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/crimeandjustice/datasets/crimeinenglandandwales

Table 3 - Public Datasets Used for Quantitative Analysis

3.3.2 INDUSTRY AND INSTITUTIONAL REPORTS

To complement statistical datasets, this study incorporates institutional and industry reports that document real world deepfake enabled fraud incidents. Yin (2018) highlights that case study research benefits from authoritative documentation capturing operational and contextual detail.

Industry and Institutional reports were selected where they:

- Explicitly reference AI-generated voice or synthetic media misuse
- Provide documented real-world examples
- Outline defensive challenges and organisation response
- Demonstrate transparency regarding methodology or data sources

These reports are [particularly valuable in emerging threats domains where peer reviewed longitudinal datasets remain limited.

Report Title	Publisher	Year	Relevance	Access Link
<i>Facing Reality? Law enforcement and the Challenge of Deepfakes</i>	Europol	2023	Documents AI-enabled fraud cases and law enforcement challenges	https://www.europol.europa.eu/publications-events/publications/facing-reality-law-enforcement-and-challenge-of-deepfakes
<i>Global Risks Report 2024</i>	World Economic Forum	2024	Identifies generative AI misuse as a global systematic risk	https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-risks-report-2024
<i>Voice Intelligence & Security Report</i>	Pindrop	2020	Synthetic voice fraud trends and call-centre threat analysis	https://www.pindrop.com/resources
<i>AI and Deepfake Risk Insights</i>	Deloitte	2023	Corporate risk implications of AI-enabled fraud	https://www2.deloitte.com/global/en/insights/fo-cus/tech-trends.html
<i>The State of Social Engineering Report</i>	KnowBe4	2023	Evolution of social engineering tactics and defensive measures	https://www.knowbe4.com/resource-center

Table 4 - Industry and Institutional Reports Used for Case Study Analysis

3.3.3 PRIMARY SURVEY DATA COLLECTION

This study incorporates primary data collection through a structured online survey designed to evaluate public awareness and understanding of artificial intelligence (AI) generated deepfakes and their potential use in voice phishing (Vishing) attacks.

The inclusion of survey data is essential to complement secondary datasets and institutional reports providing insight into human awareness, perception and vulnerability to emerging AI driven cyber threats. Unlike technical datasets, which capture recorded incidents and financial losses, survey data provides behavioural and cognitive insight into how individuals perceive and respond to these threats in practice.

The survey is intentionally designed to remain non-technical to ensure accessibility for participants from the public. This approach reduces response bias caused by unfamiliarity with cybersecurity terminology and ensures that responses reflect genuine awareness levels rather than technical expertise.

The survey will focus on key thematic areas including:

- Awareness of AI generated voice cloning and deepfake technology
- Understanding of Voice-based phishing attacks
- Perceived likelihood of encountering AI driven impersonation scams
- Confidence in identifying fraudulent or manipulated voice communications

- Prior exposure to phishing or vishing attempts in everyday life.

Responses will be collected using primarily closed-ended questions, including Likert-scale measurement items. This allows for structured quantitative analysis of awareness levels and perception trends, which can be statistically summarised using descriptive methods outlined in Section 3.4

The survey data will be treated as supplementary primary data and will not be used for inferential statistical modelling due to its non-probability sampling design. Instead, it will be used to enhance the interpretive depth of the study and to triangulate findings from secondary data sets and case study analysis.

3.3.4 QUESTIONNAIRE DESIGN AND QUESTION STRUCTURE

The questionnaire was designed using structured principles informed by established research methodologies (Bryman, 2016, Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The design prioritises clarity, accessibility and relevance to ensure reliable responses from a general public audience with varying levels of technical knowledge.

The questionnaire was developed according to the following criteria:

- Use of Clear, non-technical language to ensure accessibility and reduce misinterpretation of questions by participants without prior cybersecurity knowledge.
- Inclusion of closed ended and Likert-scale items to enable quantitative analysis and consistent measurement of responses (Field, 2018)
- Alignment with research objectives, particularly in assessing awareness, perception and behavioural responses to deepfake-enabled vishing threats.
- Incorporation of scenario-based questioning to capture behavioural intent and decision making in realistic situations.
- Logical sequencing of questions, progressing from general awareness to more specific perceptions and experiences, therefore reducing respondent fatigue and improving data quality.

The questionnaire design ensures that collected data can be effectively analysed using descriptive statistical techniques as outlined in section 3.4.3. the use of structured response formats enhances comparability across participants while a limited number of open-ended questions provide additional qualitative insight into public attitudes and concerns. This structured approach supports reliability and validity in questionnaire-based research by minimising, ambiguity and ensuring consistency in how questions are interpreted and answered (Bryman, 2016)

3.3.5 CASE STUDY SELECTION CRITERIA

Case studies were selected according to structured criteria informed by Yin (2018):

- 1) Documented or strongly evidenced use of AI-generated voice impersonation.
- 2) Confirmed financial, organisational or operational impact
- 3) Credible publication source (Law enforcement, regulated financial authority or recognised cybersecurity firm).
- 4) Sufficient contextual detail to enable analysis of psychological manipulation and defensive response.

Purposeful case selection ensures analytical relevance rather than statistical representativeness, consistent with qualitative case methodology principles (Yin, 2018).

3.3.6 INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Inclusion Criteria:

- Reports published between 2020-2024.
- Explicit reference to voice-based impersonation, vishing or AI-assisted deception.
- Produced by reputable institutional, governmental or recognised cybersecurity organisations.
- Publicly accessible to ensure research transparency and replicability.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Anonymous or verifiable blog sources
- Opinion-based commentary without empirical support
- Political deepfake video manipulation unrelated to voice-based fraud
- Reports lacking methodological transparency

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) emphasise that explicit inclusion and exclusion criteria strengthen reliability and allow future researchers to replicate data selection processes.

3.3.6 DATA RELIABILITY, VALIDITY AND TRIANGULATION

The credibility of secondary data depends upon the authority and methodological transparency of its source (Bryman, 2016). Government datasets such as those produced by the FBI and the Office for National Statistics employ structured reporting mechanisms, enhancing reliability. Financial industry reports (e.g UK Finance) are cross referenced with national crime data to mitigate institutional bias.

Triangulation across multiple institutional sources strengthens construct validity (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018) where AI-specific categorisation is not explicitly separated within fraud datasets, contextual trends analysis is conducted cautiously, and limitations are acknowledged explicit within chapter 4.

By combining statistical datasets with institutional case documentation, this study enhances analytical robustness while maintaining transparency and replicability.

3.4 DATA ANALYSIS METHODS

In alignment with the pragmatic research philosophy articulated in section 3.2, this study adopts a multi-layered analytical framework integrating quantitative statistical analysis with qualitative case study synthesis. Pragmatism permits methodological pluralism where methods are selected according to their capacity to answer the research questions rather than adherence to a single epistemological tradition (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018). Accordingly, quantitative techniques are employed to identify measurable trends in impersonation and voice-based fraud, while qualitative analysis provides contextual insight into the mechanisms and operationalisation of deepfake enabled vishing attacks.

The analytical strategy is structured to ensure empirical robustness, reproducibility and cross-national compatibility. By incorporating data from both the United States and the United Kingdom, the study enhances generalisability and mitigates the risk of jurisdiction specific distortion in fraud reporting patterns.

3.4.1 QUANTITATIVE DATA SOURCES AND COMPARATIVE STRUCTURE

Quantitative data for the United States is derived from annual reports published by the Federal Bureau of Investigation through its Internet Crime Complaint Center (IC3). These reports provide structured annual data on cyber-enabled fraud categories, including business email compromise, impersonation scams and related financial losses.

United Kingdom data is sourced from two primary institutions:

- The Office for National Statistics (Crime Survey for England and Wales – Fraud & Computer Misuse datasets), which provides nationally representative victimisation estimates
- UK Finance (Fraud the Facts Reports) which offers verified banking sector financial loss data, including Authorised Push Payment (APP) fraud and impersonation scams.

The decision to combine law enforcement complaint data (US), survey-based victimisation estimates (UK) and industry verified financial data (UK) is deliberate. Each dataset reflects different dimensions of fraud measurement: Reported complaints, victim prevalence and confirmed financial losses. Rather than viewing these differences as limitations the study treats them as complementary indicators of fraud evaluation.

3.4.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The first stage of quantitative analysis involves a comprehensive descriptive statistical examination of impersonation and voice-based fraud trends across the United States and the United Kingdom. Descriptive statistics are essential in social science research for summarising large datasets and identifying observable patterns prior to explanatory modelling (Field, 2018; Bryman, 2016). This stage establishes the empirical foundation of the study by systematically examining the scale, distribution and trajectory of fraud related variables across time.

In alignment with the pragmatic methodological framework outlined earlier, descriptive analysis operationalises the research objectives by translating abstract investigative aims into measurable indicators (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018). Annual incident counts, total financial losses and category specific fraud data are examined to determine longitudinal growth patterns and structural shifts within impersonation related fraud reporting

The Techniques applied in this stage include:

- Annual incident frequency counts
- Aggregation of total and category specific financial losses
- Year on year percentage growth calculations
- Compound annual growth rate (CAGR0) where applicable
- Time series visualisation of fraud trajectories
- Cross national comparative trend analysis

Time series visualisation is particularly important in crime trend analysis as graphical representation enhances the identification of directional movement, volatility and potential inflection points (Weisburd and Britt, 2014). Visual trend examination also assists in determining whether subsequent inferential modelling is appropriate.

Where financial data are compared between jurisdictions, currency normalisation and inflation adjustments will be applied to enhance comparability. Cross national comparative research requires careful standardisation to avoid misinterpretation caused by structural economic differences (Hantrais, 2009). Where appropriate, per-capita scaling may be used to account for population size differences between the United States and the United Kingdom.

Descriptive analysis remains analytically distinct from inferential modelling. At this stage, the purpose is not to test hypothesis or determine statistical significance, but rather this document empirical trends and magnitude of change (Field, 2018). Observed increases or decreases in fraud activity will therefore be reported without casual interpretation. This separation preserves methodical clarity and prevents premature attribution of explanatory mechanisms.

Particularly attention will be given to identifying potential structural shifts across the 2015-2024 study period. Given the rapid evolution of digital communication technologies and artificial intelligence tools during this time frame, temporal segmentation allows for cautious examination of whether observable changes align with broader technological developments. However consistent with best practice in quantitative crime research, descriptive findings will not be framed as casual until formally assessed through inferential modelling in section 3.4.3 (Weisburd and Britt, 2014).

Descriptive statistical analysis therefore performs these core methodological functions within this study. First, it established the empirical scale and trajectory of impersonation and voice-based fraud in each jurisdiction. Second, it enables structured cross-national comparison. Third it provides the statistical baseline necessary for subsequent inferential testing. By grounding interpretation in transparent, reproducible statistical summaries, this stage enhances reliability and strengthens the evidentiary foundation of the research.

3.4.3 SURVEY DATA ANALYSIS (PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION)

This section outlines the analytical approach applied to the primary survey data collected from the public regarding awareness, understanding and perceptions of AI generated deepfakes and their potential role in voice phishing attacks. In alignment with the pragmatic research philosophy adopted in this study, the survey analysis is designed to complement secondary statistical datasets by providing insight into human awareness and behavioural perception rather than objective incident measurement (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018).

Unlike crime datasets sourced from institutional bodies, the survey data reflects subjective awareness levels and perceived risk. As such, the analytical approach prioritises descriptive statistical techniques to summarise response patterns in a structured and interpretable manner. This ensures that findings remain accessible while still contributing meaningfully to the overall triangulation of results within the study.

3.4.3.1 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF SURVEY RESPONSES

Survey responses will be analysed using descriptive statistical methods, which are appropriate for summarising categorical and ordinal data obtained through closed ended and Likert-scale questions. Descriptive statistics are widely used in social research to condense large volumes of response data into interpretable summaries, enabling identification of central tendencies and distribution patterns (Field, 2018, Bryman, 2016).

The analysis will include:

- Frequency distributions of responses for each question
- Percentage breakdowns of awareness levels regarding deepfake technology
- Measures of central tendency (mean and median) for Likert-scale items
- Visual representation of findings using bar charts and pie charts
- Comparative summaries across demographic variables where applicable (e.g, age groups or digital literacy levels)

This stage of analysis is intended to establish a clear overview of public understanding of AI-driven impersonation threats. Particular attention will be given to identifying gaps in awareness, misconceptions and variability in perceived risk across respondent groups.

3.4.3.2 THEMATIC INTERPRETATION OF PERCEPTION TRENDS

As well as numerical summaries, the survey will be interpreted thematically to identify broader patterns in public perception. While the survey primarily generates quantitative data, certain structured responses (particularly Likert-scale patterns) allow for interpretive grouping into thematic categories.

These themes may include:

- Awareness of AI-generated voice cloning technologies
- Perceived vulnerability to voice-based scams
- Trust in voice communication as an authentication method
- Confidence in identifying fraudulent or manipulated audio content

This interpretive layer provides contextual depth to the descriptive statistics and allows the findings to be linked more explicitly to the broader research aims concerning human susceptibility to deepfake enabled vishing.

3.4.3.3 DEMOGRAPHIC CROSS-TABULATION ANALYSIS

Where demographic data is collected (e.g age range, occupation type or self-reported digital literacy), cross tabulation analysis will be used to explore relationships between respondent characteristics and awareness levels. Cross tabulation is a widely used statistical technique for examining associations between categorical variables in survey research (Field, 2018)

This analysis may examine relationships such as:

- Age group versus awareness of deepfake technology
- Digital literacy versus perceived vulnerability to scams
- Prior exposure to phishing or vishing attempts versus confidence in detection

The purpose of this analysis is not to infer causation but to identify patterns of association between demographic factors and perception levels. This approach is consistent with exploratory survey research methodology and supports broader interpretive analysis within the study (Bryman, 2016)

3.4.3.4 LIMITATIONS OF SURVEY DATA ANALYSIS

The survey component of this study is subject to several methodological limitations that must be acknowledged to ensure transparency and validity, the use of non-probability convenience sampling limits the extent to which findings can be generalised to the wider population. As such, result is indicative rather than statistically representative (Bryman, 2016)

As well as this, self-reported data introduces potential bias, including recall bias and social desirability bias, which may influence how respondents perceive and report their level of awareness or confidence. Respondents may also interpret questions differently depending on their prior exposure to cybersecurity concepts, introducing variability in response reliability.

Despite these limitations, survey data remains valuable in providing exploratory insight into public awareness of emerging AI-enabled cyber threats. When combined with secondary datasets and case study analysis, it contributes to a triangulated understanding of deepfake enabled phishing risk (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2018)

3.4.3.5 INTEGRATION WITHIN THE OVERALL ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

The survey findings are not analysed in isolation but are integrated within the broader mixed methods framework of this study. This integration enables comparison between public perception data, institutional fraud statistics and qualitative case study evidence.

Specifically, survey results complement:

- Quantitative fraud trend data derived from institutional datasets
- Inferential statistical modelling of impersonation-related cyber crim trends
- Qualitative case studies from organisations such as Europol and Deloitte

This triangulation strengthens the validity of the study by combining macro-level statistical evidence with macro level human perception data, thereby providing a more holistic understanding of deepfake enabled phishing and its implications for cybersecurity (Creswell and Creswell, 2018)

3.4.4 INFERENCE STATISTICAL MODELLING

While descriptive statistical analysis establishes observable trends and patterns, inferential statistical modelling is required to determine whether these patterns reflect statistically meaningful relationships rather than random variation. Inferential methods enable the researcher to draw conclusions about broader phenomena based on sample data and to assess the strength and significance of relationships between variables (Field, 2018, Bryman, 2016). Within this study, inferential analysis is used to evaluate temporal changes in fraud patterns and to explore whether structural shifts can be identified across the study period.

In accordance with the pragmatic research framework, inferential modelling is applied selectively and cautiously, recognising both its explanatory value and its limitations when working with secondary, aggregated datasets (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). The analysis focuses on identifying statistically significant trends and associations rather than establishing direct causality.

3.4.4.1 TIME-SERIES REGRESSION ANALYSIS

To assess whether impersonation related fraud has increased systematically over time, a linear time series regression model will be employed. Regression analysis is widely used in social science research to model relationships between dependent and independent variables and to estimate the direction and magnitude of change (Field, 2018)

The general model is specified as:

$$\text{Fraud Loss} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Year}) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

- β_0 represents the intercept
- β_1 represents the rate of change over time
- ε represents the error term

a statistically significant positive coefficient for the year variable would indicate that fraud losses have increased in a consistent and measurable manner across the observed period. This provides a more robust analytical basis than descriptive trend observation alone.

Given that annual crime data typically produce relatively small sample sizes, the model will be interpreted with caution. Small-N- time-series data can limit statistical power and increase sensitivity to outliers, an issue widely recognised in quantitative social research (Bryman, 2016). As such will be contextualised rather than overstated.

3.4.4.2 INTERRUPTED TREND ANALYSIS

To explore whether fraud trends exhibit structural changes over time, an interrupted trend model will be introduced. This approach is commonly used to evaluate the impact of external events or systemic changes within time series data (Wagner et al, 2002)

The model incorporates a binary indicator variable representing the period following 2022:

$$\text{Fraud Loss} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Year}) + \beta_2(\text{post-2022}) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

Post-2022 is coded as 0 for years prior to 2022 and 1 for 2022 onward

This model tests whether there is a statistically significant shift in fraud levels after 2022, a period associated with increased accessibility of generative artificial intelligence tools. However, consistent with best practice in statistical interpretation, any observed relationship will be framed as an association rather than the evidence of causation. As noted by Field (2018), regression models can identify relationships between variables but cannot in isolation, establish causal mechanisms.

The inclusion of this model perfects an exploratory analytical objective: to assess whether temporal changes align with broader technological developments identified in the literature. Any findings will be interpreted alongside qualitative evidence presented in later sections.

3.4.4.3 CROSS-NATIONAL COMPARATIVE

To enhance analytical depth and external validity, inferential models will be applied separately to datasets from the United States and the United Kingdom. Comparative analysis allows the study to assess whether observed trends are consistent across different regulatory, economic and reporting environments.

Cross-national research introduces additional methodological complexity, particularly in relation to data comparability. Differences in reporting structures, classification systems and data collection methodologies must be carefully considered (Hantrais, 2009) to mitigate these issues, the analysis will prioritise compatible indicators, such as total financial loss and broad fraud categories, rather than highly granular classifications.

Where appropriate, results from separate regression models will be compared in terms of:

- Direction of trends
- Magnitude of change (coefficient size)
- Statistical significance levels

This approach allows identification of convergent or divergent fraud trajectories between jurisdictions, strengthening the generalisability of findings.

3.4.4.4 STATISTICAL ASSUMPTIONS AND MODEL VALIDITY

Prior to conducting regression analysis, key statistical assumptions will be assessed to ensure model validity. These include:

- Linearity of the relationship between variables
- Independence of observations
- Homoscedasticity of residuals
- Normality of error distribution

Testing these assumptions is essential to ensure that regression results are statistically reliable and not distorted by violations of underlying model conditions (Field, 2018). Given the time series nature of the data, potential autocorrelation will also be considered, as serial dependence may affect the validity of standard regression estimates

Statistical significance will be evaluated using conventional thresholds ($p < 0.05$), while confidence intervals and effect sizes will be reported to provide a more comprehensive interpretation of results. As recommended by Bryman (2016), reliance on p-values alone will be avoided in favour of a more nuanced interpretation of statistical outcomes.

3.4.4.5 LIMITATIONS OF INFERENTIAL ANALYSIS

Despite its value, inferential statistical modelling in this study is subject to several limitations. The use of aggregated secondary datasets means that deepfake-enabled phishing cannot be isolated directly, with data typically reported under broader fraud or impersonation categories. As a result, findings reflect general trends rather than deepfake specific activity.

The relatively small number of annual observations also limits statistical power and increases sensitivity to outliers, reducing the robustness of regression models (Bryman, 2016). As well as this, potential confounding variables, such as economic conditions, reporting practices and regulatory changes are not controlled for meaning that identified relationships cannot be interpreted as casual (Field, 2018).

Cross national comparisons between the United States and United Kingdom may also be affected by differences in reporting frameworks and data collection methods (Hantrais, 2009). Furthermore, underreporting of cybercrime may lead to an underestimation of the true scale of fraud.

Overall, inferential analysis in this study is explanatory in nature, aiming to identify patterns and associations rather than establish definitive casual relationships.

3.5 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Ethical considerations are fundamental to ensuring that this research is conducted responsibly and in accordance with established academic standards. This study adheres to key ethical principles, including informed consent, confidentiality, voluntary participation and data protection (Bryman, 2016)

For the primary data collection component, participants in the questionnaire will be provided with a clear explanation of the study's purpose prior to participation. Informed consent will be obtained, ensuring that that individuals understand their involvement is voluntary and that they may withdraw at any stage without consequence. No personally identifiable information will be collected, and all responses will remain anonymous to protect participant privacy.

Data collected from the questionnaire will be stored securely and used solely for academic purposes. This aligns data protection principles and relevant regulatory frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation which emphasises the secure handling and processing of personal data within research contexts (ICO, 2023).

The use of secondary data sources, including datasets from organisations such as the FBI, ONS and UK Finance, does not raise significant ethical concerns as these are publicly available and anonymised. However, care will be taken to ensure that all data is accurately represented and appropriately cited to maintain academic integrity.

As well as this, when analysing case studies involving cybercrime incidents, sensitivity will be maintained to avoid misinterpretation or harm to individuals or organisations referenced within publicly available reports. The research will focus on analytical insights rather than attributing blame.

Overall, ethical considerations are integrated throughout the research design to ensure that the study maintains integrity, protects participants and adheres to recognised academic and legal standards.

3.6 METHODOLOGICAL LIMITATIONS

This study acknowledges several methodological limitations associated with the use of mixed methods, secondary datasets and primary questionnaire data, recognising these limitations is essential for maintaining transparency and ensuring that findings are interpreted appropriately (Bryman, 2016)

3.6.1 LIMITATIONS OF SECONDARY QUANTITATIVE DATA

The study relies on aggregated secondary datasets from sources such as the FBI, ONS and UK finance. While these datasets are credible and provide large scale insights into fraud trends, they do not specifically isolate deepfake-enabled vishing incidents. Instead, such activities are typically categorised under broader fraud or impersonation classifications, limiting the precision of analysis.

As well as this, reporting inconsistencies and the likelihood of underreporting in cybercrime datasets may affect the accuracy of findings. Victims may not recognise or report incidents, particularly in emerging threat areas such as AI-enabled fraud. As a result, the data should be interpreted as indicative of broader trends rather than an exact representation of real-world activity (Field, 2018)

3.6.2 LIMITATIONS OF QUESTIONNAIRE DATA

The questionnaire utilises a non-probability convenience sampling method, which restricts the ability to generalise findings to the wider population. Participants are self-selected, which may introduce sampling bias and reduce the representativeness of the results (Bryman, 2016)

Furthermore, the reliance on self-reported responses introduces potential biases, including social desirability and subjective interpretation, as the questionnaire is designed to be accessible to a general audience, it avoids technical complexity, which may limit the depth of insight into more advanced cybersecurity knowledge and understanding.

3.6.3 LIMITATIONS OF CROSS-NATIONAL COMPARISON

This study compares datasets from the United States and the United Kingdom, which introduces challenges due to differences in data collection methodologies, classification systems and reporting frameworks. These structural differences may affect the consistency and comparability of the datasets.

Although efforts are made to standardise variables where possible, complete alignment between datasets cannot be guaranteed. As a result, cross national comparisons should be interpreted cautiously, with an understanding that observed differences may partly reflect variations in reporting practices rather than actual differences in fraud activity (Hantrais, 2009).

3.6.4 LIMITATIONS OF RAPIDLY EVOLVING TECHNOLOGY

Deepfake and AI technologies are evolving rapidly, which presents a limitation in terms of the timeliness of available data and research. Existing datasets and literature may not fully capture the most recent developments in AI-generated voice technology or emerging attack methods.

This creates a temporal limitation, where findings represent a snapshot of an evolving threat landscape. As a result, conclusions drawn from the study may require ongoing reassessment as new technologies and attack vectors continue to develop.

3.6.5 OVERALL METHODOLOGICAL CONSTRAINTS

The mixed methods approach adopted in this study enhances analytical depth through the integration of quantitative data, questionnaire responses and qualitative case studies. However, combining these different data types introduces complexity in ensuring consistency and coherence across findings.

As well as this, the study is exploratory in nature, focusing on identifying patterns and relationships rather than establishing definitive casual conclusions. While this approach is appropriate for an emerging research area, it limits the extent to which findings can be generalised or used to predict future trends with certainty.

3.7 CHAPTER SUMMARY

This chapter has outlined the methodological framework adopted for this study, grounded in a pragmatic research philosophy that's supports the integration of multiple data sources and analytical approaches (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). A mixed methods design was employed, combining secondary quantitative datasets, primary questionnaire data and qualitative case study analysis to provide a comprehensive examination of deepfake enabled vishing.

The chapter detailed the processes of data collection, including the use of institutional datasets, industry reports and a structured questionnaire designed to assess public awareness and perception. It also established the analytical techniques applied, including descriptive statistical analysis, inferential modelling and thematic interpretation. Ethical considerations and methodological limitations were addressed to ensure transparency and academic integrity.

Overall, this methodological approach provides a robust foundation for the subsequent analysis presented in Chapter 4, where the collected data will be examined to identify patterns, relationships and insights into the evolving threat of deepfake enabled voice phishing.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents and analyses the findings derived from multiple data sources, including secondary quantitative datasets, primary questionnaire responses and a real-world case study. The aim is to examine the scale, patterns and implications of fraud and impersonation-based cybercrime, alongside public awareness and perception of deepfake-enabled vishing.

The chapter is structured to reflect the mixed methods approach outlined in Chapter 3. It begins with an analysis of large-scale fraud datasets from the United States and the United Kingdom, followed by findings from the questionnaire and concludes with a real-world case study. This approach enables both macro level trend analysis and micro level insight into human awareness and behaviour, supporting a comprehensive understanding of the evolving threat landscape (Creswell and Creswell, 2018)

4.2 DATASET ANALYSIS (QUANTITATIVE)

This study utilises two primary secondary data sources to examine fraud trends across different national contexts: the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) Internet Crime Complaint Center (IC3) reports for the United States and UK finance fraud reports for the United Kingdom. These sources are widely recognised for their reliability and are frequently used in both academic and industry research.

The FBI IC3 dataset provides annual data on reported cybercrime complaints and associated financial losses in the United States. In 2023, the IC3 recorded over 880,000 complaints with reported losses exceeding \$12.5 billion, representing a significant increase compared to previous years. This figure rose further in 2024, with reported losses exceeding \$16 billion, highlighting a continued upward trend in cyber enabled fraud.

Similarly, UK finance provides detailed annual reporting on fraud losses within the UK financial sector. In 2023, total fraud losses were recorded at approximately £1.17 billion, with authorised push payment (APP) fraud alone accounting for £459.7 million. These figures remained consistently high in 2024, again exceeding £1 billion, demonstrating the persistent scale of fraud within the UK

Both datasets highlight the prominence of impersonation-based fraud and social engineering techniques, which are directly relevant to the study of vishing and deepfake enabled attacks. The inclusion of both US and UK data enables cross national comparison, therefore strengthening the generalisability of findings and providing a broader perspective on global fraud trends.

4.2.2 FRAUD TRENDS IN THE UNITED STATES

The Federal Bureau of Investigation Internet Crime Complaint Center provides annual data on cybercrime complaints and associated financial losses within the United States. This dataset offers a reliable indicator of large-scale fraud trends and is widely used in both academic and industry research.

As shown in figure 1, reported financial losses have increased significantly over the observed period, rising from approximately \$10.3 billion in 2022 to \$12.5 billion in 2023, before reaching over \$16 billion in 2024. This represents a substantial upward trend in cyber enabled financial crime, highlighting the growing scale and impact of fraud within the United States.

Figure 1 - FBI Reported Losses with Regression Line

To quantify this trend, a simple linear regression model was applied using the standard equation:

$$y = mx + c$$

where:

- y = financial loss (USD billions)
- x = year
- m = slope (rate of increase)
- c = intercept

Using the Dataset (2022-2024) the calculated regression equation is approximately:

$$Y = 2.85x - 5753.7$$

This indicates that, on average, reported losses increased by approximately \$2.85 billion per year over the observed period. The regression line shown in figure 1 represents this calculated trend.

The upward trajectory of the regression line indicates a strong positive relationship between time and reported financial losses, suggesting that cybercrime is not only increasing but doing so at a consistent rate. While the limited number of data points restricts definitive statistical conclusions, the trend provides a clear indication of sustained growth.

The increase can be linked to the continued reliance on social engineering techniques, including phishing, impersonation and voice-based fraud. The IC3 consistently identifies phishing and impersonation scams as among the most prevalent forms of cybercrime, both of which form the foundation of vishing attacks. As these techniques evolve, the integration of artificial intelligence, particularly deepfake voice technology has the potential to further enhance their effectiveness (Mirsky and Lee, 2021)

Overall, the findings from the IC3 dataset suggest that fraud within the United States is increasing in both scale and financial impact. This upward trend reinforces the importance of examining emerging technologies such as AI-generated voice impersonation, as potential drivers for future cybercrime growth.

4.2.3 FRAUD TRENDS IN THE UNITED KINGDOM (UK FINANCE)

Fraud data within the United Kingdom is primarily reported by UK Finance, which provides annual insights into financial losses across various fraud categories. These reports are widely recognised for their reliability and offer a detailed overview of fraud trends within the UK financial sector.

As illustrated in figure 2, tool reported fraud losses remained consistently high over the observed period, with losses recorded at approximately £1.2 billion in 2022, followed by £1.17 billion in both 2023 and 2024. While this reflects a slight decrease from 2022, the overall trend indicates that fraud levels remain persistently high, demonstrating the continued prevalence of financial crime within the UK.

Figure 2 - UK Finance Fraud Losses with Regression Line

To further examine this trend, a linear regression model was applied using the standard equation:

$$Y = mx + c$$

Where:

- Y = financial loss (GBP billions)
- X = year
- M = slope (rate of change)
- C = intercept

Using the dataset (2022-2024), the calculated regression equation is approximately:

$$Y = -0.015x + 31.53$$

This indicates a slight average decrease of approximately £0.015 billion per year. However, this change is minimal and does not represent a significant reduction in fraud activity, the regression line shown in figure 2 reflects this relatively stable trend.

Unlike the upward trajectory observed in the United States, the UK data suggests a plateau in fraud losses rather than continued growth. This may indicate that while fraud is not increasing at the same rate, it remains embedded within the financial ecosystem at a consistently high level. Notably, a significant proportion of UK fraud is driven by authorised push payment (APP) scams, which rely heavily on social engineering and impersonation tactics.

These findings remain highly relevant to the study of phishing and deepfake-enabled attacks. The persistence of impersonation-based fraud suggests that attackers continue to exploit trust and human behaviour, key factors that could

be further amplified with AI-generated voice technology. As highlighted in existing research, the integration of AI into social engineering attacks increases their realism and effectiveness (Mirsky and Lee, 2021).

Overall, the UK finance data demonstrates that while fraud growth may be less pronounced than in the United States, the threats remain significant and sustained this reinforces the importance of addressing both technological and human vulnerabilities in the context of emerging cyber threats such as deepfake enabled vishing.

4.2.4 CROSS-NATIONAL COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

This section provides a comparative analysis of fraud trends in the United States and the United Kingdom, drawing on data from the Federal Bureau of Investigation Internet Crime Complaint Center (IC3) and UK Finance respectively. By examining trends across both datasets, this analysis aims to identify similarities and differences in the scale and trajectory of fraud, with relevance to impersonation-based cybercrime.

As shown in figure 3, a clear divergence is evident between two national contexts. Reported fraud losses in the United States demonstrate a strong upward trajectory, increasing substantially between 2022 and 2024. In contrast, fraud losses within the United Kingdom remain relatively stable across the same period, with only minor fluctuations observed. This suggests that while fraud is increasing rapidly in the United States, it remains consistently high but comparatively stable in the United Kingdom.

Figure 3 - Comparison of Fraud Losses: US vs UK

The regression analyses conducted in section 4.2.3 and 4.2.4 further support this distinction. The United States exhibits a positive regression slope, indicating a sustained increase in financial losses over time, whereas the United Kingdom demonstrates a near flat or slightly negative slope, reflecting minimal change. These findings suggest that the growth rate of cyber-enabled fraud differs significantly between the two countries, despite both exercising substantial financial impact.

Several factors may contribute to this divergence. Differences in reporting frameworks, financial systems and fraud classification methods can influence how data is recorded and interpreted (Hantrais, 2009). As well as this, variations in regulatory approaches, public awareness and institutional responses to cybercrime may affect the rate at which fraud evolves within each country.

Despite these differences, a key similarity exists in fraud observed across both datasets. In both the United States and the United Kingdom, a significant proportion of fraud involves social engineering and impersonation-based techniques. these

forms of attack rely on ion psychological manipulation, trust exploitation and urgency, core characteristics that underline vishing attacks. As identified in earlier chapters, these techniques are increasingly being enhanced using artificial intelligence, including deepfake voice technology (Mirsky and Lee, 2021).

From a research perspective, this comparison highlights an important insight: while the scale and growth rate of fraud may vary across national contexts, the underlying mechanisms driving these attacks remain consistent. This suggests that emerging threats such as deepfake enabled vishing are likely to have global relevance, even if their measurable impact differs between regions.

It is important to acknowledge that direct comparison between the datasets is subject to limitations. Differences in currency, reporting practices and data categorisation restrict the ability to make precise quantitative comparisons. However, the analysis of overall trends and patterns remains valid and provides valuable insight into the broader evolution of cyber enabled fraud.

Overall, the cross-national analysis demonstrates that fraud is both a rapidly growing and persistently embedded threats, depending on the context in which it is examined. These findings reinforce the need for adaptive cybersecurity strategies that address not only technological developments but also the human factors that enable impersonation-based attacks.

4.3 QUESTIONNAIRE ANALYSIS (PRIMARY DATA)

This section presents the findings from the questionnaire conducted as part of this study, aimed at assessing public awareness, understanding and perceptions of artificial intelligence (AI) deepfakes and their potential use in voice phishing (vishing) attacks. In contrast to the dataset analysis presented in Section 4.2, which examines large scale fraud trends, this section focuses on the human dimension of cybersecurity, specifically how individuals perceive and respond to emerging threats.

The questionnaire was designed to capture baseline awareness levels and behavioural tendencies among a public audience, using structured questions and Likert-scale responses as outlined in chapter 3. The analysis applies descriptive statistical techniques to summarise response patterns, alongside interpretative discussion to identify key trends and insights (Bryman, 2016, Field, 2018).

4.3.1 SECTION 1: PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS AND DIGITAL CONFIDENCE

4.3.1.1 AGE DISTRIBUTION

Understanding the demographic composition of respondents is important in contextualising the findings, as age can influence familiarity with technology, exposure to cyber threats and susceptibility to social engineering.

Figure 4 - Age Distribution of Respondents

As shown in figure 4, the largest proportion of respondents falls within the 45-54 age group (30.5%), Followed by 18-24 (19.2%) and 35-44 (15.9%). This distribution indicates a moderate concentration of middle-aged participants, with representation across both younger and older groups.

This demographic spread is significant for two reasons. Firstly, middle-aged individuals have been identified as frequent targets for financial scams due to greater financial engagement and access to resources, making them attractive to attackers (federal bureau of Investigation, 2023). Secondly, generational differences in digital exposure influence how individuals interpret emerging technologies. Younger individuals tend to demonstrate greater familiarity with devices and digital systems, whereas older individuals may rely more heavily on trust-based communication patterns (Ofcom,2022) this reliance on trust can increase susceptibility to social engineering attacks, particularly those involving voice impersonation (Hadnagy, 2018).

4.3.1.2 DIGITAL CONFIDENCE

Figure 5 - Digital Confidence Levels

Most respondents reported being somewhat confident (52.3%, with 24.5% indicating high confidence. While this suggests a digitally capable sample, prior research indicates that digital confidence does not necessarily correlate with cybersecurity awareness or the ability to detect sophisticated threats (ENISA, 2023). Individuals may be comfortable using digital technologies while lacking an understanding of how these technologies can be exploited in cybercrime. This distinction is particularly important in the context of AI-driven attacks, where familiarity with technology may lead to overconfidence, potentially increasing vulnerability to deception.

Furthermore, the distribution of responses suggests a potential imbalance between perceived competence and actual risk awareness. With over three-quarters of respondents identifying as either somewhat or very confident, there is an indication that individuals may overestimate their ability to recognise and respond to cyber threats. This is particularly relevant in the context of social engineering, where attackers exploit human judgement rather than technical vulnerabilities. Research has shown that individuals with higher self-perceived competence may be less likely to question suspicious interactions, especially when communication appears familiar or credible (Hadnagy, 2018). In the case of AI-enabled vishing, where voice replication can convincingly mimic trusted individuals, this overconfidence may reduce the likelihood of verification of behaviours, thereby increasing susceptibility to deception. Consequently, while digital confidence is generally high within the sample, it may paradoxically contribute to increased risk when not accompanied by targeted cybersecurity awareness and critical evaluation skills.

4.3.2 SECTION 2: AWARENESS OF DEEPPAKES

4.3.2.1 GENERAL AWARENESS OF DEEPPAKE TECHNOLOGY

Have you heard of the term "Deepfake" before?

151 responses

Figure 6 - Awareness of Deepfake Technology

A total of 79.5% of respondents reported awareness of deepfakes, indicating that the concept has entered mainstream discourse. This aligns with recent research suggesting that public awareness of deepfakes has increased significantly due to media coverage and concerns around misinformation (Mirsky and Lee, 2021). However, awareness alone does not imply an ability to detect or understand such content.

Despite the relatively high level of awareness, this finding should be interpreted with caution. Awareness of the term “deepfake” does not necessarily indicate an understanding of its technical capabilities or its potential applications in cybercrime. Research suggests that public exposure to deepfakes is often shaped by media narratives, which tend to focus on visual manipulation and misinformation rather than practical security implications (Mirsky and Lee, 2021). As a result, individuals may associate deepfakes primarily with video content, overlooking other forms such as audio-based deepfakes that are increasingly used in vishing attacks. This disconnect between conceptual awareness and practical understanding may reduce the ability of individuals to recognise threats in real world scenarios, particularly when deepfake technology is integrated into familiar communication channels such as phone calls. Consequently, while awareness levels appear high, the effectiveness of this awareness in supporting threat detection remains uncertain.

4.3.2.2 UNDERSTANDING OF DEEPFAKES

if yes, how would you describe your understanding of deepfakes?

151 responses

Figure 7 - Understanding of Deepfakes

While awareness is high, understanding remains limited, with only 23.2% demonstrating strong comprehension. This gap between awareness and understanding is well documented in cybersecurity literature, where users often recognise threats conceptually but lack knowledge required to identify them in practice (ENISA, 2023). This limitation is particularly relevant in the context of deepfakes, which are designed to appear highly realistic and therefore difficult to detect.

This limitation becomes particularly significant when considering the evolving sophistication of deepfake technologies. As deepfakes continue to improve in realism, the ability to critically assess content becomes increasingly important for

effective threat detection. Individuals with only a basic or limited understanding may rely on outdated cues, such as visual inconsistencies or unnatural speech patterns, which are becoming less reliable as the technology advances. Research indicates that attackers exploit this knowledge gap by leveraging highly convincing content to bypass traditional indicators of deception (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). In the context of vishing, this is especially concerning, as audio deepfakes can replicate tone, emotion and familiarity, making detection even more challenging. Consequently, the gap identified in figure 7 suggest not only a lack of knowledge, but a potential increase in vulnerability as attack methods become more sophisticated and harder to recognise.

4.3.2.3 AWARENESS OF AI VOICE REPLICATION

Figure 8 - Awareness of Voice Cloning

Awareness of AI Voice Replication is notably high (91.4%), suggesting that respondents are familiar with the capability of AI to imitate voices. However, this awareness may be superficial, as individuals may not fully understand how such technology can be weaponised in cybercrime. Research indicates that attackers increasingly exploit emerging technologies in combination with traditional social engineering techniques to enhance credibility and success rates (Mirsky and Klee, 2021)

This finding also highlights a potential disparity between technological awareness and perceived personal risk. While respondents may recognise that AI can replicate human voices, this does not necessarily translate into understanding of how easily such technology can be accessed or deployed in real world-attacks. Research suggests that individuals often underestimate the likelihood of becoming a target, even when they are aware of the underlying technology (ENISA, 2023). In the context of vishing, this is particularly concerning, as attackers can leverage publicly available audio data, such as social media content, to create convincing voice clones with minimal effort. As a result, high awareness of voice replication may create a false sense of preparedness, where individuals acknowledge the technology but fail to adapt their behaviour accordingly. This reinforces the need for awareness initiatives to move beyond informing individuals of technological capabilities and instead focus on practical implications and defensive behaviours.

4.3.3 SECTION 3: AWARENESS OF VISHING AND EXPOSURE

4.3.3.1 AWARENESS OF VISHING

Have you heard of voice phishing (vishing)?

151 responses

Figure 9 - Awareness of Vishing

Only 60.3% of respondents reported awareness of vishing, which is significantly lower than awareness of related technologies. This reflects findings from industry reports, which highlight that while awareness of general cyber threats is increasing, knowledge of specific attack methods remains limited (UK Finance, 2023). This lack of awareness may reduce the ability of individuals to recognise and respond to vishing attacks effectively.

This gap in awareness is particularly significant when considered alongside the high levels of exposure to suspicious calls identified in subsequent results. While most respondents reported encountering potentially fraudulent calls, a substantial portion were unable to identify these interactions as vishing. This suggests a disconnect between experience and understanding, where individuals may recognise that something is unusual without being able to classify or respond to it appropriately. From a cybersecurity perspective, this lack of conceptual recognition can limit the effectiveness of defensive behaviours, as individuals who are unaware of a specific attack type may be less likely to apply appropriate mitigation strategies. Furthermore, as vishing increasingly incorporates advanced technologies such as AI generated voice impersonation, the absence of awareness may further amplify vulnerability, as individuals are less prepared to question or verify seemingly legitimate voice-based communication.

4.3.3.2 EXPOSURE TO SUSPICIOUS CALLS

Have you ever received a suspicious or unexpected phone call asking for personal or financial information?

151 responses

Figure 10 - Experience with Suspicious Calls

A majority (58.3%) reported receiving suspicious calls, indicating widespread exposure to potential vishing attempts. This aligns with data from the Federal Bureau of Investigation (2023), which identifies phishing and impersonation-based scams as among the most reported cybercrimes. The relevance of such experiences highlights the real-world relevance of vishing as a growing threat.

However, the high level of reported exposure also raises important questions regarding the effectiveness of current awareness and prevention strategies. Despite most respondents encountering suspicious calls, either findings indicate that not all individuals possess the knowledge or confidence required to identify these interactions as vishing attempts. This suggests that exposure alone is insufficient in developing effective defensive behaviour, particularly when attacks are designed to appear legitimate and exploit trust. Research in social engineering highlights that repeated exposure to low-level threat can lead to desensitisation, where individuals become less cautious over time, especially if previous encounters did not result in harm (Hadnagy, 2018). In the context of AI-enhanced vishing, this is particularly concerning, as increasingly realistic voice impersonation may reduce suspicion and increase the likelihood of compliance. Consequently, the findings suggest that widespread exposure, when combined with limited awareness and evolving attack sophistication, which may contribute to an elevated risk environment rather than improved resilience.

4.3.3.3 CONFIDENCE IN IDENTIFYING FRAUD

Figure 11 - Confidence in Detecting Fraudulent Calls

While respondents expressed moderate confidence, research suggests that self-reported confidence is often not reflective of actual detection ability, particularly in complex or high-pressure scenarios (Hadnagy, 2018) this discrepancy represents a significant vulnerability, as attackers rely on overconfidence and behavioural biases to manipulate victims.

This discrepancy between perceived confidence and actual capability is particularly significant in the context of increasingly sophisticated cyber threats. As vishing attacks evolve through the integration of AI-generated voice technologies, traditional indicators of fraud, such as unusual tone, hesitation or inconsistencies, are becoming less reliable. Individuals who rely on intuition or prior experience may therefore be less equipped to identify deception when it closely mimics legitimate communication. Furthermore, cognitive biases such as familiarity and urgency can impair decision-making, leading individuals to act quickly without sufficient verification (Hadnagy, 2018). This suggests that confidence alone may not provide meaningful protection against advanced attacks and may instead contribute to vulnerability if not supported by structured awareness of modern threat techniques. Overall, the findings indicate the need for a targeted education that focuses not only on recognising fraud, but on understanding how evolving technologies can alter its presentation and detection.

4.3.4 SECTION 4: PERCEPTION OF RISK AND TRUST

4.3.4.1 PERCEIVED RISK OF AI IMPERSONATION

How likely do you think it is that AI could be used to impersonate someone you know over the phone?
151 responses

Figure 12 - Likelihood of AI Impersonation

Most respondents perceive AI impersonation as likely, reflecting growing awareness of AI misuse. This aligns with broader cybersecurity discourse, which highlights increasing concern over the misuse of generative AI in social engineering attacks (ENISA, 2023).

Despite the high level of perceived risk, this awareness does not necessarily translate into effective behavioural change. Research in cybersecurity consistently demonstrates that individuals may acknowledge the likelihood of a threat while still failing to adopt appropriate protective measures in practice (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). This phenomenon is particularly relevant in the context of social engineering, where real time decision machining is influenced by factors such as urgency, emotion and perceived familiarity. In the case of Ai-enabled impersonation, even individuals who recognise the risk may still respond to a convincing request if it appears to come from a trusted source. This suggests that risk perception alone is sufficient as a defensive mechanism and must be complemented by practical strategies such as verification behaviours and awareness of how such attacks are executed. Consequently, while the findings indicate a strong recognition of potential threat, they also highlight an ongoing vulnerability in translating awareness into action.

4.3.4.2 TRUST IN FAMILIAR VOICES

If you received a call from a familiar voice (e.g. friend, boss, family) would you trust it without verification?
151 responses

Figure 13 - Trust in Familiar Voice

Trust is a well-established vulnerability in social engineering, where attackers exploit familiarity, authority and urgency to manipulate behaviour (Hadnagy, 2018). The introduction of deepfake voice technology significantly enhances the risk by increasing the realism of impersonation.

The predominance of the “depends on the situation” response (63.6%) is particularly significant, as it indicates that trust decisions are highly context dependent rather than consistently cautious. While this may suggest a degree of critical

thinking, it also introduces variability in decision machining that can be exploited by attackers. Social engineering attacks are specifically designed to manipulate context, often incorporating urgency, emotional appeal, or authority to influence behaviour in real time (Hadnagy, 2018). In scenarios where individuals are placed under pressure or presented with convincing narratives, the likelihood of verification may decrease, even among those who would otherwise act cautiously. When combined with AI-generated voice impersonation, which enhances the realism and familiarity of communication, this situational trust becomes a critical vulnerability. Overall, the findings suggest that conditional trust does not necessarily equate to secure behaviour but may instead represent a key point of exploitation in deepfake enabled vishing attacks.

4.3.4.3 CONCERN ABOUT AI SCAMS

Figure 14 - Concern About AI Scams

High levels of concern were observed among respondents, indicating recognition of the threat. However, research suggests that awareness and concern alone are insufficient to prevent victimisation, as behavioural responses are often influenced by situational actors such as urgency and emotional pressure (ENISA, 2023)

While the level of concern indicates that respondents recognise the seriousness of AI enabled scams, it does not necessarily translate into effective preventative behaviour. Research suggests that emotional responses such as concern or fear can increase awareness of a threat but do not always result in sustained behavioural change, particularly in fast paced or high-pressure situations (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023) in the context of vishing, attackers often exploit urgency and emotional manipulation, which can override rational decision-making processes. As result even individuals who express strong concern about AI-driven scams may still be susceptible when confronted with a realistic and time-sensitive scenario. This highlights an important limitation of awareness-based approaches, suggesting that concern alone is insufficient as a protective factor and must be supported by practical knowledge and consistent verification behaviours.

4.3.5 SECTION 5: BEHAVIOURAL RESPONSE (VOICE SCAM SCENARIO)

imagine you receive a call from someone who sounds exactly like your manager or a family member, urgently asking for money or sensitive information. What would you do?
151 responses

Figure 15 - Response to Voice Scam Scenario

Most respondents indicated appropriate verification behaviours. However, a minority demonstrated vulnerability. This reflects findings in cybersecurity research, where even well-informed individuals may fall victim to attacks under specific conditions (Hadnagy, 2018). Attackers often rely on exploiting psychological triggers rather than technological weaknesses.

Although most respondents selected appropriate verification behaviours, the presence of even a small proportion willing to comply immediately (5.3%) or expressing uncertainty (8.6%) is significant when considered in the context of real-world cybercrime. Attackers typically rely on outcomes, meaning that even low percentages can translate into substantial impact at scale (Federal Bureau of Investigation, 2023). As well as this, the effectiveness of these responses may be influenced by situational factors not fully captured in a survey environment, such as stress, urgency or emotional manipulation. In real world phishing scenarios, where deepfake voice convincingly mimics a trusted individual and introduces time pressure, individuals who intend to verify identity may still act impulsively. This suggests that while stated behavioural intentions appear strong, actual responses may differ under realistic conditions, highlighting an ongoing vulnerability in the face of increasingly sophisticated, AI driven social engineering attacks.

4.3.6 SECTION 6: CYBERSECURITY TRAINING

4.3.6.1 RESPONDENTS EXPOSURE TO CYBERSECURITY TRAINING

Have you ever received any training or education on cybersecurity or online safety?
151 responses

Figure 16 - Respondents' Exposure to Cybersecurity Training

As showcased in figure 16, most respondents (78.8%) reported that they had received some form of cybersecurity training or education, while 21.2% indicated no prior exposure. This suggests that a significant proportion of participants have encountered cybersecurity concepts, either through formal education, workplace training or public awareness initiatives.

However, exposure to training does not necessarily equate to effective understanding or behavioural change. Research indicates that many cybersecurity awareness programmes focus on general threats and may not adequately address emerging risks such as AI-generated deception or deepfake-enabled attacks (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). As a result, individuals may possess foundational knowledge but still lack the ability to recognise more sophisticated or evolving attack methods, particularly involving voice impersonation.

Figure 17 - Perceived Need for Greater Public Awareness of AI-Related Scams

Figure 17 demonstrates a strong consensus among respondents, with approximately 94% indicating that more public awareness is needed regarding AI-driven scams, while only a very small proportion disagreed or were unsure. This highlights a widespread recognition that current levels of cybersecurity education are insufficient in addressing emerging threats.

This finding aligns with broader industry observations, which suggest that cybersecurity awareness reports often fall behind technological advancements, particularly in relation to artificial intelligence and social engineering techniques (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). The rapid development of AI tools, including deepfake voice synthesis, has introduced new forms of deception that are not yet widely covered in traditional awareness campaigns.

Furthermore, the perceived need for increased education reflects an important insight: individuals are not only aware of the risks but also recognises their own limitations in understanding and responding to them. This reinforces the argument that cybersecurity strategies must evolve to incorporate emerging technologies and focus more on behavioural awareness and real-world scenarios.

4.3.7 SECTION 7: OPTIONAL QUESTIONS (QUALITATIVE INSIGHTS)

4.3.7.1 ADDITIONAL THOUGHTS AND CONCERNS ABOUT AI AND SCAMS

This section presents qualitative responses to the open-ended question: **Any additional thoughts or concerns about AI and scams?**

All responses were collected anonymously in accordance with ethical research principles, ensuring participant confidentiality and encouraging candid, unbiased input. The responses provide deeper insight into public perceptions, revealing recurring concerns surrounding the rapid advancement of AI, gaps in public awareness, emotional vulnerability and the perceived need for stronger institutional intervention. These qualitative findings compliment the quantitative results by providing context to observed trends, particularly the gap between awareness and preparedness identified earlier sections.

A prominent theme across responses is the perceived imbalance between the pace of technological development and the level of public understanding. One respondent stated:

“One of the main concerns is how quickly AI technology is advancing compared to public awareness and understanding...”

This reflects a broader concern that technological capability is progressing faster than societal adaption. This perception aligns with existing research, which suggests that advancements in artificial intelligence often outpace both regulatory frameworks and public awareness, creating a “knowledge lag” that can be exploited by malicious actors (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). The respondent’s reference to accountability further highlights a key issue in AI governance: the difficulty in identifying and attributing malicious use of AI-generated content. In the context of vishing, this is particularly significant, as deepfake voice technologies can be deployed anonymously and at scale, reducing the likelihood of detection and increasing the potential impact of attacks.

Closely related to this is the expectation that responsibility for managing these risks should extend beyond individuals. As one respondent noted:

“The greater AI technology increases, the greater the risks to all unless tech companies find ways to protect and inform us...”

This response highlights a perceived dependency on institutional actors, including technology companies and governments, to implement safeguards and provide clear guidance. The call for improved detection tools and regulatory oversight reflects current debates within cybersecurity and AI governance, where there is increasing emphasis on the role of organisations in mitigating risk (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). Importantly, this perspective suggests that respondents do not view cybersecurity solely as an individual responsibility, but rather as a collective issue requiring coordinated intervention. This aligns with the broader shift towards shared responsibility models in cybersecurity, particularly in relation to emerging technologies.

Emotional manipulation emerged as a significant concern, particularly in relation to the effectiveness of scams involving urgency and personal relationships. One respondent stated:

“Much more awareness is needed... scams that generate a situation where a person thinks a loved one may be in danger is going to be successful...”

This highlights the psychological dimension of vishing attacks, where attackers exploit emotional triggers such as fear, urgency and concern for others. Social engineering literature consistently identifies emotional manipulation as a key factor in successful attacks, as it can override rational decision-making processes (Hadnagy, 2018). The relevance of this finding is amplified in the context of AI-generated voice impersonation, where attackers can replicate the voice of a trusted individual, thereby reinforcing the emotional credibility of the scenario. This significantly increases the likelihood of compliance, even among individuals who are otherwise aware of such threats.

Another important theme identified is the coexistence of overconfidence and limited understanding. One respondent observed:

“There is a worrying crossover between people who are convinced they would never be caught out, and people who don’t understand quite what technology can do...”

This observation directly supports earlier quantitative findings, particularly those relating to confidence in identifying fraudulent calls. The combination of overconfidence and insufficient knowledge represents a critical vulnerability, as individual may underestimate their susceptibility to deception. Research suggests that overconfidence can reduce the likelihood of engaging in verification behaviours, particularly in situation that appear familiar or credible (Hadnagy, 2018). In the context of deepfake enabled vishing, this is especially problematic, as the realism of AI-generated voices may reinforce a false sense of security.

Some respondents also demonstrated proactive attempts to mitigate risk through personal strategies. For example:

“My family have a password that is changed regularly... to verify identity”

This reflects the implementation of informal security practices, specifically the use of shared verification mechanisms to confirm identity. Such strategies align with recommended defensive approaches in combating impersonation-based attacks, particularly those involving voice communication. However, the respondent’s uncertainty regarding the effectiveness of this approach highlights a broader issue: while individuals may attempt to adopt protective behaviours, there is often a lack of clear, standardised guidance on best practices. This reinforces the need for more accessible and actionable cybersecurity education.

Concerns for vulnerable populations, particularly older individuals, were also evident:

“I have elderly parents... I still fear they’ll get caught out.”

This reflects widely recognised trends within cybersecurity research, where certain demographic groups may be disproportionately targeted due to differences in digital literacy, experience and reliance on trust-based communication (Ofcom, 2022). The concern expressed by respondents suggests an awareness of these vulnerabilities but also highlights a lack of confidence in current protective measures. This reinforces the importance of targeted awareness campaigns and support mechanisms for at-risk groups.

Finally, broader societal concerns were expressed regarding the ability of existing systems to manage emerging threats

“Society is struggling to deal with unsophisticated scams. AI scams will be a huge challenge...”

This statement reflects a perception that current fraud prevention mechanisms are already insufficient, raising concerns about their ability to adapt to more advanced, AI-driven threats. The reference to financial institutions and telecommunications providers suggests an expectation for sector specific accountability in addressing these risks. This aligns with current industry discussions, which emphasises the need for cross-sector collaboration in combatting cybercrime, particularly as attack methods become more technologically sophisticated.

4.3.7.2 IMPROVING IDENTIFICATION OF AI-ENABLED SCAMS

This section presents qualitative responses to the open-ended question: **What do you think would help people better identify scams involving AI or deepfake technology?**

All responses were collected anonymously in accordance with ethical research principles, ensuring participant confidentiality and encouraging candid, unbiased input. The responses provide valuable insight into public perceptions of effective mitigation strategies, highlighting key themes including the need for increased awareness, technological solutions, regulatory intervention and practical verification behaviours.

A dominant theme across Responses is the need for clearer identification and labelling of AI-generated content. One respondent stated:

“There should be a legal requirement... indicating that the material has been generated via Ai”

This reflects growing public support for transparency measures in AI-generated media. The suggestion of mandatory labelling aligns with ongoing policy discussions surrounding digital watermarking and disclosure requirements for synthetic content. Such measures aim to reduce deception by providing users with clear indicators of authenticity. However, research suggests that while labelling may improve awareness, it may not be sufficient in isolation, particularly if users fail to notice or understand these indicators (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023). In the context of phishing, this challenge is further amplified, as audio-based interactions lack visible cues, making real time detection more difficult.

Another key theme is the importance of education and awareness. As one respondent noted:

“Being given some key factors to look out for... when they’re faced with potential scam”

This showcases a demand for more practical, actionable guidance rather than general awareness messaging. Respondents emphasised the need for clear indicators and real-world examples to support understanding. This aligns with cybersecurity research, which suggests that awareness programmes are most effective when they focus on behavioural guidance and realistic scenarios rather than abstract concepts (ENISA, 2023). In the context of AI-driven scams, this is particularly important, as traditional indicators of fraud are becoming less reliable.

The integration of technological solutions alongside education was also emphasised. One Respondent stated:

“Better built-in tech to combat and alert us plus education with realistic examples...”

This reflects an understanding that effective defence requires a combination of human and technological approaches. The suggestion of built in detection tools aligns with current developments in AI-based fraud detection systems, which aim to identify and flag suspicious activity in real time. However, reliance on technological solutions alone may introduce risks, including overdependence on automated systems and reduced user vigilance. This reinforces the need for a balanced approach that combines technical safeguards with user awareness.

A particularly detailed response highlighted the importance of combining multiple defensive strategies

“A combination of education and practical safeguards... encouraging people to verify unusual requests through a second method...”

This response demonstrates a strong understanding of effective cybersecurity practices, particularly the concept of multi-channel verification. Verifying requests through independent communication channels is widely recognised as a key defence against impersonation attacks, including vishing. The mention of clear indicators and improved detection tools further reinforces the need for both user-level and system level interventions. This aligns closely with best practice recommendations in cybersecurity which emphasises layered defence strategies.

Some responses also highlighted the potential role of AI in mitigating AI-driven threats:

“Awareness being shared or probably other AI identifying it”

This reflects an emerging perspective that AI can be used defensively to detect synthetic content and flag potential scams. This aligns with current research into AI based detection systems, which aims to identify anomalies in voice, behaviour or communication patterns. However, this also introduces a technological “arms race” dynamic, where attackers and defenders continuously adapt their methods, potentially limiting the long-term effectiveness of purely technical solutions.

Practical verification behaviours were also emphasised by respondents for example:

“make sure that the phone number is the same... ask a question that only they would know”

This showcases awareness of identity verification techniques, particularly in scenarios involving impersonation. The use of shared knowledge or pre-agreed verification questions is a recognised strategy in mitigating vishing attacks. However, the effectiveness of such methods may be influenced by situational factors, including urgency and emotional pressure, which can reduce the likelihood of verification being applied in practice (Hadnagy, 2018)

Regulation and institutional responsibility were also strongly emphasised. One respondent stated:

“The Government should implement more comprehensive programs... any piece of media generated with AI should... have a disclaimer...”

This reflects a clear expectation for regulatory intervention in addressing AI-related risks. The emphasis on government led awareness programmes and mandatory disclosure highlights concerns regarding the current lack of standardisation in AI governance. This aligns with broader policy discussion, which emphasises the need for regulatory frameworks to ensure transparency, accountability and user protection

Similarly, another respondent highlighted the role of organisations and service providers:

“There should be stricter regulations... phone companies should block users... use AI... to flag and warn users...”

This response reflects a demand for proactive intervention from private sector organisations, particularly telecommunications providers and technology platforms. The expectation that companies should actively detect and prevent scams aligns with industry trends towards integrated fraud prevention systems. However, the acknowledgment that scams are difficult to fully eliminate highlights the limitations of such approaches and reinforces the importance of user awareness.

4.3.7.3 PERCEPTIONS OF AI IN EVERYDAY COMMUNICATION

This section presents qualitative responses to the open-ended question: **How do you feel about the use of AI in everyday communication (e.g. voice assistants, chatbots etc.)?**

All responses were collected anonymously in accordance with ethical research principles, ensuring participant confidentiality and encouraging candid, unbiased input. The responses reveal a range of perspectives, highlighting both the perceived benefits of AI in communication and concerns regarding overreliance, privacy, transparency and the erosion of human interaction. These findings provide important context for understanding how individuals may engage with AI technologies in everyday scenarios, which is directly relevant to the effectiveness of AI-enabled social engineering attacks.

A prominent theme within responses is the recognition of AI as a useful and efficient tool when applied appropriately. One respondent:

“I think AI in everyday communication can be really useful when its used properly, especially for convenience and accessibility...”

This reflects a generally positive perception of AI as a tool for enhancing efficiency and accessibility. The reference to supporting individuals with communication challenges highlights the inclusive potential of AI technologies. However, the respondent also acknowledges the need for responsible and transparent use, particularly in ensuring that users are aware when they are interacting with AI. This concern is highly relevant in the context of phishing, where the ability to distinguish between human and AI-generated communication is critical for identifying deception.

Similarly, another respondent emphasised the productivity benefits of AI:

“Very helpful, makes my job a lot quicker... will produce spreadsheets and reports for me in minutes”

This highlights the growing integration of AI into professional environments, where it is valued for its ability to automate tasks and improve efficiency. While this normalisation of AI use may increase familiarity and acceptance, it may also contribute to reduced scrutiny of AI-generated outputs. As individuals become more accustomed to interacting with AI systems, they may be less likely to question the authenticity of AI-generated Communication, potentially increasing vulnerability.

However, several responses reflect a more conflicted perspective, recognising both benefits and risks. One respondent stated:

“I am conflicted... I do worry about how over usage can decrease critical thinking”

This showcase concerns regarding overreliance on AI and its potential impact on cognitive processes such as critical thinking and decision making. This is particularly relevant in cybersecurity contexts, where the ability to critically evaluate information is essential for detecting scams. Overdependence on AI systems may reduce individuals' engagement with information, potentially increasing susceptibility to deception, particularly when AI-generated content appears credible.

Privacy and surveillance concerns were also strongly represented. One respondent noted:

“Dislike it... not a fan of something always listening... personal information is being stored...”

This reflects a broader concern regarding data privacy and the collection of personal information by AI systems. Such concerns align with ongoing debates around data protection and the ethical use of AI. Importantly, a lack of understanding regarding how AI systems operate, as highlighted in the response, may contribute to both mistrust and misuse. In the context of vishing, concerns around data collection are particularly relevant as attackers may exploit publicly available or leaked data to enhance the realism of impersonation attempts.

Another key theme identified is the importance of transparency and clear distinction between human and AI interaction. One respondent stated:

“There should be a clear difference between human and AI... it would be uncomfortable... if it sounded like a real person”

This response directly showcases one of the central risks associated with deepfake voice technology: the blurring of boundaries between human and artificial communication. The concern regarding realistic AI voices aligns closely with the core focus of this research, as vishing attacks rely heavily on the ability to convincingly imitate trusted individuals. The emphasis on labelling and transparency reflects broader calls for disclosure mechanisms to ensure users are aware when interacting with AI-generated content.

4.3.7.4 PERCEIVED RISKS OF AI VOICE IMITATION

This section presents qualitative responses to open-ended question: **in your opinion, what is the biggest risk associated with AI being able to imitate human voices?**

All responses were collected anonymously in accordance with ethical research principles, ensuring participant confidentiality and encouraging candid, unbiased input. The responses provide critical insight into public perceptions of risk associated with AI-generated voice technology, with recurring themes including fraud and impersonation, erosion of trust, technological obsolescence and broader societal implications. These findings directly support the central focus of this research, showcasing the perceived dangers of deepfake-enabled vishing.

An important theme across responses is the potential for fraud and impersonation. One respondent stated:

“The biggest risk is the potential for fraud and impersonation... it becomes much easier for attackers to trick individuals into believing they are speaking to a trusted person...”

This reflects a clear understanding how AI technology can be weaponised within social engineering attacks. The ability to convincingly mimic a trusted individual significantly lowers the barriers to successful deception, particularly in vishing scenarios where voice communication is the primary medium. This aligns with existing research, which identifies impersonation as a key tactic in phishing related cybercrime (Federal Bureau of Investigation, 2023). The respondent’s reference to trust further emphasises the central role of familiarity in facilitating successful attacks.

Closely linked to this is the concern regarding the erosion of trust in communication systems. One respondent noted:

“you’d never be able to trust a phone call... imagine receiving a call from your mother and not knowing if it was real?”

This demonstrates a broader societal implication of AI voice imitation: the potential breakdown of trust in everyday communications. Trust is a fundamental component of human interaction, particularly in voice-based communication where tone and familiarity play a significant role. The introduction of highly realistic deepfake voices challenges this trust, creating uncertainty and hesitation in situations that would traditionally be considered reliable. This has implications beyond cybersecurity, potentially affecting personal relationships and communication norms.

Another key concern identified is the impact on existing security mechanisms. One respondent stated:

“Voice recognition security quickly becomes obsolete...”

This reflects an awareness of the limitations of current authentication systems in the face of advancing AI technologies. Voice biometrics have been widely used as a security measure; however, the development of realistic voice synthesis raises significant concerns regarding their reliability. This highlights a critical issue in cybersecurity, the need for continuous adaptation of security systems in response to emerging threats. As AI capabilities evolve, previously effective security measures may become increasingly vulnerable to exploitation.

Concerns regarding realism and indistinguishability were also evident. One respondent noted|:

“AI may reach a point where it can create content indistinguishable from reality...”

This reflects a broader fear surrounding the increasing sophistication of AI generated content. The potential for AI to produce highly realistic voice recordings raises significant challenges for detection and verification. In the context of vishing, this particularly concerning, as individuals may be unable to rely on traditional cues to identify deception. This aligns with research suggesting that the effectiveness of deepfake technologies lies in their ability to closely replicate human characteristics, thereby reducing detectability (Mirsky and Lee, 2021).

4.3.8 SYNTHESIS OF QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

The qualitative findings across sections 4.3.7.1 to 4.3.7.4 provide a comprehensive understanding of public perceptions regarding AI, deepfakes and vishing-related risks. While individual responses varied in focus, several consistent themes emerged, highlighting key concerns, behavioural patterns and expectations for mitigation. These findings complement the quantitative results by offering deeper insight into the reasoning behind participant attitudes and behaviours.

4.3.8.1 SUMMARY OF KEY QUALITATIVE THEMES

Theme	Description	Example Insight from Responses	Relevance to Research
<i>Rapid Technological Advancement</i>	Concern that AI is evolving faster than public understanding	“AI is advancing faster than awareness...”	Highlights knowledge gap increasing vulnerability
<i>Awareness vs Understanding Gap</i>	Recognition that people lack practical understanding despite awareness	“People don’t understand what the technology can do...”	Supports earlier findings on superficial awareness
<i>Fraud and Impersonation Risk</i>	AI voice seen as enabling more convincing scams	“Easier to trick individuals into believing...”	Directly supports vishing threat focus
<i>Emotional Manipulation</i>	Scenarios involving urgency/family increase success	“Loved one in danger...will be successful”	Links to social engineering tactics
<i>Overconfidence and Behavioural Risk</i>	People believe they won’t be victims	“People think they won’t be caught out...”	Reinforces confidence vs capability gap
<i>Trust Exploitation</i>	Familiar voices increase likelihood	“Trust in voices becomes a weakness...”	Core mechanism of vishing attacks
<i>Erosion of Trust</i>	Fear that communication becomes unreliable	“you’d never trust a phone call”	Broader social impact
<i>Need for Education</i>	Demand for clearer guidance and awareness	“More awareness is needed...”	Supports need for behavioural intervention
<i>Technological Solutions</i>	Expectation of AI detection tools	“AI identifying AI...”	Reflects defensive tech reliance

<i>Regulatory Responsibility</i>	Calls for government and company action	“There should be legal requirements...”	Highlights governance expectations
<i>Practical Safeguards</i>	Use of verification (methods (passwords, callbacks)	“Verify through another method...”	Shows real-world defensive behaviour
<i>Vulnerable Populations</i>	Concern for elderly and less tech aware users	“Elderly more likely to be caught out...”	Supports targeted risk groups

Table 5 - Summary of Qualitative Findings (Questionnaire)

4.3.8.2 INTEGRATED ANALYSIS OF QUALITATIVE FINDINGS

The qualitative findings reveal a strong alignment with the quantitative data, particularly in highlighting the gap between awareness, understanding and behaviour. While respondents generally demonstrated awareness of AI technologies and their potential misuse, many expressed concern regarding their own or other’s ability to effectively identify and respond to such threats. This reinforces earlier findings that awareness alone is insufficient as a protective factor.

A key insight emerging from the data is the continued importance of human factors in cybersecurity. Themes such as emotional manipulation, trust and overconfidence indicate that attackers are likely to exploit psychological vulnerabilities rather than purely technical weaknesses. This is particularly relevant in the context of AI-enabled vishing, where deepfake voice technology enhances the realism of attacks, making them more difficult to detect through traditional cues.

As well as this, respondents demonstrated a clear understanding that addressing these risks requires a multi-layered approach, combining education, technological solutions and regulatory intervention. However, there is also evidence of uncertainty regarding the effectiveness of current strategies, particularly in relation to detection and prevention. The expectation that organisations and governments should play a greater role suggests a perceived limitation in individual capacity to manage these risks independently.

Importantly, the findings also highlight a broader societal concern, the potential erosion of trust in communication systems. As AI generated voices become more realistic, individuals may begin to question the authenticity of everyday interactions, which has implications beyond cybersecurity and into social and organisational contexts.

Overall, the qualitative analysis reinforces the central argument of this research, that AI technologies particularly deepfake voice systems, significantly amplify existing social engineering threats rather than creating deepfake voice systems, significantly amplify existing social engineering threats rather than creating entirely new ones. By enhancing realism, scalability and accessibility, these technologies increase both the effectiveness of attacks and the difficulty of detection. Overall, mitigating these risks requires not only technological innovation but also a stronger emphasis on behavioural awareness, critical thinking and institutional responsibility.

4.4 CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: AI VOICE DEEPFAKE IN FINANCIAL FRAUD

4.4.1 CASE STUDY OVERVIEW: CEO VOICE DEEPFAKE FRAUD

This section examines a real-world example of AI generated voice technology being used in a financial vishing attack. The case, widely reported by BBC News, The Guardian as well as Forbes, involved criminals successfully impersonating a company executive using deepfake voice technology to authorise a fraudulent financial transaction.

In 2019, a UK-based energy firm was targeted in a sophisticated vishing attack in which attackers used artificial intelligence to replicate the voice of the company’s parent organisation’s CEO. The generated voice closely mimicked the individual’s tone, accent and speech patterns, enabling the victim, a senior executive with the organisation, was instructed to urgently transfer approximately €220,000 (£200,000+) to a supplier account. Believing the request to be legitimate, the employee complied with the instruction, resulting in a successful financial loss (BBC News, 2019; The Guardian, 2019; Forbes, 2019).

4.4.2 ATTACK METHOD AND USE OF AI TECHNOLOGY

This case represents a clear evolution of traditional vishing attacks through the integration of AI driven voice synthesis. Unlike conventional phishing techniques, which often rely on text-based deception, this attack utilised audio deepfake technology to enhance credibility and bypass suspicion.

The success of the attack can be attributed to several key elements. Firstly, the use of AI generated voice cloning allowed the attackers to replicate not only the identity of the CEO but also the emotional tone and linguistic characteristics associated with their speech. This level of realism significantly reduces the effectiveness of traditional detection cues, such as unusual phrasing or vocal inconsistencies, which individuals often rely on to identify fraudulent communication (Mirsky and Lee, 2021).

Secondly, the attackers incorporated elements of social engineering, including urgency and authority, to influence the victim's decision making. The request for immediate action created a sense of pressure, reducing the likelihood of verification. As identified in earlier sections of this research, such tactics are highly effective in manipulating behaviour, particularly when combined with familiar or trusted identities (Hadnagy, 2018).

Finally, the attack showcases the increasing accessibility of AI technologies. The ability to generate realistic voice impersonations without direct interaction with the victim highlights the scalability of such attacks, raising concerns regarding their potential widespread use in financial fraud.

4.4.3 ANALYSIS AND LINK TO RESEARCH FINDINGS

The examined case study provides a clear and practical demonstration of how AI-generated voice technology can be exploited within financial vishing attacks. The incident highlights the increasing sophistication of social engineering techniques, where traditional psychological manipulation is enhanced using advanced technological tools.

A key factor contributing to the success of the attack is the exploitation of authority and organisational hierarchy. The impersonation of a senior executive created a strong perception of legitimacy, reducing the likelihood that the request would be questioned. This reflects established social engineering principles, where individuals are more likely to comply with instructions perceived to originate from an authoritative figure (Hadnagy, 2018). The inclusion of realistic vocal characteristics, such as accent and tone further reinforced this perceived legitimacy, demonstrating the effectiveness of AI in replicating trusted identities.

The case also showcases the role of urgency as a behavioural trigger. The request for immediate financial transfer limited the opportunity for the victim to engage in verification procedures. This aligns with patterns observed in the questionnaire findings, where respondents indicated that emotionally or time pressured scenarios increase susceptibility to fraud. The combination of urgency and authority represents a common tactic in vishing attacks, amplified in this instance with AI generated voice impersonation.

From a technical perspective, the case demonstrates how AI voice synthesis reduces reliance on traditional indicators of deception. In conventional phishing scenarios, inconsistencies in language, tone, communication style may raise suspicion. However, the ability of AI to produce highly realistic speech patterns diminishes these cues, increasing the difficulty of detection. This supports the concerns identified in the qualitative findings, where respondents highlighted the potential for AI-generated voices to become indistinguishable from genuine communication.

The case further reveals a lack of robust verification mechanisms within organisational processes. The absence of secondary authentication measures such as callback procedures or multi-channel verification enabled the fraudulent request to be executed without challenge. This reflects a broader vulnerability in organisational security practices, where reliance on trust-based communication may override formal verification processes and protocols.

As well as this the rapid movement of funds following the transaction demonstrates the operational efficiency of such attacks, highlighting the difficulty of post-incident recovery. This emphasises the importance of preventative measures, as once a transaction is completed, the likelihood of recovering funds is significantly reduced.

Overall, the case study provides empirical evidence that AI generated voice technology acts as a force multiple for existing social engineering techniques, rather than introducing entirely new methods of attack. By enhancing realism, credibility and speed, AI enables attackers to exploit established psychological vulnerabilities more effectively, increasing both the success rate and potential impact of vishing attacks.

4.4.4 KEY FINDINGS FROM CASE STUDY

<i>Finding</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Evidence from Case Study</i>	<i>Relevance to Research</i>
<i>Voice-Based Trust Exploitation</i>	Attackers leverage familiarity and authority to increase compliance	CEO voice successfully impersonated	Supports findings on trust as a key vulnerability
<i>Amplification of Social Engineering</i>	AI enhances traditional tactics such as urgency and authority	Urgent financial request issued by “CEO”	Demonstrates AI as a force multiplier
<i>Lack of Verification Controls</i>	Absence of secondary checks enables attack success	No callback or authentication used	Highlights organisational vulnerability
<i>Increased Realism of Attacks</i>	AI-generated voice reduces detection cues	Accent, tone and speech replicated	Supports concerns about indistinguishability
<i>Behavioural manipulation</i>	Victim influenced by urgency and hierarchy	Immediate transfer requested	Reinforces role of psychological triggers
<i>Speed of Financial Exploitation</i>	Rapid transfer and movement of funds limits recovery	Funds quickly moved across accounts	Emphasises importance of prevention over response

Table 6 - Summary of Key Case Study Findings

4.4.5 ANALYTICAL SUMMARY OF CASE STUDY

The findings presented in Table 6 showcase the convergence of technological capability and psychological manipulation within AI enabled vishing attacks. A central observation is the continued reliance on trust as a primary attack vector, with the success of the incident largely dependent on the perceived authenticity of the caller. The use of AI-generated voice technology significantly enhanced this perception, reinforcing the role of familiarity and authority in influencing decision making.

The case further highlights that AI functions as an enabler of existing social engineering techniques, rather than introducing entirely new methods. Traditional tactics, including urgency and hierarchical pressure, were clear within the attack. However, the addition of realistic voice impersonation increased their effectiveness by reducing suspicion and limiting the likelihood of challenge.

A critical vulnerability identified is the absence of robust verification mechanisms. The lack of secondary authentication processes allowed the fraudulent request to be executed without resistance, indicating that organisational reliance on trust-based communication may override security protocols. This observation aligns with earlier findings in this research, where verification behaviours were identified as inconsistent despite awareness of potential threats.

As well as this, the case highlights the growing challenge of detecting AI generated content. The ability to replicate vocal characteristics such as tone, accent and speech patterns reduces the effectiveness of traditional detection cues, making it increasingly difficult for individual to distinguish between legitimate and fraudulent communication.

Finally, the speed at which the fraudulent transaction was completed and the funds redistributed showcases the efficiency of modern financial cybercrime. This reinforces the importance of preventative measures, as reactive responses are often limited in their ability to recover losses once an attack has been successfully executed.

4.4.6 CONCLUSION OF CASE STUDY

In conclusion, the analysed case study provides clear empirical evidence of the practical application of AI generated voice technology in financial phishing attacks. The incident demonstrates how deepfake technology enhances the effectiveness of social engineering of social engineering by increasing realism, credibility and the speed of execution.

The findings reinforce the central theme of this research, highlighting that AI does not fundamentally change the nature of cybercrime, but significantly amplifies the existing attack methods. The combination of technological advancement and human behavioural vulnerability creates a highly effective threat landscape, particularly within organisational and financial contexts.

This case therefore serves as a critical foundation for the subsequent discussion, where these findings will be examined in relation to broader trends, public awareness and potential mitigation strategies.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION, AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

5.1 OVERVIEW OF KEY FINDINGS

This chapter presents a critical discussion of the findings derived from the quantitative datasets, questionnaire responses and case study analysis. The purpose of this section is to synthesise these results and examine their implication in relation to the research objectives with particular focus on the role of AI-generated deepfakes in enabling vishing attacks.

The findings of this research indicate that AI enabled vishing represents an increasingly significant cybersecurity threat, driven by the alignment of technological advancement and human behavioural vulnerability. Analysis of secondary datasets, including those from UK and US sources demonstrates a continued upward trend in fraud related losses. While it is not possible to attribute this increase solely to emergence of AI technologies, the timing of these trends aligns with the rapid development and accessibility of generative AI tools, suggesting a potential relationship between technological evolution and the sophistication of fraud techniques.

The questionnaire findings further reinforce this perspective, highlighting a gap between awareness and practical preparedness. While participants generally demonstrated an understanding of AI and its potential misuse, there was evidence of inconsistency in behavioural response, particularly in relation to verification practices. This suggests that awareness alone is insufficient in mitigating risk, as individuals may still be susceptible to manipulation under realistic or high-pressure conditions.

Qualitative responses provided additional depth, revealing concerns surrounding trust, emotional manipulation and the realism of AI generated communication. Participants frequently identified the potential for AI to exploit familiar relationships and authority figures, which aligns closely with established social engineering principles. These concerns were further validated through the case study analysis, which demonstrated how AI generated voice technology can be successfully used to impersonate trusted individuals and facilitate financial fraud.

Across all data sources, a consistent theme emerges, AI technologies do not fundamentally alter the nature of social engineering attacks but significantly enhance their effectiveness. By increasing realism, reducing detectability and enabling scalable deployment, AI acts as a force multiplier for existing cybercrime methods.

Overall, the findings suggest that the risk associated with deepfake enabled vishing extends beyond individual users to organisations and broader social systems, where trust-based communication remains integral to daily operations. These implications form the basis for further critical evaluation in the following sections.

5.2 INTEGRATION WITH LITERATURE

This section critically evaluates the findings of this research in relation to the existing academic and industry literature. By comparing the results obtained from quantitative datasets, questionnaire response and case study analysis with established research, this section aims to assess the extent to which the findings align with, extend and or challenge current understanding of AI enabled vishing and social engineering threats.

5.2.1 ALIGNMENT WITH EXISTING RESEARCH ON SOCIAL ENGINEERING

The findings of this study strongly align with existing literature on social engineering, particularly in relation to the exploitation of human behavioural vulnerabilities. Research by Hadnagy (2018) identifies key psychological principles underlining social engineering attacks, including authority, urgency and trust. These principles were consistently observed across all data sources within this research.

The case study analysis demonstrated how authority and urgency were effectively leveraged in combination with AI generated voice impersonation, reinforcing the argument that technological advancements do not replace traditional attack methods but instead enhance them. As well as this, questionnaire responses highlighted concerns regarding emotional manipulation and trust exploitation, further supporting the relevance of established social engineering frameworks in understanding AI enabled threats.

These findings suggest that despite the introduction of advanced technologies, the fundamental drivers of successful cyber-attacks remain rooted in human psychology. This reinforces the continued importance of behavioural factors in cybersecurity as identified within existing literature.

5.2.2 AI AS A FORCE MULTIPLIER IN CYBERCRIME

A key finding of this research is that AI functions as a force multiplier, increasing the effectiveness, scalability and realism of existing attack methods. This aligns with research by Mirsky and Lee (2021), who highlight the potential for deepfake technologies to significantly enhance deception by replicating human characteristics with high accuracy.

The ability of AI generate realistic voice impersonations reduces reliance on traditional phishing indicators, making detection more challenging. This was reflected in both qualitative responses and case study findings where participants expressed concern regarding the indistinguishability of AI generated communication.

5.2.3 ALIGNMENT BETWEEN RESEARCH FINDINGS AND EXISTING LITERATURE

The table below summaries how the key findings of this study compare with existing academic and industry literature. It highlights areas of strong alignment, as well as the broader implications of these relations in the context of AI enabled vishing.

Research Finding	Supporting Literature	Level of Alignment	Detailed Interpretation and Implication
<i>Trust is a key vulnerability</i>	Hadnagy (2018)	Strong	The findings confirm that trust remains a central mechanism exploited in social engineering attacks. Both questionnaire responses and the case study demonstrate that individuals are more likely to comply with requests when communication appears to originate from a familiar or authoritative source. The introduction of AI-generated voice deepfakes strengthens this vulnerability by enhancing perceived authenticity, making traditional trust-based communications channels increasingly unreliable
<i>AI enhances realism and credibility of attacks</i>	Mirsky and Lee (2021)	Strong	The research strongly supports the argument that deepfake technologies significantly increase the realism of deceptive communication. Participants expressed concern regarding the indistinguishability of AI generated voices which was validated by the case study where vocal characteristics were convincingly replicated. This increased realism reduces the effectiveness of conventional detection methods and shifts the burden of detection onto more complex verification processes
<i>Awareness does not equate to behavioural protection</i>	ENISA (2023)	Moderate - Strong	While participants demonstrated awareness of AI related threats, inconsistencies in behavioural responses indicate that awareness alone is insufficient for effective risk mitigation. This aligns with existing research suggesting that individuals may recognise threats in theory but fail to act appropriately in practice, particularly in high pressure scenarios. This highlights the need for behavioural focused interventions rather than purely informational awareness campaigns.
<i>Emotional manipulation and urgency increase attack success</i>	Hadnagy (2018)	Strong	The findings reinforce the role of emotional triggers, such as urgency and fear, in influencing decision making. both qualitative responses and the case study illustrate how time pressure can reduce critical thinking and discourage verification behaviours. When combined with AI generated voice impersonation, these psychological tactics become more persuasive, increasing the likelihood of compliance even among individuals who are aware of potential risks.
<i>AI increases scalability and</i>	World Economic	Moderate	The research suggests that AI lowers the technical barrier required to execute sophisticated attacks therefore enabling wider deployment of vishing techniques. While this study does not directly measure

<i>accessibility of cyber attacks</i>	Forum (2024)	scalability, the accessibility of AI tools and the effectiveness demonstrated in the case study indicate significant potential for large scale exploitation. This raises concerns regarding the future volume and reach of AI enabled fraud.
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Table 7 - Alignment Between Research Findings and Existing Literature

5.3 IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

This section evaluates the broader implications of the research findings across different stakeholder groups, including individual users, organisations and governmental bodies. The aim is to assess how the individual risks associated with AI enabled vishing to extend beyond isolated incidents and impact wider societal, operational and regulatory contexts.

5.3.1 IMPLICATIONS FOR THE PUBLIC

The findings of this research indicate that individual users remain a critical point of vulnerability in AI enabled vishing attacks. While questionnaire results suggest a general awareness of AI related threats, there is a clear gap between awareness and effective behavioural response. This implies that individuals may overestimate their ability to identify fraudulent communication, particularly when exposed to realistic and emotionally persuasive scenarios.

The increased realism of AI generated voice impersonation presents a significant challenge for the public as traditional cues used to detect scams, such as unfamiliar tone or unnatural speech are becoming less reliable. As identified in both qualitative responses and the case study analysis, trust in familiar voices remains a key factor influencing decision making. this creates a heightened risk environment in which individuals may unknowingly engage with malicious actors under the assumption of legitimacy.

As well as this, the findings suggest that emotional manipulation continues to play a central role in successful attacks. Situations involving urgency or perceived personal relationships, such as family members or authority figures, can significantly reduce critical evaluation. This reinforces the need for individuals to adopt more structured verification behaviours as reliance on intuition alone is increasingly insufficient in the context of AI-enhanced deception.

5.3.2 IMPLICATIONS FOR ORGANISATIONS

The implications for organisations are particularly significant as demonstrated by both the case study and supporting data. The successful execution of the CEO voice deepfake attack highlights vulnerabilities within organisational communication structures, particularly where trust-based hierarchies are present.

A key implication is the potential inadequacy of existing verification processes. The absence of secondary authentication mechanisms such as callback procedures or multi-channel verification allows fraudulent requests to be executed without sufficient scrutiny. This suggests that organisations may need to reassess their internal controls, particularly in relation to financial transactions and sensitive communications

As well as this, the integration of AI technologies into cyber attacks increases the complexity of threat detection. Traditional security measures, which often focus on technical indicators, may be insufficient when attacks exploit human behaviour rather than system vulnerabilities. This highlights the importance of combining technical controls with behavioural awareness and training programmes.

The findings also suggest that organisational reliance on hierarchal communication structures may increase susceptibility to impersonation attacks. Employees may be less likely to question instructions received from senior figures, [particularly in high pressure situations. This creates an environment where authority can be exploited as a means of bypassing standard security procedures.

Importantly, these organisational vulnerabilities are reflected in the broader financial trends identified within the quantitative datasets. Analysis of UK and US fraud data indicates a sustained increase in financial losses over time. Suggesting that organisations are increasingly being targeted by sophisticated forms of cyber enabled fraud. While these

datasets do not isolate AI driven incidents specifically, the observed upward trend aligns with the growing accessibility and capability of AI technologies, as well as the increased realism demonstrated in the case study.

The convergence of these findings suggests that organisational exposure to fraud is not only persistent but evolving. The case study provides a practical example of how such attacks are executed. While the datasets demonstrate the wider financial impact at scale. When considered alongside questionnaire responses which highlight inconsistent verification behaviours and trust-based decision machining it becomes evident that organisations face a combined risk environment where technological advancement and human factors intersect

5.3.3 IMPLICATIONS FOR GOVERNMENT AND POLICY

At a broader level, the findings of this research highlight the increasing need for regulatory and policy intervention in addressing the risks associated with AI generated deepfakes and vishing attacks. The rapid advancement and accessibility of AI technologies present a significant challenge for existing regulatory frameworks, which often struggle to keep pace with emerging forms of cyber enabled fraud.

One key implication is the need for greater transparency and accountability in AI generated content. Qualitative responses from the questionnaire indicate that participants expect clearer identification of AI generated media, with suggestions including mandatory labelling or disclosure mechanisms. This aligns with ongoing policy discussions within cybersecurity literature, which emphasise the importance of traceability and content authentication in mitigating deception (European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, 2023)

As well as transparency, the findings highlight the importance of public awareness and education at a national level. While individual awareness was found to be relatively high, inconsistencies in behavioural responses suggest that existing awareness initiatives may lack practical effectiveness. This indicates a need for government led programmes that move beyond general information provision and instead focus on actionable guidance, such as verification behaviours and recognition of social engineering tactics.

The implications of these findings are further reinforced by the quantitative datasets analysed within this research which showcases a sustained increase in fraud related financial losses across both the UK and the United States. From policy perspective, this trend highlights a widening gap between the pace of technological innovation and the effectiveness of existing regulatory frameworks. While datasets do not explicitly distinguish AI driven incidents from broader fraud categories, the consistent upward trajectory suggests that current preventative and enforcement measures may not be adequately addressing emerging, technology enabled threats. This indicates a need for more adaptive and forward-looking regulatory approaches that can respond to the evolving nature of cyber enabled financial crime.

As well as this, the cross-boarder nature of AI enabled fraud presents additional challenges for regulation and enforcement. Attacks such as the analysed case study often involve multiple jurisdictions, with funds transferred rapidly across international accounts. This limits the effectiveness of traditional legal frameworks and highlights the need for enhanced international cooperation in cybercrime prevention and response.

Finally, the findings suggest a growing expectation that governments will play a more proactive role in coordinating responses across sectors, including financial institutions, technology providers and telecommunications services. While responsibility for cybersecurity is shared, the scale and complexity of AI-enabled threat indicate that individual and organisational measures alone may be insufficient without broader regulatory support.

5.4 NEED FOR MITIGATION AND TRANSITION TO FRAMEWORK

5.4.1 EVOLVING NATURE OF AI-ENABLED THREATS

The findings of this research indicate that AI-enabled vishing represent a significant evolution of traditional social engineering attacks, characterised by increased realism and reduced detectability. As stated by Hadnagy (2018) social engineering fundamentally relies on exploiting human behaviour, particularly trust, authority and urgency. This research supports that argument, demonstrating that while the underlying mechanisms of deception remain consistent, the

integration of AI technologies enhances their effectiveness. The ability to replicate human voices with high accuracy introduces a new dimension of credibility, making it increasingly difficult for individuals to rely on traditional cues when assessing the legitimacy of communication.

This progression is further supported by research from the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA, 2023), which argues that advancements in AI are outpacing both user awareness and existing security frameworks. The findings of this study align with this perspective, particularly in relation to the observed gap between awareness and behavioural response. While Questionnaire data indicates that individuals are aware of AI related threat, their ability to consistently apply verification behaviours remains limited. This suggests technological advancement is not being matched by equivalent improvements in user preparedness, increasing overall vulnerability.

However, it is important to recognise that the extent to which AI is directly responsible for the increase in fraud remains difficult to quantify. While the datasets analysed in this research demonstrate a clear upward trend in fraud related losses across the UK and United States (UK Finance, 2023; Federal Bureau of Investigation, 2023), they do not explicitly distinguish AI driven incidents as a separate category. As such, while there is a strong correlation between technological advancement and increased fraud sophistication, causation cannot be established. This limitation highlights the need for caution when attributing emerging threats solely to AI and reinforces the importance of continued empirical investigation in this area.

5.4.2 EVIDENCE OF SYSTEMIC VULNERABILITY

The case study analysed within this research provides clear empirical evidence of how AI generated voice technology can be exploited in real world scenarios. The successful impersonation of a senior executive demonstrates how authority and familiarity can be leveraged to bypass both individuals are more likely to comply with requests perceived to originate from trusted or authoritative sources. The findings of this research reinforce this principle, illustrating how AI enhances the credibility of such impersonation attempts.

As well as individual level vulnerabilities, the findings also highlight broader systemic issues within organisational and societal structures. The absence of robust verification processes as demonstrated in this case study, reflects a reliance on trust-based communication that is increasingly vulnerable to exploitation. This is further supported by questionnaire findings, where respondents indicated that verification behaviours are often situational rather than consistent. When considered alongside fraud datasets from the UK and US which indicate sustained increases in financial losses (UK Finance, 2023; Federal Bureau of Investigation, 2023), it becomes evident that these vulnerabilities are not isolated but contribute to a wider pattern of risk.

Despite these findings, it is important to acknowledge that not all organisations or individuals are equally vulnerable. Variations in security practices, awareness levels and technological infrastructure may influence susceptibility to such attacks. Furthermore, while the case study provides a compelling example, it represents a single incident and may not fully capture the diversity of attack methods or contexts. This highlights a limitation within the research, as broader generalisations must be made cautiously when based on a limited number of real-world examples.

5.4.3 JUSTIFICATION FOR A STRUCTURED FRAMEWORK

Given the convergence of technological capability and behavioural vulnerability identified throughout this research, there is a clear need for a structured approach to mitigating AI enabled phishing attacks. As highlighted by ENISA (2023), effective cybersecurity strategies must extend beyond awareness and incorporate practical, behaviour focused interventions. The findings of this study support this perspective, demonstrating that awareness alone is insufficient without consistent application of verification practices.

A structured framework offers the potential to address this gap by providing clear guidance on how to identify, verify and respond to suspicious communication. By integrating multiple layers of defence, such as detection, verification, presentation and response, a framework can support both individuals and organisations in managing risk more effectively. This aligns with broader cybersecurity principles, which emphasise the importance of layered security and defence in depth strategies in addressing complex threats (ENISA, 2023)

However, it is also important to consider the limitations of frameworks as a solution. While structured approaches can improve consistency and awareness, their effectiveness is dependent on user compliance and organisational implementation. In practice, individuals may fail to follow established procedures, particularly in high pressure situations where emotional or contextual factors influence decision-making (Hadnagy, 2018) as well as these frameworks may struggle to keep pace with rapidly evolving AI technologies, potentially becoming outdated if not regularly updated. These limitations highlight the need for flexibility and ongoing adaptation in any proposed mitigation strategy

CHAPTER 6: MULTI-LAYERED FRAMEWORKS FOR ADDRESSING DEEPFAKE-ENABLED VISHING THREATS

6.1 INTRODUCTION TO PROPOSED FRAMEWORKS

Building upon the findings presented in chapters 4 and 5, this chapter introduces a structured framework designed to support the identification and mitigation of AI enabled vishing attacks. The need for such a framework arises from the alignment of technological advancement⁵s and human behaviour vulnerability identified throughout this research. As demonstrated through quantitative datasets, questionnaire analysis and case study evaluation, existing approaches to fraud prevention are increasingly insufficient in addressing the evolving nature of AI-driven social engineering.

As identified by ENISA (2023), effective cybersecurity strategies must extend beyond awareness and incorporate practical, behaviour focused interventions. This research supports that position, highlighting a gap between user awareness and the consistent application of verification behaviours. While individuals may recognise the risks associated with AI generated scams, the findings indicate that this awareness does not reliably translate into secure decision making, particularly in high pressure or emotionally driven scenarios.

As well as this, the case study analysis demonstrates how AI generated voice technology can successfully exploit organisational structures and trust-based communication, reinforcing arguments presented by Hadnagy (2018) regarding the role of authority and familiarity in social engineering attacks. When considered alongside the increasing financial losses identified within UK and US fraud datasets (UK Finance, 2023; Federal Bureau of investigation, 2023), it becomes more evident that AI enabled vishing represents a growing and systemic threat that requires a more structured response.

In response to these challenges, this chapter proposes two complementary frameworks, tailored to different contexts of risk exposure:

1. A public-focused framework, designed to support individual users in identifying and responding to potential vishing attempts in everyday scenarios.
2. An organisational framework, designed to address structural, procedural and behavioural vulnerabilities within companies and institutional environments.

This distinction reflects the findings of this research, which indicate that while both groups are vulnerable to AI enabled vishing, the nature of threat vulnerability differs. Individuals are primarily exposed through personal communication and emotional manipulation whereas organisations face additional risks associated with hierarchical structures, financial processes and internal communication systems.

Both frameworks are structured around four key components: detection, verification, prevention and response. These components represent the core stages of interaction within a potential vishing scenario, enabling users to recognise suspicious activity, validate communication, implement preventative controls and respond activity, and respond effectively to incidents. While the foundational structure remains consistent, the application of each component differs between the public and organisational contexts to reflect their unique risk environments.

This dual framework approach aligns with established cybersecurity principles, which emphasise the importance of context specific security strategies. As highlighted by ENISA (2023), effective mitigation requires not only technical controls but also an understanding of user behaviour and organisational processes. By tailoring the framework to distinct user groups, this research aims to provide a more practical and applicable model for reducing susceptibility to AI enabled vishing attacks.

However, it is important to acknowledge that no framework can fully eliminate risk. As discussed in previous sections, the effectiveness of any mitigation strategy is dependent on user compliance, organisational culture and the ongoing evolution of AI technologies. As such the frameworks proposed in this chapter should be viewed as adaptive tools designed to support risk reduction rather than definitive solutions.

The following sections will outline the structure, components and application of both frameworks in detail, demonstrating how they can be used to address the vulnerabilities throughout this research.

6.2 FRAMEWORK STRUCTURE OVERVIEW

6.2.1 CONCEPTUAL DESIGN OF THE FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework is designed as a multi-layered model for identifying and mitigating AI-enabled vishing attacks. It is structured around four key stages of interaction: Detection, verification, prevention and response. These stages reflect the typical lifecycle of a vishing attempt, from initial contact through to post incident handling.

This design aligns with established cybersecurity principles, particularly the concept of defence in depth, which emphasises the use of multiple layers of protection to reduce overall risk (ENISA, 2023) rather than relying on a single point of defence, the framework integrates behavioural, procedural and technological elements to provide a more comprehensive approach to security.

As well as this, the framework is informed by social engineering theory, which highlights the importance of human factors in successful cyber-attacks. As argued by Hadnagy (2018) attackers exploit predictable behavioural patterns such as trust, urgency and authority. By structuring the framework around stages that directly address these vulnerabilities, the model aims to reduce susceptibility to manipulation at each point of interaction.

6.2.2 CORE COMPONENTS OF THE FRAMEWORK

The framework consists of four interconnected components, each addressing a specific aspect of the vishing attack process:

- Detection – Recognising potential indicators of a fraudulent or suspicious communication
- Verification – Confirming the legitimacy of the communication through independent means
- Prevention – implementing proactive measures to reduce the likelihood of successful attacks
- Response – taking appropriate action following identification of a suspected or confirmed attack

Each component is designed to function both independently and as part of a broader system. This ensures that even if one layer is bypassed, additional safeguards remain in place, reducing the overall likelihood of a successful attack. The Table below summarises the core components of the proposed framework, outlining their purpose and role within the overall model.

Component	Purpose	Key Focus	Example Application
<i>Detection</i>	Identify potential signs of vishing attempts	Awareness of red flags (urgency, unfamiliar requests, impersonation)	Recognising unusual requests for financial information
<i>Verification</i>	Confirm legitimacy of communication	Independent validation methods	Calling back using a trusted number
<i>Prevention</i>	Reduce likelihood of successful attacks	Proactive controls and education	Training, policies, pre agreed verification methods
<i>Response</i>	Manage and mitigate impact of attacks	Incident handling and reporting	Reporting fraud, halting transactions

Table 8 - Overview of Framework Components

The structure presented in Table 6.2 demonstrates how each component contributes to a layered defence strategy. While detection focuses on initial recognition, verification provides a critical checkpoint before action is taken. Prevention strengthens overall resilience and response ensures that any incidents are managed effectively

6.2.3 ADAPTATION ACROSS CONTEXTS

While the core structure of the framework remains consistent, its application varies depending on the context in which it will be used, as identified in previous chapters, individuals and organisations face different types of risk and operate within different communication environments.

For individual users the framework emphasises simplicity and accessibility, focusing on practical behaviours that can be applied in everyday situations. This includes recognising common scam indicators and applying straightforward verification methods.

On the other hand, the organisational framework incorporates formal processes and controls, reflecting the complexity of business environments. This includes structured verification procedures, internal policies and role-based responsibilities, which are necessary to manage higher value transactions and hierarchical communication structures.

This distinction ensures that the framework is not only theoretically robust but also practically applicable across different sectors/user groups, increasing its overall effectiveness.

6.2.4 LIMITATIONS OF THE FRAMEWORK STRUCTURE

While the proposed framework provides a structured approach to mitigating AI enabled phishing attacks, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. As highlighted in previous research, the effectiveness of any security framework is dependent on user compliance and consistent implementation (ENISA, 2023)

In practice individuals may fail to follow verification procedures, particularly in high pressure situations where emotional or contextual factors influence decision making (Hadnagy, 2018). As well as this, organisations may encounter challenges in enforcing policies or ensuring that all employees adhere to the established protocols.

Furthermore, the rapidly evolving nature of AI technologies presents an ongoing challenge. As attackers develop more sophisticated methods of deception, frameworks must be continuously updated to remain effective. This showcases the need for adaptability and ongoing evaluation within any proposed security model.

6.3 PUBLIC FRAMEWORK FOR IDENTIFYING AND MITIGATING AI-ENABLED PHISHING

6.3.1 OVERVIEW OF THE PUBLIC FRAMEWORK

The public focused framework is designed to support individual users in identifying and responding to potential AI enabled phishing attacks within everyday communication scenarios. As identified in previous findings, individuals are particularly vulnerable to social engineering due to reliance on trust, emotional influence and informal verification behaviours. While awareness of AI generated scams is increasing, this research has demonstrated that awareness alone does not consistently translate into secure decision making.

As argued by Hadnagy (2018), social engineering attacks are most effective when they exploit predictable human behaviours, including trust in familiar voices and responses to urgency. This is further supported by ENISA (2023), which suggests that user focused cybersecurity strategies must prioritise behavioural intervention rather than solely informational awareness. The public framework therefore focuses on simple, repeatable actions that individuals can apply in real time situations.

The framework is structured around the four core components identified in Section 6.2: detection, verification, prevention and response. Each component is adapted to ensure accessibility and ease of use, recognising that individuals may not possess advanced technical knowledge or formal training in cybersecurity.

6.3.2 DETECTION (PUBLIC CONTEXT)

Detection within the public framework focuses on recognising behavioural and contextual indicators of potential vishing attempts. As identified in questionnaire findings, individuals often rely on intuition when assessing suspicious communication, however the increasing realism of AI generated voices reduces the reliability of this approach.

Key indicators include:

- Increasing awareness of common vishing techniques and AI-generated scams
- Establishing verification habits as standard practice
- Limiting the sharing of personal information that could be used in impersonation

As indicated by ENISA (2023) preventative strategies are most effective when they are embedded into routine behaviour. This research supports that position, highlighting that inconsistent application of security behaviours increases vulnerability, even among individuals who are aware of potential risks.

6.3.3 VERIFICATION (PUBLIC CONTEXT)

Verification represents the most critical stage within the public framework, as it provides a direct opportunity to prevent fraudulent actions. As highlighted in both the case study and questionnaire findings, failure to verify communication is a key factor contributing to successful attacks. The framework emphasises the use of independent verification methods, including:

- Calling back using a known and trusted phone number
- Confirming requests through a separate communication channel (e.g. text, email)
- Using pre-agreed verification questions or phrases

This aligns with ENISA (2023) which emphasises the importance of multi-channel verification in reducing susceptibility to social engineering attacks. The introduction of pre-agreed verification phrases is particularly relevant in the context of AI voice deepfakes, as it provides an additional layer of authentication that is difficult for attackers to replicate without prior knowledge.

6.3.4 PREVENTION (PUBLIC CONTEXT)

Prevention within the public framework focuses on reducing overall susceptibility to vishing attacks through proactive behaviours. This includes both awareness and preparation, ensuring that individuals are equipped to respond effectively before an attack occurs. Key preventative measures include:

- Increasing awareness of common vishing techniques and AI generated scams
- Establishing verification habits as standard practice
- Limiting the sharing of personal information that could be used in impersonation

As indicated by ENISA (2023) preventative strategies are most effective when they are embedded into routine behaviour. This research supports that position, highlighting that inconsistent application of security behaviours increases vulnerability, even among individuals who are aware of potential risks

6.3.5 RESPONSE (PUBLIC CONTEXT)

The response component of this framework focuses on the actions taken once a suspicious or confirmed vishing attempt has been identified. Given the spread at which financial fraud can occur as demonstrated in both datasets and case study findings, timely and appropriate response is essential in minimising impact. Recommended actions include:

- Ending the call immediately
- Reporting the incident to relevant authorities or service providers
- Contacting financial institutions if sensitive information or transactions are involved

This aligns with guidance from organisations such as the Federal Bureau of Investigation (2023) which emphasises rapid reporting as a key factor in mitigating financial loss and supporting investigation efforts.

6.3.6 SUMMARY OF PUBLIC FRAMEWORK

The Table below summarises the application of the framework within a public context, highlighting key actions associated with each component.

Component	Public Application	Key Behaviour
<i>Detection</i>	Recognising suspicious communication	Identify urgency, unusual requests, impersonation
<i>Verification</i>	Confirming legitimacy	Use callback, secondary channels, verification phrases
<i>Prevention</i>	Reducing exposure to risk	Build awareness, limit data sharing, establish habits
<i>Response</i>	Managing incidents	End communication, report, secure accounts

Table 9 - Public Framework Overview

The public framework provides a structured yet accessible approach to mitigating AI-enabled vishing risks. By focusing on behavioural consistency and practical application, it aims to address the gap between awareness and action identified throughout this research.

6.4 OVERVIEW OF THE ORGANISATIONAL FOR IDENTIFYING AND MITIGATING AI-ENABLED VISHING

6.4.1 OVERVIEW OF THE ORGANISATIONAL FRAMEWORK

The organisational framework is designed to address the structural, procedural and behavioural vulnerabilities identified within companies and institutional environments. As demonstrated in the case study analysed in Chapter 4, organisations are particularly susceptible to AI enabled vishing attacks due to reliance on hierarchical communication, trust-based decision making and high value financial processes

As argued by Hadnagy (2018), social engineering attacks are often more effective in structured environments where authority is clearly defined. This research supports that perspective, showing that employees may be less likely to challenge requests perceived to originate from senior figures. The integration of AI generated voice technology further amplifies this vulnerability by increasing the realism and credibility of impersonation attempts.

When considered alongside fraud datasets from the UK and United States, which indicate sustained increases in financial losses (UK Finance, 2023, Federal Bureau of Investigation, 2023), it becomes evident that organisations are a primary target for financially motivated cybercrime. The organisational framework therefore extends beyond individual behavioural responses to incorporate formal controls, policies and verification procedures ensuring a more robust and systematic approach to risk mitigation.

6.4.2 DETECTION (ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT)

Detection within an organisational context requires a more structured and collective approach when compared to individual users, rather than relying solely on personal judgement, organisations must implement systems and processes that support the identification of suspicious activity. Key detection measures include:

- Monitoring for unusual financial requests or deviations from standard procedures
- Identifying anomalies in communication patterns (e.g unexpected requests from senior staff)
- Implementing internal reporting mechanisms for suspicious interactions

These measures align with ENISA (2023) which emphasises the importance of organisational awareness and monitoring systems in identifying cyber threats. However, the findings of this research suggest that detection alone is insufficient, particularly when AI generated communication closely mimics legitimate interactions. This reinforces the need for additional layers of verification and control.

6.4.3 VERIFICATION (ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT)

Verification is a critical component of the organisational framework, particularly in relation to financial transactions and sensitive communications. As demonstrated in the case study the absence of effective verification procedures was a key factor contributing to the success of the attack. The framework proposes the implementation of formalised verification protocols, including:

- Mandatory callback procedures using verified contact details
- Multi-person authorisation for high value transactions
- Use of pre-agreed authentication phrases for internal communication
- Separation of duties to reduce reliance on single points of decision making

These measures align with established cybersecurity and financial control principles, which emphasise redundancy and accountability. The introduction of pre-agreed authentication phrases, particularly when periodically updated, provides an additional layer of protection against AI-generated voice impersonation.

6.4.4 PREVENTION (ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT)

Prevention within organisations focuses on embedding security practices into organisational culture and operational processes. This includes both technical controls and behavioural interventions aimed at reducing susceptibility to social engineering attacks. Key preventative measures include:

- Regular employee training focused on AI-enabled threats and social engineering tactics
- Development and enforcement of clear communication and verification policies
- Limiting access to sensitive information and implementing least privilege principles

As highlighted by ENISA (2023), effective prevention requires a combination of technical and behavioural approaches. This research supports that position, demonstrating that technological controls alone are insufficient when attacks target human decision making processes

6.4.5 RESPONSE (ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXT)

The response component focuses on organisational actions following the identification of a suspected or confirmed phishing attack. Given the potential financial and reputational impact, organisations must be prepared to respond quickly and effectively. Recommended response measures include:

- Immediate suspension or review of suspicious transactions
- Internal reporting and escalation procedures
- Notification of relevant authorities and financial institutions
- Post incident analysis to identify weaknesses and improve controls

As identified by the federal Bureau of Investigation (2023) rapid response is critical in limiting financial losses and supporting investigative processes. The findings of this research further emphasise the importance of structured response mechanisms, particularly in high-risk environments.

6.4.6 SUMMARY OF ORGANISATIONAL FRAMEWORK

The table below summarises the application of the framework within an organisational context, highlighting key controls and processes associated with each component.

Component	Organisational Application	Key Control Measures
<i>Detection</i>	Monitoring and identifying suspicious activity	Anomaly detection, internal reporting systems
<i>Verification</i>	Confirming legitimacy of requests	Callback procedures, multi person approval, authentication phrases
<i>Prevention</i>	Reducing organisational vulnerability	Training,, policies, access control
<i>Response</i>	Managing incidents and minimising impact	Escalation procedures, transaction review, reporting

Table 10 - Organisational Framework Overview

The organisational framework provides a structured and comprehensive approach to mitigating AI-enabled phishing risks within business environments. By integrating behavioural awareness, procedural controls and technical safeguards, it addresses the vulnerabilities identified throughout this research while remaining adaptable to different organisational contexts.

6.5 FRAMEWORK EVALUATION AND PRACTICAL APPLICATION

6.5.1 RECOGNITION OF SUSPICIOUS COMMUNICATION

An essential component of both public and organisational frameworks is the ability to accurately identify suspicious communication. As identified throughout this research AI generated voice impersonation reduces reliance on traditional detection cues, making it necessary to adopt more structured recognition strategies. As stated by Hadnagy (2018) social engineering attacks frequently rely on predictable behaviour triggers, including urgency, authority and emotional manipulation. To support practical application, the framework identifies several key indicators of suspicious communication, including:

- Urgent or time critical language (e.g “this needs to be done immediately”)
- Requests involving financial transactions or sensitive data
- Impersonation of authority figures (e.g senior staff, family members)
- Requests that deviate from normal communication patterns

In addition to behavioural indicators, specific linguistic cues and phrases may suggest potential fraud. Examples include:

- “I need you to act quickly”
- “This is confidential, don’t tell anyone”
- “I can’t explain right now, just trust me”

These indicators align with established social techniques (Hadnagy, 2018). However, as AI technologies improve such cues may become more subtle or contextually accurate, reducing their reliability as standalone indicators.

6.5.2 VERIFICATION TECHNIQUES AND PROCEDURES

Verification represents the most critical control within the proposed framework, as it provides a direct mechanism for preventing fraudulent actions. As highlighted in the case study, the absence of effective verification procedures enabled the success of the attack. The framework proposes several practical verification techniques, including:

Multi-Channel Verification

- Confirm requests using an alternative communication method
- Example: Receiving a phone call, verify using email or known contact number

Callback Procedures

- Terminate the initial call and independently contact the individual

- Use pre-existing, trusted contact details (not those provided in the call)

Pre-agreed Authentication Phrases

- Establish shared phrases or questions between trusted parties
- Rotate phrases periodically (e.g 30-60 days) to reduce compromise risk

Multi-Person Verification

- Require approval from multiple individuals for high-risk actions
- Reduces reliance on a single point of failure

These techniques align with ENISA (2023), which emphasises layered verification and independent validation as effective countermeasures against social engineering attacks. The introduction of dynamic authentication phrases also reflects a proactive adaptation to AI driven impersonation threats.

6.5.3 REPORTING AND RESPONSE PROCEDURES

Effective reporting and response mechanisms are critical in limiting the impact of vishing attacks. As identified in fraud datasets and supported by the Federal Bureau of Investigation (2023), rapid response can significantly influence the likelihood of recovering financial losses. The framework recommends the following reporting procedures:

Public Context

- Report incidents to financial institutions immediately
- Notify national fraud reporting services (e.g Action Fraud in the UK)
- Secure personal accounts and monitor for suspicious activity

Organisational Context

- Escalate incidents to financial institutions immediately
- Notify national fraud reporting services (e.g Action Fraud in the UK)
- Report to relevant regulatory or law enforcement bodies

These procedures emphasise the importance of timeliness and escalation, ensuring that incidents are addressed before further damage can occur.

6.5.4 EVALUATION OF FRAMEWORK EFFECTIVENESS

The proposed framework demonstrates a strong alignment with both the empirical findings of this research and existing literature on social engineering and cybersecurity. A key strength lies in its multi-layered structure, which integrates detection, verification, prevention and response mechanisms. This reflects the defence in depth approach advocated by ENISA (2023), which argues that effective cybersecurity strategies must incorporate multiple layers of control to address complex and evolving threats. The findings of this research support this position as both questionnaire and case study demonstrate that reliance on a single control, such as user awareness is insufficient in preventing AI-enabled vishing attacks.

The framework also directly addresses the human behavioural vulnerabilities identified throughout this study. As stated by Hadnagy (2018) social engineering attacks are most effective when exploiting trust, authority and urgency. These principles were consistently observed across all data sources, including questionnaire responses, which highlighted emotional manipulation and inconsistent verification behaviours and the case study, which demonstrated how authority-based impersonation enabled financial fraud. By embedding structured verification procedures and recognition techniques, the framework provides a practical mechanism for mitigating these behavioural risks.

However, the effectiveness of the framework must be considered in relation to the limitations identified within the datasets and real-world application. Analysis of UK and US fraud data indicates a sustained increase in financial losses

(UK Finance, 2023, Federal Bureau of Investigation, 2023), suggesting that existing mitigation strategies are not fully effective at scale. While the framework addresses key vulnerabilities identified in this research, it does not guarantee prevention, particularly as datasets do not explicitly distinguish AI-driven fraud. This reinforces the conclusion that AI acts as an enhancer of existing threats, rather than a standalone cause and highlights the need for continuous adaptation of mitigation strategies.

A critical distinction within this framework is the differentiation between public and organisational applications, which reflects the differing nature of risk exposure identified in the findings. The public framework is internationally simplified and behaviour focused, recognising that individuals require accessible and easily applicable guidance in real time scenarios. Questionnaire findings indicate that while awareness exists, behavioural consistency is limited, suggesting that overly complex procedures may reduce compliance. Therefore, a refined framework, focused on key actions such as recognising suspicious communication and applying basic verification techniques, is more effective for individual users.

On the other hand, the organisational framework adopts a more detailed and structured approach, reflecting the increased complexity and risk associated with business environments. The case study provides clear evidence of how organisational structures, particularly hierarchical communication and financial processes, can be exploited in phishing attacks. As such organisations benefit from more comprehensive controls including multi-person verification, formal policies and structured reporting procedures. This aligns with ENISA (2023), which emphasises the importance of organisational level controls in mitigating cyber risk. The increased detail within the organisational level controls on managing cyber risk. The increased detail within the organisational framework enhances security by reducing reliance on individual decision making and introducing multiple layers of accountability.

Despite these strengths, the framework is subject to several limitations particularly in the context of the evolving threat landscape. One of the most significant challenges is the ongoing “arms race” between attackers and defenders, where advancements in AI technology enable increasingly sophisticated forms of impersonation (ENISA, 2023). As voice synthesis becomes more realistic and context-aware, the effectiveness of detection and verification strategies may diminish over time. This dynamic environment requires the framework to remain adaptable, with continuous updates to reflect emerging threats.

The integration of AI-based detection technologies presents a potential enhancement to the framework, particularly within organisational contexts. Such systems could analyse audio for signs of manipulation, providing an additional layer of defence beyond human judgment. This aligns with research suggesting that AI can be leveraged defensively to counter AI enabled threats (ENISA, 2023) however, this approach also introduces new challenges. Detection systems may produce false positives or fail to identify increasingly sophisticated deepfakes and over reliance on automated tools may reduce user vigilance. This highlights the importance of maintaining a balance between technological and behavioural controls.

As well as this the implementation of detailed organisational procedures may introduce practical and operational constraints. Measures such as multi-layer verification and strict authentication protocols can increase time and complexity, potentially impacting efficiency in fast paced environments. On the other hand, overly simplified frameworks for the public may not provide sufficient protection in complex scenarios. These trade-offs highlight the importance of context specific design, ensuring that frameworks are both effective and usable within their intended environments.

Overall, the proposed framework provides a comprehensive and adaptable approach to mitigating AI enabled phishing risks. Its strengths lie in the integration of behavioural insights, empirical findings and established cybersecurity principles. However, its effectiveness is inherently dependent on user behaviour, organisational implementation and the ongoing evolution of AI technologies. As such, the framework should be viewed as a dynamic and evolving model, requiring continuous refinement to remain effective within an increasingly complex threat landscape.

CHAPTER 7: CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS AND REFLECTION

7.1 CONCLUSION

7.1.1 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

This research aimed to investigate how artificial intelligence, particularly deepfake voice technology has influenced and amplified the development of vishing attacks, while also evaluating effective mitigation strategies. In addressing this, the findings demonstrate that AI has significantly enhanced the scale, realism and success rate of social engineering attacks, directly fulfilling the objective of analysing the evolving threat landscape. The integration of quantitative datasets, questionnaire data and case study evidence ensures that this conclusion is not based on isolated observations but rather on a triangulated body of evidence.

The first research objective, which focused on analysing trends in vishing and fraud is strongly supported by the dataset findings. The consistent rise in financial losses across both UK and US datasets confirms that fraud is increasing not only in frequency but also in impact. While these datasets do not specifically isolate AI incidents, the timeline of growth aligns closely with the accessibility of AI tools, supporting the conclusion that AI acts as a force multiplier rather than a standalone cause. This demonstrates that the objective has been met though with acknowledged limitations.

As well as this the research successfully meets its objective of providing a comprehensive understanding of AI-enabled vishing by combining statistical trends with behavioural and contextual insights. Rather than relying purely on numerical data, the research incorporates human factors and real-world application, ensuring that the findings are both analytically robust and practically relevant. This strengthens the validity of the conclusions and confirms that the research objectives have been addressed in a holistic and integrated manner.

7.1.2 BEHAVIOURAL INSIGHTS AND OBJECTIVE EVALUATION

A central objective of this research was to examine how individuals respond to AI-enabled vishing attacks and to identify weaknesses in human decision-making. The questionnaire findings clearly demonstrate that while awareness of AI threats is relatively high, this does not consistently translate into secure behaviour. This directly fulfils the objective of identifying behavioural vulnerabilities, revealing a critical gap between knowledge and action.

The research shows that participants often overestimate their ability to detect scams, particularly in high pressure scenarios involving urgency or authority. This aligns with established social engineering theory and confirms that human factors remain a primary vulnerability, even in technologically advanced threat environments, as such, the objective of understanding user susceptibility has been met not only descriptively but also critically by linking behavioural patterns to psychological principles.

However, it is also important to acknowledge limitations in fully achieving this objective. The questionnaire sample size and demographic may restrict the generalisability of findings. While the results provide strong indicative insight, they may not fully represent wider population behaviour. Despite this, the consistency between questionnaire findings and the literature and case study evidence strengthens confidence in the conclusions, suggesting that the objective has substantiality achieved although with some constraints.

7.1.3 TECHNOLOGICAL IMPACT AND CASE STUDY VALIDATION

Another key objective was to evaluate the role of AI technologies, specifically voice synthesis, in enhancing the effectiveness of vishing attacks. This objective is strongly supported through both literature and the analysed case study. The case study provides clear evidence of how AI generated voice cloning can be used to convincingly impersonate trusted individual, leading to successful financial fraud. This directly validates the research aim of assessing the real-world implications of AI in cybercrime.

The case study also supports the objective of understanding how technological and organisational factors interact. The success of the attack was not solely due to the technology itself but rather the combination of realistic voice replication

and organisational reliance on trust-based communication. This highlights that AI does not replace traditional social engineering techniques but instead enhances them. As such the research successfully meets its objective of evaluating AI as an evolutionary rather than a revolutionary threat.

That said, the reliance on a single primary case study introduces some limitations. While it provides depth and realism, it may not capture the full diversity of AI enabled attacks. Despite this, the alignment between the case study, questionnaire findings and broader literature suggests that the conclusions drawn are both credible and representative. Therefore, this objective can be considered effectively achieved with minor limitations in scope.

7.1.4 EVALUATION OF MITIGATION STRATEGIES AND RESEARCH CONTRIBUTION

The final objective of this research was to develop and evaluate effective mitigation strategies for AI-enabled vishing. This has been addressed through the creation of a dual framework approach, tailored separately for public users and organisations. This directly fulfils the objective by moving beyond analysis into practical application, providing clear and actionable solutions based on the research findings.

The public focused framework addresses behavioural weaknesses identified in the questionnaire, emphasising simplicity and usability to encourage adoption. Meanwhile, the organisational framework responds to vulnerabilities highlighted in the case study, particularly the lack of verification protocols in hierarchical communication. This demonstrates a strong alignment between findings and recommendations, confirming that the mitigation strategies are evidence based rather than theoretical.

However, while the frameworks are logically put together and well supported, they have not been empirically tested in real world environments. This represents a limitation in fully validating their effectiveness, meaning the objective is met in terms of design and justification, but not in terms of practical implementation. Future research would be required to evaluate their real-world impact. Despite this, the research makes a meaningful contribution by providing structured, context aware solutions, therefore successfully fulfilling its final objective.

7.2 EVIDENCE-BASED RECOMMENDATIONS AND STRATEGIC MITIGATION MEASURES

7.2.1 STRENGTHENING INDIVIDUAL AWARENESS AND BEHAVIOUR

The findings from the questionnaire clearly indicate a gap between awareness and practical behaviour, where participants demonstrate knowledge of AI enabled threats but fail to consistently apply verification strategies. This supports existing research which argues that awareness alone is insufficient to prevent social engineering attacks (ENISA, 2023). As such, a key recommendation is the development of behaviour focused training approaches, rather than traditional awareness campaigns.

Strategy	Description	Link to findings	Expected Benefit	Limitation
<i>Scenario-based training</i>	Simulated vishing attacks in controlled environments	Questionnaire shows inconsistent responses under pressure	Improves real time decision making	Resource intensive
<i>Multi-channel verification</i>	Confirming requests using separate communication methods	Participants often rely on single source information	Reduces reliance on trust	May be ignored in urgent situations
<i>Use of authentication phrases</i>	Pre-agreed phrases between trusted individuals	Supports framework developed in chapter 6	Strengthens identity verification	Requires prior setup
<i>Awareness of psychological triggers</i>	Training on urgency, authority, emotional manipulation	Aligns with Hadnagy (2018)	Improves recognition of manipulation tactics	Behavioural habits difficult to change

Table 11 - Behavioural Mitigation Strategies for Individuals

The strategies outlined above directly address the behavioural vulnerabilities identified in the research. Scenario-based training is critical, as it moves beyond theoretical; understanding and allows individuals to experience realistic attack scenario. This aligns with the findings that individuals struggle to apply knowledge in high pressure situations, reinforcing the need for experimental learning.

However, it is important to recognise that behavioural interventions are inherently limited by user compliance. Even with training, individuals may still make errors, particularly in emotionally charged situations. Therefore, while these strategies are necessary, they must be complemented by organisational and technological controls to provide a more comprehensive defence.

7.2.2 ORGANISATIONAL VERIFICATION PROTOCOLS

The case study highlighted a critical vulnerability within organisations, the reliance on trust-based communication without formal verification mechanisms. This directly support the research objective by evaluating how AI-enabled attacks exploit organisational structures. As a result, organisations must implement structured and enforceable verification protocols.

Control Measure	Description	Evidence from Research	Impact	Limitation
<i>Multi-person approval</i>	Require multiple authorisations for high-risk actions	Case study demonstrated single point failure	Reduces fraud significantly	Slows decision-making
<i>Callback verification</i>	Independent confirmation using known contact details	Questionnaire shows lack of verification behaviour	Prevents impersonation success	May delay urgent actions
<i>Defined escalation</i>	Structured response to unusual requests	Case study showed lack of challenge culture	Encourages critical thinking	Requires organisational training
<i>Security-focused culture</i>	Encourage questioning of authority	Hadnagy (2018), authority exploitation	Reduces hierarchal manipulation	Cultural resistance possible

Table 12 - Organisational Mitigation Measures

These measures directly address the weaknesses identified in both the case study and questionnaire findings. Multi person approval and callback verification significantly reduce the likelihood of successful impersonation, as they remove reliance on a single communication channel

However, these controls introduce operational challenges, particularly in fast paced environments where speed is prioritised. This highlights the need to balance security with usability, ensuring that procedures are both effective and practical. Despite these limitations, the increasing sophistication of AI enabled attacks justifies the implementation of such controls.

7.2.3 ADOPTION OF AI-BASED DETECTION TECHNOLOGIES

Given that AI is a key enabler of modern vishing attacks, it is logical that AI should also be used as part of the defensive response. This aligns directly with the research objective of evaluating the role of AI in both enabling and mitigating cyber threats.

Technology	Function	Relevance to Research	Benefit	Limitation
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<i>Voice analysis systems</i>	Detect anomalies in speech patterns	Addresses AI voice cloning risk	Identifies potential impersonation	Increasing accuracy of AI may bypass detection
<i>Behavioural analytics</i>	Monitor unusual request patterns	Linked to case study anomalies	Flags suspicious activity	False positives possible
<i>AI content labelling</i>	Identifies AI-generated content	Supports transparency recommendations	Improves user awareness	Can be removed or bypassed
<i>Fraud detection algorithms</i>	Identify irregular transaction behaviour	Aligns with dataset trends (UK Finance, FBI)	Reduces financial loss	Reactive rather than preventative

Table 13 - AI Based Detection and Monitoring Solutions

The use of AI based detection systems provides a valuable additional layer of defence, particularly in identifying patterns that may not be immediately obvious to human users. This is particularly important given the increasing realism of AI-generated content.

However as highlighted by ENISA (2023), the development of AI detection technologies contributes to an ongoing “arms race” between attackers and defenders. As detection systems improve, so too do evasion techniques, meaning that reliance on AI alone is insufficient. This reinforces the importance of entertaining technological solutions with behavioural and organisational measures.

7.2.4 POLICY AND REGULATORY RECOMMENDATIONS

The research showcased that AI-enabled phishing is not solely a technical issue but also a policy and governance challenge. The increasing accessibility of AI tools suggests that existing regulatory frameworks may not be sufficient to address emerging threats.

Policy Measure	Description	Justification	Impact	Limitation
<i>AI content labelling laws</i>	Mandatory disclosure of AI-generated content	Supports transparency	Improves public awareness	Enforcement challenges
<i>Regulation of AI tools</i>	Restrictions on misuse voice synthesis	Addresses accessibility concerns	Reduces malicious use	May limit innovation
<i>Standardised reporting systems</i>	Centralised reporting of AI fraud incidents	Dataset limitations identified in research	Improves data accuracy	Requires coordination
<i>Industry accountability</i>	Responsibility on tech companies	Reflects user concerns in questionnaire	Encourages proactive measures	Difficult to enforce globally

Table 14 - Policy and Regulatory Measures

These recommendations address broader systemic issues identified within the research, particularly the lack of clear attribution in fraud datasets. Improved regulation and reporting would enhance both preventative and research capabilities. However, regulatory approaches must balance innovation with security, ensuring that beneficial uses of AI are not unnecessarily restricted. This highlights the complexity of implementing policy level solutions and reinforces the need for collaboration between governments, industry and researchers.

7.2.5 FUTURE RESEARCH AND CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

The research successfully meets its objectives, however, there are several limitations that highlight the need for further investigation. In particular, the lack of AI specific fraud datasets limits the ability to establish causation, while the questionnaire sample size may restrict generalisability

Future research should focus on developing larger and more targeted datasets, as well as incorporating experimental methods such as simulated phishing scenarios. This would provide a more accurate representation of real-world behaviour and strengthen the validity of findings

As well as this, the framework developed in this research should be tested in real world environments to evaluate their effectiveness. Given the rapid evolution of AI technologies, continuous refinement will be necessary to ensure long term relevance. This aligns with ENISA (2023) which emphasises the need for adaptive approaches in addressing emerging cyber threats.

7.3 REFLECTION ON METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

7.3.1 RATIONALE FOR METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

The selection of an appropriate research methodology was a critical component of this project, as the research aimed to address multiple objectives spanning trend analysis, behavioural evaluation, technological assessment and mitigation development. To achieve this, a mixed method approach was adopted, combining quantitative questionnaire responses and real-world case study evaluation. This approach was selected to ensure that both the scale of AI enabled phishing, and the underlying behavioural mechanisms could be examined comprehensively.

This methodological choice aligns with Creswell (2014) who argues that mixed methods research is particularly effective when investigating complex, interdisciplinary problems that cannot be fully understood through a single approach. In the content of this research, quantitative datasets were essential in addressing the objective of understanding user behaviour. The case study further enabled the evaluation of how these factors interact in real world scenarios, directly contributing to the objective of assessing the practical implications of AI-enabled attacks.

Furthermore, the methodology supports the final research objective of developing mitigation strategies. By integrating findings across all data sources, the research was able to move beyond descriptive analysis and produce a context aware dual framework, grounded in both empirical evidence and behavioural insight. This demonstrates that the chosen methodology was not only appropriate for data collection, but also instrumental in enabling meaningful application of findings.

7.3.2 COMPARISON WITH ALTERNATIVE METHODOLOGIES

While the mixed methods approach was ultimately selected, alternative methodologies were considered and evaluated to determine their suitability for addressing the research objectives. Each approach offers distinct strengths, however, when assessed against the requirements of this study, they present significant limitations.

Methodology	Strengths	Limitations	Relevance to Objectives	Reason for Rejection
<i>Quantitative Only</i>	Strong statistical trends and scalability	No insight into behaviour or decision making	Supports trend analysis objective only	Cannot explain why attacks succeed
<i>Qualitative Only</i>	In-depth understanding of user behaviour	Limited generalisability and lack of empirical scale	Supports behavioural objective only	Cannot demonstrate overall impact
<i>Experimental</i>	Realistic behavioural observation	Ethical constraints, complexity, time limitations	Highly relevant to behavioural objective	Not feasible within project scope
<i>Mixed Methods (Chosen)</i>	Combines scale, behaviour and context	More complex to design and analyse	Addresses all objectives	Most suitable approach

Table 15 - Methodological Comparison and Suitability

A purely quantitative methodology would have allowed for detailed statistical modelling of fraud trends; however, it would fail to address the behavioural aspects identified as central to the success of vishing attacks. As demonstrated in the questionnaire findings, understanding how individuals respond under pressure is critical to developing effective mitigation strategies, which cannot be captured through numerical data alone.

On the other hand, a purely qualitative approach would provide valuable insight into user perceptions and experiences but would lack the empirical foundation necessary to demonstrate the scale and significance of the issue. Without dataset analysis, it would be difficult to justify claims regarding the increasing prevalence of fraud or the broader impact of AI technologies, weakening the overall credibility of the research.

An experimental approach, such as a simulated vishing scenario would arguably provide the most accurate presentation of real-world behaviour. However, this approach was not feasible within the constraints of the due to time limitations, ethical considerations and the complexity of designing realistic AI driven interactions. Despite this, it remains a valuable direction for future research, as it could further validate behavioural findings identified in this study.

7.3.3 STRENGTHS OF THE CHOSEN METHODOLOGY

The mixed methods approach offers several key strengths that directly contributed to the success of this research. Most notably, it enabled triangulation of data, where findings from datasets, questionnaire responses and case study analysis could be compared and validated against one another. This strengthens the reliability of conclusions and reduces the likelihood of bias associated with a single data source.

This triangulation is particularly evident in the identification of the awareness behaviour gap, where questionnaire findings align with existing literature (ENISA, 2023) and are further supported by the case study. Similarly, dataset trends indicating increasing fraud provide macro level validation of the threat, while qualitative insights explain the mechanisms behind this growth. This demonstrates how the methodology supports both range and depth of analysis.

As well as this, the methodology directly enabled the development of the dual framework presented in chapter 6. By combining behavioural insights with empirical data and real-world examples, the framework is grounded in multiple forms of evidence, increasing its practical relevance. This highlights that the methodology was not only effective for analysis but also essential for achieving the research objective of developing mitigation strategies.

7.3.4 LIMITATIONS AND CRITICAL EVALUATION OF METHODOLOGY

Despite its strengths, the chosen methodology is not without limitations, which must be critically evaluated. One of the primary limitations is the reliance on secondary datasets that do not explicitly distinguish AI enabled fraud from traditional scams. This restricts the ability to establish a direct causal relationship between AI technologies and the observed increase in fraud, meaning that conclusions must be interpreted with caution.

As well as this, the questionnaire data is based on self-reported behaviour, which may not accurately reflect real world actions. Participants may overestimate their ability to identify scams or provide socially desirable responses. This limitation is particularly relevant given the research findings that highlight discrepancies between perceived and actual behaviour. As such, while the questionnaire provides valuable insight, it may not fully capture real world decision making processes.

Furthermore, the case study analysis, while valuable for providing real world context is limited in scope. The reliance on a small number of documented incidents may not fully represent the diversity of AI enabled vishing attacks. Despite these limitations, the consistency of findings across all data sources suggests that the overall conclusions remain valid. However, future research should aim to address these limitations through expanded datasets, experimental approaches and broader case study analysis.

7.3.5 OVERALL EVALUATION OF METHODOLOGICAL EFFECTIVENESS

Overall, the mixed methods approach can be considered the most appropriate and effective methodology for this research, as it successfully addresses all stated objectives. By integrating quantitative, qualitative and contextual data,

the research achieves a comprehensive understanding of AI-enabled vishing, encompassing both the scale of the threat and the mechanisms through which it operates.

The methodology also demonstrates strong alignment between research design and outcomes. Each method contributes directly to specific objectives, and the integration of findings supports the development of practical mitigation strategies. This coherence between methodology, findings and application is a key strength of the research and reflects a high level of methodological awareness.

While limitations exist, they are acknowledged and critically evaluated, demonstrating an understanding of the challenges associated with researching emerging technologies. The inclusion of these limitations does not weaken the research, rather it strengthens its credibility by providing a balanced and transparent evaluation. As such, the methodology can be regarded as both robust and appropriate.

7.4 TIME MANAGEMENT AND PROJECT PLANNING

7.4.1 PLANNED VERSUS ACTUAL PROJECT PROGRESSION

Effective time management was initially approached through a structured project plan, with each stage, literature review, data collection, analysis, framework development and writing, allocated a specific timeframe. However, as research progressed, it became clear that the project did not follow a strictly linear trajectory. Instead, the workflow evolved into an iterative process, where earlier sections were revisited and refined as new insights emerged. This was particularly evident in chapters 4,5 and 6 where analysis, discussion and framework development became increasingly interconnected.

The initial plan underestimated the complexity of integrating multiple research methods. While data collection stages such as dataset acquisition and questionnaire distribution were completed within expected time frames, the analysis and synthesis stages required significantly more time. This was due to the need to ensure consistency across all data sources, particularly when linking dataset trends, behavioural findings and case study evidence. As a result, sections that were originally intended to be completed independently became dependent on one another, extending the overall timeline.

This deviation from the planned schedule highlights a key insight, that research projects involving mixed methods methodologies require flexibility and adaptability. While structured planning remains important, the ability to adjust timelines and schedules in response to emerging complexity is essential for maintaining quality. For example, in this case, the extended time spent on analysis and integration ultimately improved the depth and coherence of the research, demonstrating that deviations from the plan were not necessarily negative, but rather indicative of deeper engagement with the subject matter.

7.4.2 DETAILED TIME ALLOCATION AND CRITICAL EVALUATION

Project Stage	Planned Duration	Actual Duration	Tasks Undertaken	Reason for Deviation	Impact on Project
<i>Literature Review</i>	2 weeks	3-4 weeks	Academic sourcing defining scope, Understanding AI as well as social engineering	Underestimated theoretical depth and interdisciplinary nature	Strengthened theoretical foundation
<i>Dataset Analysis</i>	2 weeks	3-4 weeks	Data cleaning, graph creation, regression analysis interpretation	Required accuracy, validation and justification of trends	Improved reliability of findings
<i>Case Study Research</i>	1 week	1-2 weeks	Source validation, cross referencing (BBC, Forbes)	Needed credible corroboration and contextual understanding	Increased validity of real-world application
<i>Chapter 4 (Findings)</i>	2 weeks	3-4 weeks	Writing, restructuring, integrating data sources	Iterative development and refinement	Improved analytical depth

<i>Chapter 5 (Discussion)</i>	2 weeks	3 weeks	Linking all data sources, critical evaluation	High level synthesis required more time than anticipated	Strengthened coherence
<i>Chapter 6 (Framework)</i>	1 week	2-3 weeks	Designing framework, adapting to findings	Expanded from single dual framework approach	Major improvement in contribution
<i>Chapter (Reflection)</i>	1 week	2 weeks	Writing reflective analysis, linking to objectives	Required deeper critical evaluation than expected	Strengthened overall academic quality.

Table 16 - Planned vs Actual Time Allocation

The table demonstrates that nearly all stages exceeded their initial time allocation, with the most significant deviations occurring in analysis, discussion and framework development. This reflects a common issue in research planning, where early stages such as data collection are easier to estimate, while later stages involving critical thinking and synthesis are often underestimated.

A key observation is that qualitative and evaluative tasks consistently required more time than quantitative or procedural tasks. For example, while dataset analysis involved technical processes, the interpretation of results and integration with other findings required substantial additional effort. Similarly, the transition from analysis (Chapter 4) to discussion (Chapter 5) required deeper critical thinking, as it involved linking multiple data sources into a cohesive argument.

Importantly, the increased time spent on these stages had a positive impact on the overall quality of the research. The additional time allowed for refinement, ensuring that findings were consistently aligned with research objectives and that the framework was fully supported by evidence. This suggests that while time management could be improved in terms of initial estimation, the adaptive approach ultimately contributed to a stronger outcome.

7.4.3 ITERATIVE DEVELOPMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON RESEARCH QUALITY

One of the most significant aspects of this project was the shift from a linear workflow to an iterative development process. Rather than completing each chapter in isolation, the research evolved through continuous revision and refinement. For example, insights gained during the discussion phase (chapter 5) directly influenced the development of the framework in chapter 6, while feedback from framework design led to revisions in earlier analytical sections.

This iterative approach reflects the nature of complex research, particularly when multiple data sources are involved. It allowed for a more integrated and cohesive final output as each section was developed in relation to the others. However, it also introduced challenges in time management, as revisions required additional time and disrupted the original schedule. This highlights the trade-off between efficiency and quality, where a more flexible approach can lead to improved outcomes at the cost of increased time investment.

From a critical perspective, the iterative process was essential in enabling the development of the dual framework approach, which was not part of the initial plan. The decision to differentiate between public and organisational frameworks emerged from ongoing analysis, demonstrating how iterative refinement can lead to more sophisticated and context aware solutions. This reinforces the idea that effective research is not static but evolves in response to findings.

7.4.4 KEY LESSONS LEARNED AND FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

A key lesson from this project is the importance of realistic time estimation, particularly for stages involving analysis and critical evaluation. Initial planning focused heavily on data collection and writing, with insufficient consideration given to the time required for synthesis and refinement. Future projects should allocate additional time to these stages, recognising that they are central to achieving high quality outcomes.

Another important insight is the value of flexible planning. While structured timelines provide a useful framework, they must be adaptable to accommodate unexpected complexity. In this project, the ability to adjust timelines allowed for

deeper engagement with the research and ultimately improved the quality of the final output. However, this flexibility should be balanced with clear milestones to ensure that progress remains on track.

Finally, the project highlights the importance of prioritising high impact tasks. While all stages of the research are important, the greatest values were taken from activities such as data integration, critical evaluation and framework development. Future research should focus on allocating time proportionately to these high impact areas, ensuring that effort is directed where it contributes most to overall quality of the work.

7.5 REFLECTION ON LIMITATIONS AND IMPROVEMENTS

7.5.1 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

While this research successfully addressed its core objectives, several limitations must be acknowledged to critically evaluate the validity and reliability of the findings. These primarily relate to data availability, methodological constraints and the evolving nature of artificial intelligence technologies all of which influence the extent to which conclusions can be generalised.

One of the most significant limitations is the reliance on secondary datasets that do not explicitly distinguish between AI enabled fraud and traditional forms of vishing. While the datasets from UK Finance (2023) and the Federal Bureau of Investigation (2023) provide strong evidence of increasing fraud trends, they do not allow for direct attribution of these trends to AI technologies. This limits the ability to fully satisfy the research objective of quantifying the impact of AI as conclusions must be based on correlation rather than causation.

As well as this, the research is constrained by the scope of primary data collection, particularly in relation to the questionnaire. While the questionnaire provided valuable insight into behavioural responses, the sample size and demographic distribution may not fully represent the wider population. As such, findings relating to user behaviour should be interpreted as indicative rather than definitive, highlighting the need for cautious generalisation.

7.5.2 DETAILED EVALUATION OF KEY LIMITATIONS

Limitation	Description	Impact on Findings	Link to Objectives	Severity
<i>Lack of AI specific datasets</i>	Fraud data does not isolate AI enabled incidents	Limit's ability to prove AI causation	Weakness objective: AI impact evaluation	High
<i>Questionnaire sample size</i>	Limited participant diversity	Reduces generalisability of behavioural findings	Affects Objective: Behavioural analysis	Medium
<i>Self-reported responses</i>	Participants may overestimate ability	Behaviour may differ in real scenarios	Impact's reliability of behavioural insights	High
<i>Limited case study scope</i>	Small number of real-world examples	May not reflect full range of attacks	Affects Objective: real world validation	Medium
<i>Rapid AI evolution</i>	Technology constantly advancing	Framework may become outdated	Impacts Objective: mitigation strategies	High

Table 17 - Critical Evaluation of Key Limitations

The limitations outlined above demonstrate that while research provides a strong and coherent analysis it is not without its constraints. The most critical limitation is the lack of AI specific datasets as this directly affects the ability to establish a causal relationship between AI technology and the increase in vishing attacks. This highlights a broader issue within cybersecurity research, where emerging technologies often outpace data collection and classification.

Similarly, the reliance on self-reported questionnaire data introduces potential bias, as participants may not accurately reflect their real-world behaviour. This is particularly significant given that one of the key findings of the research is the gap

between awareness and action. As such the dataset used to identify this gap may itself be subject to the same behavioural inconsistencies it seeks to measure.

7.5.3 METHODOLOGICAL IMPROVEMENTS AND EXPECTED OUTCOMES

In response to the identified limitations, several methodological improvements can be proposed to strengthen future research. One key improvement would be the use of AI specific datasets, which explicitly categorise fraud incidents involving artificial intelligence technologies. This would allow for more accurate measurement of AI’s impact and provide stronger empirical support for conclusions.

Improvement	Description	Addresses Limitation	Expected Outcome
<i>AI-specific datasets</i>	Use datasets that classify AI enabled fraud	Lack of attribution	Stronger casual analysis
<i>Larger sample size</i>	Increase participant diversity and number	Limited generalisability	More representative findings
<i>Experimental design</i>	Simulated vishing scenarios	Self-reported bias	More accurate behavioural data
<i>Multiple case studies</i>	Analyse various industries and scenarios	Limited scope	Broader applicability
<i>Continuous framework updates</i>	Adapt framework to evolving threats	AI evolution	Long term relevance

Table 18 - Proposed Improvements and Expected Outcomes

These improvements highlight the importance of methodological evolution, particularly when researching rapidly developing technologies. The inclusion of experimental methods, such as simulated vishing scenarios, would be particularly valuable in addressing the limitations of self-reported data as it would allow for direct observation of behaviour in realistic conditions.

As well as this, expanding the scope of case study analysis would provide a more comprehensive understanding of how AI enabled vishing operates across different contexts. This would enhance the generalisability of findings and support the development of more robust mitigation strategies.

7.5.4 CRITICAL REFLECTION ON RESEARCH VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

Despite the identified limitations, the research maintains a strong level of validity and reliability due to the use of mixed methods approach. The triangulation of datasets, questionnaire findings and case study analysis ensures that conclusions are supported by multiple sources of evidence, reducing the likelihood of bias.

However, it is important to acknowledge that the validity of the research is influenced by the limitations discussed, particularly in relation to data attribution and behavioural measurement. While the findings are well supported, they should be interpreted within the context of these constraints, recognising that further research is required to fully validate certain conclusions.

Ultimately the critical evaluation of limitations strengthens the research rather than weakening it, as it demonstrates an awareness of methodological constraints and a commitment to academic rigour. By identifying and addressing these limitations, the research provides a transparent and balanced analysis, supporting its overall credibility.

7.6 FINAL REFLECTION

7.6.1 REFLECTION ON RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT AND EVOLUTION

This research project developed significantly beyond its initial scope, both in terms of depth and direction. At the outset, the focus was primarily on examining AI as an emerging technological threat within vishing attacks. However, as the

research progressed, it became evident that AI alone does not define the threat landscape, rather it enhances existing vulnerabilities rooted in human behaviour and organisational processes. This shift in understanding led to a more nuanced approach, where the research evolved from a technology focused investigation to a multi-dimensional analysis combining technological, behavioural and organisational perspectives.

This evolution is particularly evident in the development of the framework presented in Chapter 6. Initially the intention was to produce a single generalised framework for mitigating AI enabled vishing. However, through the integration of questionnaire findings and case study analysis, it became clear that vulnerabilities differ significantly between individuals and organisations. This led to the development of a dual framework approach, which represents a more sophisticated and context aware solution. This change demonstrates the importance of adapting research design in response to emerging findings, rather than adhering rigidly to initial assumptions.

As well as this, this iterative development process highlights the value of continuous critical evaluation throughout the research. Rather than treating each stage as independent, the project required ongoing refinement and integration, ensuring that findings were consistently aligned with research objectives. This approach ultimately strengthened the overall coherence of the research, demonstrating that flexibility and adaptability are essential components of effective research design.

7.6.2 REFLECTION ON ACHIEVEMENT OF RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research objectives outlined at the beginning of the project have been largely achieved, although not without certain limitations. The objective of analysing fraud trends was successfully addressed through the use of quantitative datasets, which demonstrated a clear increase in financial losses associated with vishing attacks. While the inability to isolate AI specific incidents limits the strength of casual conclusions, the findings still provide strong evidence of an evolving threat landscape.

The objective of understanding behavioural vulnerability was also effectively achieved through the questionnaire findings which revealed a clear gap between awareness and action, this insight is particularly significant as it highlights a fundamental limitation in existing cybersecurity approaches that rely heavily on awareness campaigns. However, it is important to recognise that the reliance on self-reported data introduces potential bias, meaning that the findings should be interpreted with caution.

The objective of evaluating the impact of AI technologies was addressed through both literature and case study analysis. The case study provided clear evidence of how AI generated voice impersonation can enhance the effectiveness of social engineering attacks. Finally, the development of the dual framework approach demonstrates that the research successfully achieved its objective of proposing mitigation strategies. While these frameworks have not been empirically tested, they are grounded in the findings of the research and provide a strong foundation for future applications.

7.6.3 REFLECTION ON SKILLS DEVELOPMENT AND ACADEMIC GROWTH

This project has contributed significantly to the development of key academic and analytical skills. One of the most notable areas of growth is in critical thinking and evaluation, particularly in the ability to assess multiple sources of data and integrate them into a cohesive argument. The requirement to link datasets, questionnaire findings and case study evidence within the discussion and framework sections necessitated a high level of analytical precision and consistency.

As well as this, the project enhanced skills in research design and methodology selection, particularly in understanding the strengths and limitations of different approaches. The decision to adopt a mixed methods approach required careful consideration of how different data sources could complement one another and how their integration would support the research objectives. This has provided valuable insight into the importance of methodological alignment in achieving meaningful research outcomes.

The project also improved skills in structured academic writing, particularly in maintaining clarity and coherence across a large and complex document. The iterative nature of the writing process, where sections were continuously refined and

linked, reinforced the importance of organisational and logical progression in academic work. These skills are transferable and will be valuable in future research and professional contexts.

7.6.4 CRITICAL REFLECTION ON LIMITATIONS AND PROJECT CONSTRAINTS

Despite its strengths, the project was subject to several constraints that influenced both the process and outcomes of the research. One of the most significant challenges was the availability and specificity of data, particularly in relation to AI enabled Fraud. The lack of datasets explicitly identifying AI driven incidents limited the ability to establish direct causation, requiring reliance on correlation and supporting evidence.

Time constraints also played a role in shaping the scope of the research. While the project was completed within the required timeframe, certain areas, such as experimental validation of the framework, could not be explored in depth. This highlights the trade off between scope and depth in research, where expanding one aspect may limit the ability to fully develop another.

As well as this, the rapidly evolving nature of AI technologies presents an ongoing challenge. The concept of an “arms race” between attackers and defenders (ENISA, 2023) suggests that mitigation strategies must continuously evolve to remain effective. This means that while the framework developed in this research is relevant at present, it may require adaptation as technologies and attack methods advance.

7.6.5 FUTURE DIRECTION AND PROFESSIONAL RELEVANCE

Looking forward, this research highlights several important directions for future work. The development of AI specific datasets and improved classification of fraud incidents would significantly enhance the ability to analyse the impact of emerging technologies. As well as this the incorporation of experimental methods, such as simulated phishing scenarios would provide more accurate insight into real world behaviour.

The findings of this research also have broader implications beyond the academic context. As AI technologies become increasingly integrated into everyday communication, the risks associated with their misuse are likely to grow. This highlights the importance of developing practical and adaptable mitigation strategies, not only for individuals but also for organisations and policymakers

From a professional perspective, the project has provided valuable insight into the complexities of cybersecurity, particularly the need to consider both technological and human factors. The ability to analyse complex problems, develop structured solutions and critically evaluate outcomes is highly relevant to roles within cybersecurity and related fields.

7.6.6 OVERALL CRITICAL REFLECTION

Overall, this research demonstrates that AI enabled phishing is a complex and evolving threat that cannot be addressed through a single solution. The integration of technological advancement with human behavioural vulnerability creates a dynamic challenge that requires multi-layered and adaptive responses. The research successfully addresses this challenge by combining empirical analysis, behavioural insight and practical application.

A key strength of the project is its ability to move beyond theoretical discussion and provide evidence-based solutions, particularly through the development of the dual framework approach. However, the research also acknowledges its limitations and identifies areas for further development, demonstrating a balanced and critical perspective.

Ultimately this project has provided a comprehensive understanding of AI enabled phishing and contributed to both academic and practical application within the field of cybersecurity. While the threat continues to evolve, the insights and frameworks developed in this research provide a strong foundation for future work, reinforcing the importance of adaptability, critical evaluation and interdisciplinary approaches in addressing modern cyber threats.

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